

**UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID
FACULTAD DE CIENCIAS ECONÓMICAS Y
EMPRESARIALES**

TESIS DOCTORAL

**Teletrabajo y bienestar afectivo: impacto de la proximidad
percibida y la expresión de voz de los trabajadores**

**Telework and affective wellbeing: the impact of perceived
proximity and employee voice**

MEMORIA PARA OPTAR AL GRADO DE DOCTOR

PRESENTADA POR

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Madrid

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0. Resumen de la tesis

Resumen de la tesis

La presente tesis estudia la influencia que la proximidad percibida entre compañeros de trabajo y la voz de los empleados tienen en el bienestar afectivo de los teletrabajadores. El impacto de los constructos mencionados en el bienestar afectivo de 542 profesionales es analizado mediante la técnica de las ecuaciones estructurales. Se evalúan tres antecedentes principales de proximidad percibida: (1) el uso de las Redes Sociales Empresariales (ESNs), (2) la comunicación entre compañeros de trabajo y (3) la identidad compartida entre los mismos. Los tres antecedentes demuestran una relación positiva y significativa con la proximidad percibida, y ésta, a su vez, con el bienestar afectivo. Por el contrario, los resultados obtenidos no apoyan la idea de que los mecanismos de voz mejoren el bienestar de los teletrabajadores. Respecto a la voz indirecta, expresada a través de representantes de los trabajadores, no se observó relación significativa con el bienestar afectivo mientras que, la voz directa, ejercida en redes sociales públicas, deteriora el bienestar afectivo de quienes la practican.

Investigadores y profesionales tienen una necesidad urgente de comprender mejor qué factores contribuyen al bienestar afectivo de los teletrabajadores, como medida clave de atracción y retención del talento en las empresas (Uribetxebarria et al., 2021). El teletrabajo como factor que propicia el bienestar no sólo beneficia a los empleados sino también a los empleadores, a través de la mejora de resultados como el desempeño laboral (Oakman et al., 2020), y el compromiso de la plantilla (Miglioretti et al., 2022).

Investigaciones recientes sobre teletrabajo apuntan a la eficiencia de la comunicación y al apoyo social internos como posibles generadores de bienestar afectivo (Becker et al., 2022; Belostecinic et al., 2022). En línea con esa idea, se han planteado dos preguntas de investigación:

- a) ¿Cuál es el impacto de la proximidad percibida (Wilson et al., 2008) en el bienestar afectivo de los empleados que teletrabajan?
- b) ¿Cuál es el impacto de la expresión de voz en el bienestar afectivo de los teletrabajadores?

Las estructuras sociales suelen volverse frágiles a medida que se intensifica el trabajo desde casa (Charalampous et al., 2019; Yang & Lin, 2022). Esta falta de contacto social es un problema recurrente en entornos de trabajo remoto (Seinsche et al., 2022) que se ve agravado por el hecho que los teletrabajadores parecen tener una mayor necesidad de relación que los empleados sitios en la oficina (Brunelle & Fortín, 2021). Durante el teletrabajo, las comunicaciones espontáneas se reducen al mínimo, poniendo en peligro actividades clave para el rendimiento empresarial como son el intercambio de conocimientos o la innovación (Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021).

Wilson et al. (2008) estudiaron cómo se construye la proximidad percibida entre trabajadores llegando a la conclusión de que compañeros físicamente separados podían desarrollar sentimientos de cercanía más fuerte que los desarrollados por personas que compartían una misma oficina física. A esta situación la denominaron paradoja *lejos-cerca*. La paradoja *lejos-cerca* es de vital importancia para el modelo de investigación de esta tesis. Curiosamente, una paradoja inversa también se manifestaba, es decir, compañeros de trabajo que compartían el mismo espacio de oficina se sentían psicológicamente distantes entre sí. En este sentido, Wilson et al. (2008) señalaron que la distancia física no es un factor determinante de la proximidad percibida en el trabajo.

Los resultados de nuestro estudio confirman que los vínculos psicológicos entre compañeros de trabajo remotos pueden crearse y consolidarse mientras se trabaja desde casa. El uso de las redes sociales corporativas, la comunicación con compañeros de trabajo y la identificación permiten

generar percepción de cercanía entre la fuerza laboral remota. La capacidad de encontrar y "seguir" a colegas de ideas afines en la organización es un recurso necesario en el futuro del trabajo (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020). Los resultados de esta tesis amplían el conocimiento previo sobre relaciones interpersonales en teletrabajo y sugieren un cambio de enfoque, desde la frecuencia de comunicación hacia la distancia psicológica. Las conclusiones derivadas de esta investigación tienen implicaciones importantes para el rediseño los escenarios de trabajo actuales.

El estudio de la voz del empleado se ha segmentado en voz directa e indirecta. De acuerdo con las recomendaciones de los investigadores de voz, se ha examinado el uso de las redes sociales públicas más utilizadas en la actualidad con fines de expresión de voz directa (Martin et al., 2015b). Para la voz indirecta se ha seguido a Barnes et al. (2019), que recomiendan estudiar los mecanismos de expresión de voz teniendo en cuenta su efectividad percibida.

Esta tesis doctoral pone de manifiesto la necesidad de rediseñar las condiciones de teletrabajo en un escenario postpandemia (Carrillo et al., 2021). Los investigadores del teletrabajo han advertido sobre los peligros del aislamiento en el lugar de trabajo, destacando la importancia de las relaciones sociales como medida de contingencia (Adamovic, 2022; Collins et al., 2016; Ruiller et al., 2019). La presente investigación ha tratado de ir un paso más allá ampliando el marco de la paradoja *lejos-cerca* de varias maneras: (1) El constructo de proximidad percibida se ha examinado en una gran muestra de datos de teletrabajadores, (2) El uso efectivo de las redes sociales internas se ha propuesto como un nuevo antecedente de proximidad percibida, (3) Se ha conectado la paradoja *lejos-cerca* (Wilson et al., 2008) con el estudio del bienestar afectivo de los teletrabajadores.

Los primeros resultados de esta tesis han sido publicados por la revista *International Journal of Manpower* a través del artículo [A time after time effect in telework: an explanation of willingness to telework and self-reported productivity](#) (Labrado et al., 2022).

Summary of the study

This thesis studies how perceived proximity with coworkers and employee voice influence the affective wellbeing of those working regularly from home. Using a 2021 dataset of 542 professionals the model includes the analysis of several constructs (e.g., perceived proximity, employee voice, or enterprise social networks (ESNs)), to assess the results of the outcome variable (affective wellbeing). Structural equation modeling (SEM) was chosen to examine the model.

Recent telework research points to the importance of internal communication and social support as potential antecedents of affective well-being (Becker et al., 2022; Belostecinic et al., 2022). In line with that idea, we formulate two research questions:

- 1) What is the impact of Perceived Proximity (Wilson et al., 2008) between coworkers on the affective wellbeing of those working from home?
- 2) What is the impact of employee voice expression, both direct and indirect, on the affective wellbeing of those working from home?

A novelty of this study is the positive and significant relationship found between perceived proximity to a coworker and affective wellbeing. In other words, the closer one symbolically feels to a faraway coworker, the higher the positive affective wellbeing he/she will experience during telework. This finding may reveal a new reality is possible in the future of remote work, after Covid-19 experiment,

one in which close relationships can be maintained, despite the frequency and longevity working from home (WFH). Another novelty in this study is the idea that ESNs are effective in building such psychological bonding. Our results confirm this idea. Thus, the use of ESNs like MS Yammer, or Oracle, for example, promotes feeling of being close to a distant coworker under telework settings. This finding is very relevant to remote communications literature, and practitioners. The results of this thesis may indicate that, after Covid-19 telework experiment, the internal social media, ESNs, can be effective to manage psychological distance between coworkers. Additional findings reveal that shared identity and electronic communications are relevant predictors of perceived proximity.

With regards to employee voice, the expectation was set for it direct and indirect to have a positive effect on teleworker's wellbeing. The hypotheses were not supported. In the case of direct voice, the hypothesis was rejected, and correlation found in direct opposition to our initial belief. Thus, the expression of direct voice through public social media (e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter, ...) had a negative effect on affective wellbeing. For indirect voice, we found no correlation between indirect voice and affective wellbeing, during telework. We find a plausible explanation of this result in the fact that the urgency from some Spanish employers to go back to office-based arrangements may have not given working councils enough space for such negotiations to take place (ONTSI, 2021). Voice researchers advise that for indirect voice to generate positive outcomes, Unions need to be involved in the solution of problems or negotiations of changing work conditions (Della Torre, 2019).

In today's digital economy, enterprises are shifting towards an important internal resource to maintain their competitiveness: the employees. In doing so, it becomes apparent that telework can be seen a source of competitive advantage for its ability to attract and retain the best talent (Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021; Avolio et al., 2014). The topic of this thesis is thus of considerable importance. With remote work models becoming the new normal after the pandemic (Durakovic et al., 2023), effective work-from-home contexts can be a source of strategic competitive advantage (Neirotti et al., 2017). Telework increases critical business factors such as job performance and organizational commitment (Blahopoulou et al., 2022), but only if it results in the expected positive outcomes. Organizations need to consider the quality of the telework experience if they want to collect the benefits, through increased employee engagement and wellbeing (Miglioretti et al., 2022). Decisions on how to promote employee's wellbeing at telework need to be based on the best available evidence to optimize worker outcomes (Oakman et al., 2020). Thus, wellbeing at telework is an employee outcome in which to base decisions of future workplace arrangements (Wood et al., 2021), especially to prevent work-from-home negative effects, such as social isolation, to occur. In this sense, social connectedness at work acts as a health protective resource (Bakker et al., 2003; Seinsche et al., 2022). This thesis answers calls to examine the role of social connectedness in developing successful work-from-home experiences (Bloom et al., 2013; Golden et al., 2008; Memon et al., 2022).

Results from this study confirm that psychological bonds between remote coworkers can be created and consolidated in work-from-home settings, despite the lack of face-to-face interactions (Guest, 2017; Ruiller et al., 2019). The use of ESNs, workmate communication and identification allow to build engagement and commitment in a remote workforce. The ability to find and "follow" like minded colleagues in the workplace is a needed resource in the future of work (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020). Collaborative work environments are rapidly growing as hybrid work is rearranging the way knowledge workers work (Yang et al., 2022). Our findings extend previous knowledge on connectivity during WFH arrangements by shifting the focus from communication frequency to perceived distance. Our results from the examination of voice mechanisms sheds light into the negative side effects uncontrolled behavior in public social media can have in teleworker's wellbeing. Finding ways to manage and prevent such actions safeguard collateral efforts to foster the wellbeing

of the organization. The conclusions drawn from this thesis are actionable insights for practitioners shaping future work scenarios. Decisions about working conditions, technology requirements or cultural attributes associated with technology usage (e.g., open, collaborative, supportive) will impact the outcomes of telework in different ways.

The first results from this thesis were published in International Journal of Manpower under the article *A time after time effect in telework; an explanation of willingness to telework and self-reported productivity* (Labrado et al., 2022).

1. Introduction

If given the choice, 84% of Spanish workers prefer to work-from-home after Covid-19 forced telework (ONTSI, 2022). Of those, one in three are willing to increase the number of hours they currently work-from-home. Considering that, prior to the Covid-19 outbreak, 74,5% of Spain's working population had not been exposed to this form of remote work (Eurofound, 2020; ONTSI, 2021) it seems reasonable to think that Spanish workers have found in telework a positive working experience. Covid-19 has raised employer's and employee's willingness to telework. It becomes apparent to explore the antecedents of such positive experiences to best shape future ways of working in a post-pandemic world. Scholars are increasingly shifting towards a social perspective to study telework outcomes (Becker et al., 2022; Belostecinic et al., 2022; Carillo et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2020a). In this sense, this thesis will hence focus on the impact of work-from-home environments in employee wellbeing. In doing so, two research perspectives will be applied:

- (1) The Perceived Proximity perspective (Wilson et al., 2008), where technology enabled interactions to build a sense of closeness will be assessed.
- (2) The employee voice perspective, where electronic forms of voice expression (direct and indirect) will be assessed in its ability to influence employee wellbeing through stronger social support in the adoption of work-from-home practices.

The focus on affective wellbeing as employee outcome has been raised by former scholars to understand how it influences employees and their organizations (Blahopoulou et al., 2022; Guest, 2017; Uribetxebarria et al., 2021). There are more perspectives involved in telework management practices, as well as in affective wellbeing at work (e.g., work-life balance), but are not the primary focus of this research. Thus, this thesis proposes an original research lens to the study of telework, with the focus on the importance of psychological distance in work-from-home environments. The following paragraphs present an overview of relevant findings from telework research overtime, that have been found relevant to our research questions.

Almost two decades ago, telework researchers were busy investigating whether the condition of WFH was a positive or a negative situation, for employees' and employers. The results from this period of investigation unveiled several contradicting outcomes. Gajendran and Harrison (2007) captured what was known up to that moment during a meta-analysis of the extant telework literature. These pair of researchers did not find conclusive evidence to postulate in favor or against WFH, thus they proposed the *telecommuting paradox*. The *telecommuting paradox* (Gajendran and Harrison, 2007) captured the collection of contradicting evidence available in academic work. For example, telework may increase the workers autonomy and work-life balance. At the same time, they found a harnessing effect in the connections and relationships with colleagues and supervisors. As the authors postulate, telework is neither good nor bad, it depends heavily in the contextual setting where it is based. Individual factors like former experience in telework, openness to telework, or self-efficacy (Allen et al., 2015) are known to influence the outcomes of telework. The employee own openness to experience, or self-leadership (Anderson et al., 2015) are also attributes shaping the experience of WFH. The *telecommuting paradox* have guided successive research effort towards segmented analysis of the experience WFH (Collins et al., 2016b; Charalampous et al., 2019).

Golden (2006) claimed that any form of virtual work should be understood in terms of the effect it has on working relationships. Wilson et al. (2008) studied how psychological distance is constructed in remote and collocated teams. During their investigation, Wilson and her team found distant team members were able to develop feelings of being close to each other. In some cases, these feelings were stronger than the ones shared between collocated workers. This team of researchers named this

the *far-but-close* paradox. The *far-but-close* paradox is of vital importance to the research model of this thesis. Interestingly the reverse paradox was also prevalent, that is, coworkers sharing the same office space felt psychologically distant to each other. Thus, Wilson et al. (2008) noted that physical distance is not determinant to coworker perceived proximity. On the contrary, according to the *far-but-close* paradox, psychological distance arises from workmate identification and increased communication.

Leonardi et al. (2010) studied remote working relationships under the lens of technology usage. This team of researchers posit that the use of Information Technology Communications (ICTs) to connect home workers with central office coworkers are a two-sided sword. On one side, ICTs enable employers and teleworkers to make extensive use of them to perform their daily work and stay connected with the organization. On the other side, the same technology communications can be a source of distress from interruptions and unwanted connections. In this sense, Leonardi and his team (2010) evidenced there can be too much connectivity under remote work settings. Unless properly controlled by the teleworkers, the ease of connectivity may generate a sense of being overly connected to the organization, thus negating the benefits from telework, derived from higher levels of autonomy, flexibility, and focus. They named this effect the *connectivity paradox*. In some cases, teleworkers developed coping strategies as direct as physically disconnecting their computers from the company's network to appear disconnect and gain focus. Managers can also suffer the negative influence of telework, in their own way. Teleworkers often see in their supervisors the default reference point of assistance and expect to channel any visibility needs through them (Ipsen et al., 2021). Boell et al. (2016) posit that these paradoxical outcomes are, among other reasons, due to the lack of understanding of the different ways ICT can enact remote work practices. In situations of crisis-induced WFH, for example New Zealand's earthquake, managers are placed as single point of communication with the organization, on top of suffering the consequences of the crisis themselves (Donnelly & Proctor-Thomson, 2015).

We find relevant to note one last paradoxical effect, related with the adoption of telework. One of the major challenges in the adoption of telework is the implied flexibility in spatial and temporal arrangements, often referred to as the *flexibility paradox* (Sewell & Taskin, 2015). The paradox arises from the balancing act the autonomy and control employees gain in telework co-exist with the organizational processes the employer must put in place to ensure effectiveness is maintained in WFH arrangements. Thus, gains in perceived autonomy, control, and flexibility, often emotionally appreciated by employees (Anderson et al., 2015), are confronted with supervisors losing trust over their employees work due to lack of face-to-face contact. Sewell and Taskin (2015) suggest that to overcome this challenge teleworkers must accept closer control systems in place, which in turn implies some level of flexibility loss. Lautsch et al. (2009) propose an alternative to increased bureaucracy, suggesting emphasis in sharing information to replace the lack of in situ supervisory procedures. This proposed change in supervisory models will possibly lead to more positive outcomes.

Although the *far-but-close*, the *flexibility*, and the *connectivity* paradox refer to remote/flexible work settings, not exclusively to WFH arrangements, their findings are found relevant to our research question as they both focus on working relationships from two complementary angles: subjective proximity and technology enabled interactions. It is simply not possible to study the implications of telework arrangements without considering how it may suit varying personal and team conditions (Pyöriä, 2011). In sum, telework effectiveness cannot be studied applying straightforward manners.

The number of hours/days worked from home is an interesting research perspective (Bailey & Kurland, 2002; Fonner & Roloff, 2010; Gajendran & Harrison, 2007). As teleworkers intensify their time WFH the following outcomes become salient: higher reliance on communication technology, development of a distinct telework identity, changing communication patterns, or segmented psychological thresholds, compared to those sporadically WFH. When Golden (2006) tested telework intensity he found it had a positive effect on job satisfaction, derived from improved work-family conflict and quality of relationships at work. Other researchers stress the fact teleworkers are particularly susceptible to feelings of isolation (Beauregard et al., 2019b). Workplace isolation have detrimental effects in psychological wellbeing (Becker et al., 2022) and the happiness at work. Addressing employee wellbeing in the workplace has become increasingly important for practitioners and researchers, as it is known to explain more than 25% of teleworker's performance (Wright, 2010).

With regards to telework adoption, since its inception, rates have moved slower than expected (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020). Reasons explaining this inconsistent adoption are found in: (1) unclear strategic benefits derived from telework (e.g., innovation, collaboration or complexity remotely managing task interdependence (Dandalt, 2021; Hynes, 2016; Maruyama & Tietze, 2012)), and (2) manager attitude towards telework (e.g., supervisor mistrust; detachment from work; uncertainty in the manager's role (Anderson et al., 2015; Golden & Eddleston, 2020; van der Lippe & Lippényi, 2019). Fluctuation in adoption may have also shaped the interests of scientific research, tipping in favor of extensive debate about the benefits and drawbacks of telework (Boell et al., 2016; Golden & Gajendran, 2019; Hynes, 2016). Debates about telework are important as the consequences of telework and their contingent factors remain still unclear (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007; van der Lippe & Lippényi, 2019). The result is that little attention has been paid to examining ways to overcome the negative consequences of telework. The advent of extended telework practices and the growing presence of paradoxical findings is a sign that, perhaps, new research perspectives need to be taken.

Given the low prevalence rates prior to the pandemic, many employers faced full-time and almost firm-wide teleworking among their workers for the first time (Fana et al., 2020). The adoption of sustained forms of remote work present interesting benefits the senior-level managers are willing to accept like dramatic reduction of cost of buildings, ubiquitous access to talent, new talent retention measures or more robust sustainability plans. As practitioners rethink their workplace in a post-lockdown period, there are lessons to learn from the health crisis. Most importantly, practitioners need to recognize the importance of employee wellbeing and engagement in the achievement of the desired business goals (Gallup, 2021). Researchers advise the need to deeply investigate contextual factors, to understand some of paradoxes identified in this field of research (Allen et al., 2015; Lautsch et al., 2009; Leonardi et al., 2010; Wilson et al., 2008). Thus, extant body of research on telework management need to be revisited, as it is prevalent from a period where workers were delivered on homogeneous schedules, had little work responsibility, all under strict physically present supervision (Kossek et al., 2009). Also, prior to social distancing restrictions the employer's office workplace maintained a central position in shaping employees' experiences (Collins et al., 2016b), giving meaning to the individuals' jobs. Covid-19 WFH experiment has revealed the need for new work-from-home primary data, as learnings from the past may not be applicable in post-pandemic scenarios (Carillo et al., 2021). Telework, at a larger or smaller extent, must be an integral part of future working design investigations. Psychological and social demands of telework (e.g., isolation, forming social relations, coworker support) need to be properly addressed (Seinsche et al., 2022). In this vein, this thesis explores the impact of perceived proximity and employee voice in employee wellbeing in organizations which have adopted telework arrangements. Drawing from former research on

perceived proximity model (O’Leary et al., 2014a; Ruiller et al., 2019; van Zoonen et al., 2014; Wilson et al., 2008), we place a focal point in the impact that ICT-based interactions, communication, identification and employee voice have in shaping the outcomes of subjective proximity and affective wellbeing.

Structure of the thesis document

The structure of this thesis is built as follows. In Chapter one, the introduction of this dissertation, we provide a brief description of the study. In this chapter the background of the study and the problem statement are presented, the concept of telework is introduced, and the literature gap identified. Chapter 2 provides the theoretical rationale of the research from which the research question, hypotheses and research design will emerge. The literature review will shed light into different aspects of the research problem, providing historical background, describing the current knowledge in the field, relevant variables and leading scholars, identifying gaps and, in general, becoming a connecting chapter with the remaining sections. In the methodology chapter (chapter 3) the specific steps taken to address the research questions will be described. The research design is also described. A detailed description of the methods used (e.g., selection of participants, instrumentation, data collection, data analysis) is provided for future references or use by other researchers. Chapter 4 contains a comprehensive presentation of the results of the data analysis. Pure, objective analysis is described in this fourth chapter, without injecting value judgements, these will be presented in the following chapter. The concluding chapter (chapter 5) contains a summary of the study, discussion of the findings, implications for practice and recommendations for future research. Annexes with additional data, such as tables, figures, description of the model, or a copy of the questionnaire used to collect responses will also be provided.

Figure 1 - Structure of the thesis

Source: Own elaboration

1.1 The concept of telework

The concept of telework dates back in the oil crisis in the early 1970's (Pyöriä, 2011). Back then, societal problems like urban crowding, pollution, energy shortages, or traffic congestions led Nilles et al. (1976) to analyze the pros and cons of working from home. The obtained results from reduced commuting scenarios anticipated a positive impact on national economy. Thus, the notion of *telecommuting* arose as dominant concept (Jackson & van der Wielen, 1998). Since then, the rise of the knowledge-based economy, and advancements in technology have introduced new motivations for telework adoption (Allen et al., 2015).

The term telework covers a wide array of distributed work arrangements with options for customizable locations and durations to deliver work outside the central office. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO-Eurofound, 2017), telework refers to the use of ICTs for work that is performed away from the employer's premises. Telework has also been referred as, *telecommute*, *remote work*, *flexible work*, *distance work*, and more recently named *smartwork*. What is common to all these arrangements is the use of ICTs to conduct the work and the fact that one of more workers are not physically present at the office (Golden, 2006; Kossek et al., 2009). ILO-Eurofound (2017) recognizes the existence of two overlapping categories: (1) work done outside the employer's premises using information technology, and (2) work performed from home. This clarification is relevant to consider when using secondary data from national reports, where major differences can be found. For example, data collected in United States operationalizes categories (1) and (2) distinctively whereas other countries, e.g., Argentina, only operationalizes category (1).

According to Allen et al. (2015:44), "Telecommuting is a work practice that involves members of an organization substituting a portion of their typical work hours (ranging from a few hours per week to nearly full-time) to work away from a central workplace—typically principally from home—using technology to interact with others as needed to conduct work tasks". In brief, telework refers to the organization of work and/or completion of tasks away from the workplace using ICT (Illegems & Verbeke, 2004).

The definition of telework in European Framework Agreement of Telework is deliberately left broad.

Telework is a form of organizing and/ or performing work, using information technology, in the context of an employment contract/ relationship, where work, which could also be performed at the employer's premises, is carried out away from those premises on a regular basis (Eurofound, 2010:15).

This definition provides a wide space to agree on definitions in the Member States; the lack of standardization reveals difficulties when measuring and comparing telework incidence across countries.

Although there is no universally accepted definition of telework, during this thesis project the following definition of telework will be used:

work achieved with the help of Information Technology tools and conducted from home.

In this vein, telework will be mostly applicable within high-skilled workers. Generally, high-skilled workers are those who do work with their computers, are employed in knowledge intensive activities and experience high levels of autonomy within their work. Teachers, managers, and ICT professionals in Europe show the highest levels of telework prevalence (Eurofound, 2020). On the other end of the scale, administrative and manufacturing and those involving high levels of face-to-face encountering find it difficult or impossible to perform outside of the employer's premises.

The story behind telework adoption

Before any further development of arguments of this dissertation we find relevant to understand a key antecedent of telework academic knowledge and practice in present times: Telework adoption has failed to meet scholar's predictions over time.

The concept of telework finds its roots in an energy crisis, in the early 70s. Although its adoption has direct implications in business and individual employee performance, its origin belongs to non-business domain. Maybe this has some relations with the slow pace of adoption since early days, and the relatively low interest managers have shown in it (Bailey & Kurland, 2002). Since its inception, large employers have, over time, manifested contradictory decisions regarding telework allowance. Early adopters of telework (e.g., american large employers) rushed to make public announcements of their telework embracement, giving sign of modern organizational development. Nonetheless, unexpected news in the press would read the decision to step back from such decisions (e.g., Yahoo or Best Buy, in 2.013) (Allen et al., 2015). Both companies argued the need for physical presence to foster collaboration and generation of dynamic work environments. Pyöriä (2011) referred to the lack of "culture of telework" in the organizations being a barrier to telework adoption. The sole fact that appropriate ICT tools were in place to ensure good quality of remote communications seemed not enough encouragement from managers to grant access to telework. At the time, managers showed a propensity to mistrust employees work-from-home, thus explaining the slow adoption trend.

Likewise, the existence of company policies that regulate telework have not predicted its adoption (Hynes, 2016; Palomino et al., 2020). The literature highlights several reasons for this. First, managers being restrictive when granting access to telework. Manager's trust to grant access to telework is mostly formed by cumulative judgements of the employee's conscientiousness (Anderson et al., 2015). In other words, provided a telework program is in place, only when the employee holds a consistent track record of positive work performance, will he/she be likely to be granted access to telework arrangements. Second, even mature organizations still see issues with remote workers having difficulties adapting to new job demands as they become accustomed to work autonomy and being self-sufficient (Canónico, 2016). Managers are hesitant that, overtime, teleworkers lack understanding of what goes on in the company and/or what is expected from them. A recurrent complaint from adopting managers is the resistance they find from employees when a non-flexible office-time is set (e.g., attending monthly team meetings, ...). Third, distinct adopter vs. non-adopter perspectives on the outcomes of telework highlight non-adopters hold a more negative view of the results of telework implementation. Results from a comparative study posit non-adopter organizations underestimate the positive impact of telework in attracting and retaining the right talent; and overestimate the expected negative effects of telework in productivity and teamwork effectiveness; they also expect a much harder implementation process (Illegems & Verbeke, 2004). In other words, telework adopters were significantly happier with enhanced productivity and increase flexibility, found teamwork effectiveness less of a problem, and did not encountered difficulties with social

isolation of those who telework. With regards to concerns over the security of internal data and face to face contact problems were not significantly distinct between adopters and non-adopters.

Extant research is extensive in benefits, barriers, and drawbacks of telework adoption (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007; Pyöriä, 2011; Salas et al., 2015). Although much is known about the good and bad consequences of telework, little is yet known about which factors influence the employee's experience of WFH (Beauregard et al., 2019b; Golden & Gajendran, 2019). Telework ability to attract and retain the right talent can be a source of strategic competitive advantage for the firm (Illegems & Verbeke, 2004), but only if the employees are engaged to perform. Throughout time, scholars have sought to understand the consequences of telework for enterprises and for employees. As seen above, the public announcements made by influential employers may have ignited further debate about the benefits of telework as a practice, drifting attention away from investigations on contextual factors to augment the expected positive outcomes from telework (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020).

Prior to social distancing restrictions in 2020, the employer's office was referential to shaping experiences at work (Collins et al., 2016b). Back then, motivations to telework were time flexibility and ability to balance work-life; whereas on the employer side, reducing office accommodation seemed to be the main motivation to embrace large transitions to telework (Bloom et al., 2013; Maruyama & Tietze, 2012). Amid the pandemic, telework has become not only a popular practice but a matter of national interest (Thompson et al., 2022). Covid-19 health pandemic aftermath is disrupting extant paradigms in many fields. For example, new motives to telework (e.g., attend family matters, or increase productivity) have emerged. In many European Union countries, more than half of the workers who started WFH during the pandemic had no prior experience with teleworking (Durakovic et al., 2023). With regards ways of working, evidence from post-Covid-19 lockdown times is indicative social practices WFH may have evolved during this time (Becker et al., 2022). Learnings from the crisis-induced telework period represent an opportunity for academic and researchers to accelerate the social base perspective of WFH. The social base perspective of telework stresses the importance of work relationships in maintaining the energy levels and mitigating negative impacts in individual and organizational outcomes such as wellbeing, employee engagement, and organizational commitment, or intention to quit (Mehta & Sharma, 2022).

In this vein, this thesis has defined employee wellbeing as dependent variable in the study. Additionally, two social based research perspectives will be applied: (1) the influence of ICTs on perceived proximity; introducing some novelties to previous studies such as the use of ESNs; and (2) the role of online employee voice mechanisms in shaping employee wellbeing. Overtime, technology is being recognized by its ability to produce organizational and individual outcomes such as social and symbolic value in the construction of identities, coordination of relationships and the enactment of sense-making process (O'Leary et al., 2014a) In the advent of turbulent times for large organizations to increase their performance under changing working conditions, this study borrows from Guest (2017), who was the first to take into consideration employee wellbeing in such contexts.

We believe that the research lens applied in this thesis will contribute to the design of future workplaces by providing new empirical evidence on the use of modern ICTs and its corresponding effect in organizational results, through increased psychological wellbeing of the individual workers.

Telework adoption during Covid-19 turbulent times

Pre-pandemic prevalence figures in the European Union are available in Eurostat (2019) Labour Force Survey. In 2019, 9% of EU27 workers from home, at least partially. Although adoption rates are inconsistent across countries and sectors. Technology and knowledge-intensive sectors, for example, score the highest telework adoption levels (30%) (Eurofound, 2020). The inflexion point arrived by the first week of April 2020; half of the world's population were under some sort of lockdown. According to Eurofound (2020) over 36% of workers in EU27 started teleworking fulltime as results of Covid-19 outbreak. Most knowledge workers transitioned to work-from-home arrangements, practically overnight (Becker et al., 2022).

According to *Living, working and Covid-19* report (Eurofound, 2020), in June-July 2020 52% of Spanish workers were WFH; for 1 in every 3 employees, this was the first experience with this mode of work. This situation is also the case for many European countries (Milasi et al., 2020). Although imposed restrictive measures varied as the pandemic situation evolved, data collected in April 2021 shows prevalent ratios have decreased. The largest drop in WFH exclusively was recorded in Spain (from 46% to 21%). In spring 2021, working exclusively from home was most common in Ireland (48%) and least common in Croatia (9%). The increase in working exclusively from home was most noticeable in Netherlands (15 points increase in less than a year). The report sheds light into the relevance of factors like previous experience, technical feasibility, and the industrial structure of the Member States as determinant of varying of telework adoption across EU countries.

Figure 2 – Work-from-home prevalence ratios in Spain shows the recorded variation in telework prevalence since the outbreak of the pandemic in the country, segmented by telework intensity. The data was collected by Spain's Labour Force Survey (Encuesta de Población Activa (EPA)) every trimester; EPA distinguishes three levels of WFH intensity: a) occasionally (those that work-from-home upmost half of the hours worked during the month); b) regularly (those that work-from-home more than 50% of the hours worked during the month); and c) non-teleworkers (those that have not worked from home at all during the month (ONTSI, 2021). Figure 2 shows a declining prevalence of work-from-home scenario b) in favor of a) and c).

Figure 2 - Work-from-home prevalence ratios in Spain

(*) Regularly: More than half of the days worked during the month

Source: INE, 2022

Telework has been a field of interest for scholars and policy makers for many years. With the pandemic experiment, both employers and employees may gain a better understanding of the potential of telework (Durakovic et al., 2023). The study of the determinants of telework is vital to move forward (Beck et al., 2020). WFH will be a norm in a post-pandemic world. Eurofound (2021) estimates that at least one fifth of EU 27 employees will telework regularly or occasionally in a post-pandemic scenario. It seems certain that the crisis-induced telework period has permanently transformed the way we work (Becker et al., 2022). By understanding the antecedent conditions of telework, organizations are better able to design and implement teleworking arrangements.

Over three years now since the outbreak, controversy has again arisen between multinational companies holding contrary views regarding the future adoption of telework. Some, like Facebook, are showing public signs of intensification of telework arrangements in large organizations. Facebook CEO Mark Zuckerberg announced the company will gradually adopt permanent telework practices, up to 50% of the workforce by 2030 (Sandler, 2020). Other large companies like Google, Twitter, Square, Microsoft have announced permanent remote working measures (Brownlee, 2020). Different industry sectors, such as Investment Banking are making blunt statements about their position against any form of remote work. These decisions may be signaling that telework management dilemma is still not solved. As telework adoption can open doors for companies to successfully accommodate in the digital economy; and technologies continue to evolve (Allen et al., 2015; Arvola et al., 2017; Kok, 2018), learning from recent intensive WFH period are relevant to shaping successful working conditions in the future (Wood et al., 2022). The intensity and length of Covid-19 induced telework

has changes former telework paradigms; thus, learnings from this period are critical to shape future decisions on employer/employee relations, and the role to be played by technology enabled interactions (Carillo et al., 2021).

1.2 Goals of the research

The primary goal of this dissertation is to understand the influential role of coworker perceived proximity, a measure of psychological distance, and employee voice mechanisms have in the wellbeing of teleworkers. Specifically, this thesis attempts to answer the following two research questions:

- (1) What is the impact of perceived proximity (Wilson et al., 2008) with coworkers in employee wellbeing?
- (2) What is the impact of online employee voice mechanisms in employee wellbeing?

The study of perceived proximity is valuable in telework contexts where physical distance is a daily ingredient in coworker relationships. The advancements on communication technologies adopted by large employers (e.g., knowledge portals, ESNs, open videoconferencing tools, ...) and the experience gained during Covid-19 forced telework (Becker et al., 2022) raises the need to empirically test the potential use of these ICTs to build a sense of being close amongst distant coworkers and to test whether such perception of proximity influences the affective state of teleworkers.

Additionally, this thesis will examine the effect that employee voice mechanisms have in affective wellbeing, under the same contextual setting. The research model will distinctively examine direct and indirect voice mechanisms to provide new light into the dilemma. Recent research suggests that caring work cultures, where employees are encouraged to express their voice, encourage employee engagement and participation, which in turn predicts positive levels of satisfaction at work (Mehta & Sharma, 2022). With telework programs becoming a regular in a post-pandemic era (van Zoonen et al., 2021a), it becomes apparent to explore if and which employee voice mechanisms regulate affective states during telework practice.

To best answer our two research questions for large organizations, the following detailed issues need to also be addressed:

- What are the channels and frequency involved in workmate communication?
- Which attributes define coworker's identity?
- Which choice of media usage is most appropriate to build perceived proximity?
- Which work profile attributes predicts positive telework experience?
- How does enterprise social network usage impact perceived proximity?
- Is public social media an appropriate channel to express voice?
- What is the perceived contribution of Unions in shaping telework adoption arrangements?
- How are Unions performing communications about telework adoption?
- Is participation in online Union activity shaping employee voice?
- What is the overall teleworker experience?

These and other details have been considered in the design of this investigation. The collection of data and its analysis will carefully address these questions to provide valuable results for academia and management.

Humans have a basic need to affiliate with other humans (Cacioppo & Cacioppo, 2018). Telework environments place a threat in the way teleworkers affiliate and relate with each other (Golden et al., 2008). With negative emotions in the workplace at a record high since 2009 (Gallup, 2021), social interactions in the workplace are increasingly taking a central role in the telework researchers' agenda. Drawing from former research on perceived proximity model, this thesis will place a focal point in the impact that social networking sites (e.g., ESNs) and technology enabled interactions have in shaping the outcomes of communication and social identification processes. The advancement of technological tools enables open conversations among employees to exchange information, finding solutions, or simply fulfill the social need to be in contact with other people (Sakka & Ahammad, 2020). Following guidance from Allen et al. (2015), we will examine the use coworkers make of communication tools to emulate the social context in the remote workplace. Examples of this detailed examination include channels used (e.g., email, chat, live calls, ...), as well as contextual information (e.g., formal events, informal events organized by the dyad/ employer, ...). With that focus in mind, the findings from the study will determine whether feelings of proximity can be effectively driven through these means.

Technology is also expected to play a supporting role in *wellbeing-friendly* telework practices (Leonardi et al., 2010). We will subsequently analyze the impact that perceived proximity has on the psychological wellbeing of teleworkers. The higher the prevalence of telework arrangements, the stronger the need to redirect research efforts towards a better understanding of the factors that predict successful telework experiences through work characteristics like identity, psychological distance, or employee wellbeing (Becker et al., 2022). Conclusions from this thesis provide body of research with results grounded in new primary quantitative data on the impact of perceived proximity in employee wellbeing in telework contexts of large organizations.

The present study follows suggestions from Leonardi et al. (2010) to further investigate emergent and informal uses of technology in telework contexts. We will do so, for example, by exploring the use of public social media for teleworkers to express their voice. Public social media offers the ability to easily communicate with a vast number of people (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010), offering immediacy, and accessibility to co-create. We will also examine whether these solutions can connect employees with Unions and worker representatives to discuss telework-specific topics. We acknowledge the warning from recent studies on the barriers intra-firm social media may face to successfully engage with employees. Some unintended behaviors (e.g., use of social media posts as a self-promoting activity) may limit the potential use by Unions for voice purposes (Laumer et al., 2017). Nonetheless, the goal of the present research is to examine whether the experience gained during Covid-19 telework has shaped new forms of electronic employee voice (direct and indirect) in large organizations, and to assess whether this expression of voice has any influence on psychological wellbeing of teleworkers.

1.3 Research relevance

The topic of this thesis is of considerable importance for employers and academia, as telework increases its footprint in a post-pandemic work world. This dissertation project contributes to telework literature through the study of the influence of perceived proximity and employee voice as explanatory factors of teleworker psychological wellbeing. The results from the present study will shed light into the effects Covid-19 will permanently have in workplace environments. The data used in the study was collected a year after social distancing measures were enforced in most European countries and many employees were removed to the office and sent home to work. Participants in the study had gained experienced WFH regularly over the previous year, at least. Analysis of the proposed research question in such a rich experiential context will be crucial to continue the quest to understanding the telework phenomena in a post-pandemic world (Sutarto et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021).

In the advent of telework, both employers and employees need to gain new understanding of the causal effects of regular telework in employee wellbeing. A futuristic view of work environments, where telework represents an asset to attract and retain high-skilled resources (Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021; Neirotti et al., 2017) places an urgent need to better understand what drives positive telework experiences (Mehta & Sharma, 2022). Work social contexts where happy employees feel motivated to engage and collaborate are crucial for organizations to thrive in digital economies (Kazekami, 2020; Wang et al., 2020a).

Recent telework research advises on the loss of social ties (Yang et al., 2022) as results of firm-wide crisis-induced telework arrangements. Reasons for this are found in reduced work-related communication opportunities and informal interactions (Dettmers & Plückhahn, 2021; Seinsche et al., 2022). In this situation, employee engagement, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, or implicit knowledge exchange, to name a few, are clearly at risk (Coenen & Kok, 2014; van der Lippe & Lippényi, 2019). If co-located workers spend, on average, 75 minutes a day in water cooler-type informal conversations (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020): how are intensive telework programs providing for alternative ways to re-create such situations? what is the impact on organizational outcomes? Little is yet known (Durakovic et al., 2023). What has been long known is that socialization in the workplace plays a major role in the sound implementation of telework (Lautsch et al., 2009). Social interactions at work may revert the loss from lack of “coffee talk”, necessary to build relationships at work (Seinsche et al., 2022).

Given the above, the present study contributes to existing knowledge on socialization in remote work environments by placing focus on the role of coworker relations. Our aim is to better understand if and what ICT-based coworker interactions and expression of voice shape positive affective wellbeing at telework. Positive telework outcomes come from the individual’s satisfaction with the working conditions (e.g., job satisfaction). Work-from-home experiences are known to be most influenced by communication efficiency, alongside perceived productivity, and domestic economy savings (Belostecinic et al., 2022). In this vein, telework can have a positive effect on wellbeing, provided the threat of isolation is maintained at control (Adamovic, 2022). The lack of face-to-face encounters is the key disadvantage of telework. This research contributes to post-pandemic telework literature by closely examining the mediating role psychological distance has in telework outcomes. With happy teleworkers performing better and demonstrating increased levels of wellbeing, the research lens of this thesis gives response to former calls for new evidence on employee experiences at telework (Allen et al., 2015; Arvola et al., 2017; Blahopoulou et al., 2022).

1.4 Problem description and literature gap

After the extensive exposure to Covid-19 forced telework, employees, practitioners, and regulators are examining standing adoption of telework (Wood et al., 2022). Many organizations are looking into adoption of some form of hybrid work model for the future (Yadav et al., 2022); but the mere adoption of WFH arrangements will not be sufficient to reach the expected benefits (e.g., productivity, reduced costs, organizational performance, ...) (Miglioretti et al., 2022). Any sustainable approach to remote work is called to contemplate enhancing and maintaining employee wellbeing (Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021), examined through the lens of relationships at work (Golden, 2006). Human Resource practices that promote healthy relationships and employee participation, among others, play a significant role in employee wellbeing (Clarke & Hill, 2012). Thus, in this thesis, we aim to better understand the role of coworker relationships (through perceived proximity) and employee online voice in improving the affective wellbeing of teleworkers.

For decades, telework has been a heavily debated political issue (Wöhrmann & Ebner, 2021). Former focus was placed on employment relationships, policy definition or contractual arrangements (Canónico, 2016; Illegems & Verbeke, 2004). Focus on the outcomes of telework remains scarce and, often, inconclusive in its findings (Uribetxebarria et al., 2021). The goal of this dissertation is to expand the knowledge regarding the antecedents of employee's wellbeing whilst at telework. The potential for telework adoption is at its peak nowadays. In Spain for example, one in three jobs can be entirely performed from home (Dingel & Neiman, 2020). With these predictions in mind, former scholar research on telework can benefit from new empirical evidence on more up to date working practices. The following paragraphs will outline the major gaps of knowledge identified during the literature review undertaken during this thesis project.

Firstly, there is scarce knowledge about what shapes wellbeing-friendly telework experiences. Telework scholars are increasingly advising of the limited knowledge about antecedents of such experiences at telework (Moens et al., 2022). Up to now telework research may have been oversimplifying the telework phenomena by simply seeking to understand how it impacts individual and organizational performance (Maruyama & Tietze, 2012). Thus, a deeper understanding is required in the experience of telework itself. The lack of understanding of how positive experiences are shaped can result in the interruption of healthy work relationships; dampening of employee energy levels and psychological wellbeing (Becker et al., 2022). Learnings from recent studies reveal that fostering a caring culture where anxiety is low, and employees feel encouraged to express their voice encourages employee engagement and satisfaction during telework (Mehta & Sharma, 2022). In general, high-quality relations and social interactions at work can positively influence employee wellbeing (Niebuhr et al., 2022; Wöhrmann & Ebner, 2021). The challenge is thus set for Human Resources practitioners. With little knowledge about the new ways of working in a post-pandemic world simple repetition of former management practices is not advisable (Moens et al., 2022). Additionally, as individuals gain job control and autonomy, they are making personalized decisions on how to segment their lives (Becker et al., 2022) leaving no space for one-size-fits-all solutions. In sum, what makes telework experience a pleasant one is far from clear (Wöhrmann and Ebner, 2021), hence more research on the psychological dimension of work-from-home wellbeing is needed (Charalampous et al., 2019; Wöhrmann & Ebner, 2021).

The research questions in this dissertation project are a humble attempt to cover this research gap on telework experience by providing new understanding of antecedents of wellbeing-friendly telework

experiences. The mediating effect perceived proximity can have in wellbeing will be investigated. Hypotheses in this study will assess the impact of social ties in teleworker's affective wellbeing. The mediating effect of workmate communication, identification, ESN usage, and the use of online mechanisms to express voice will be analyzed to assess whether the independent variables (perceived proximity and employee voice) influence psychological wellbeing in any way. More specifically this study places a focal point of examination in the role of technology's potential to build positive affect or reduce negative affect.

Secondly, extant research on the shaping of social structures in the workplace is limited (van der Lippe & Lippényi, 2019). Recent evidence on the damage work-from-home arrangements can have on the organization's network structures, confirm the need for employers to purposely plan for such social interactions in the workplace (Yang & Lin, 2022). Company social structures may become static and siloed in forced work-from-home. Even though enlarging the ties may have not been a priority in Covid-19 lockdown times, researchers and practitioners have a pending subject with effective provision of social presence in remote contexts (Marshall et al., 2007). Social presence (Short et al., 1976) refers to the ability of communication media to provoke sense of closeness. Past studies on social presence have failed to fully evaluate contextual issues regarding social presence on teleworkers. Previous focus seemed to end at the study of frequency and richness of media used, they have failed to gauge how the social connectedness are formed in remote work environments (Burgoon et al., 2002; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). We propose to go a step further by evaluating, for example, the impact of internal social media (ESNs) to build closeness between teleworkers, or leaning on public social media to express one's voice, and later, confirm whether this use of technology increases the psychological wellbeing of teleworkers. Thus, we attempt to extend previous studies on the relationship between media use, feelings of presence, and affective states of employees (Fonner & Roloff, 2012).

Thirdly, extant knowledge on the perceived proximity construct is solid on the antecedents of feelings of being close to a distant colleague but the consequences of such closeness in business outcomes remains unexplored. The early model proposed by Wilson et al. (2008) identified the mediating factors shaping the sense of proximity. These are categorized as individual factors (e.g., openness to telework or previous experience with telework) and organizational ones (e.g., network structures or structural assurance). Later, empirical research applying this theory (O'Leary et al., 2014a; Ruiller et al., 2019; van Zoonen et al., 2021a) have provided positive validation of scale but they have neglected to explore perceived proximity influence on ulterior outcomes. Wilson et al. (2008) perceived proximity framework has been validated theoretically and empirically as a measure of psychological distance but, up to now, its influential role in telework outcomes has not been explored. Following recommendations made by Beauregard et al. (2019) and Spilker & Breaugh (2021), we set focus on employee wellbeing as dependent variable, and will study the mediating effect of perceived proximity on such outcome. This project contributes to the development of perceived proximity theory by assessing the causal relation with the outcome of wellbeing at telework. To the best of our knowledge, this thesis project will be the first study to examine the influential role of perceived proximity in work-related outcomes.

Fourthly, despite the vast existence of employee voice literature in office-based context, specific knowledge of voice under telework arrangements remains unexplored. Employee voice has long been studied for over 200 years, since its appearance in Adam Smith's *Wealth of Nations* (Kaufman, 2013). Scholars have unveiled the antecedents of voice and have, in recent years started discovering the consequences of it. Most of these studies have examined office-based work contexts (Liu et al.,

2022b). Thus, scientific knowledge on if and how electronic voice expression can affect the telework experience is limited. Some recent evidence (Yang & Lin, 2022) is optimistic on the ability of electronic voice to enhance affective environment at work and stresses the need for further studies of online voicing mechanisms. This thesis will distinctively look at direct and indirect voice forms of expression by teleworkers and assess the impact on employee individual outcomes (wellbeing).

Lastly, we found that pre-pandemic knowledge of telework may not be applicable in a post-pandemic world of work. Conclusions from pre-Covid-19 period, when no prior mass-scale intensive telework has been held, are being directly contradicted by post-Covid-19 research findings. This represents a major gap in telework literature as it is uncertain which previous knowledge is still applicable in the new work environment altered by the health crisis (Syrek et al., 2022). Examples of the recent discoveries can be found in Thompson et al. (2022) new taxonomy of employee motives to telework; here reduced commuting arises as primary telework motive, in direct contradiction with Bailey & Kurland (2002). Additionally, in the past regular teleworkers benefited from reduced time pressure at work (Sardeshmukh et al., 2012); interestingly Wöhrmann & Ebner (2021) found telework was related with more time pressure. The extent of telework did not affect time pressure in Wöhrmann and Ebner study. In other words, contrary to previous belief, choosing to work from seems no longer a suitable coping strategy in situations of time pressure. To justify such contradicting findings in literature, Carillo et al. (2021) argue that lessons learnt from telework experience during the pandemic shape the outcomes of telework, as employee have more resources and are more skilled. New evidence from experienced teleworkers is needed. Inevitably, telework-relevant primary data collection from post Covid-19 pandemic times remains limited. This thesis contributes to post-pandemic telework research with primary data.

1.5 Rationale behind the research design

The target population of this thesis is knowledge workers experienced in telework environments. The dependent variable of the study is psychological wellbeing. This is in line with the increasing attention from telework researchers on the psychological strain WFH social environments have placed over teleworkers. The lack of social contact is a recurrent demand in modern WFH (Seinsche et al., 2022). Collaboration and social exchange in the workplace are tagged as effective WFH resources to counteract psychological distress (Durakovic et al., 2023; Memon et al., 2022). In this regard, we have defined two independent variables of the study (namely coworker perceived proximity and employee voice). We have additionally examined the antecedent of the independent variables, according to existing literature. In the assessment of perceived proximity, for example, we have defined the communication and identification process. We extend previous analysis on perceived proximity by including the use of ESNs as antecedent in the model. This way we ensure the wide array of communication tooling available in large organizations is properly analyzed. Similarly, the study of employee voice have been distinctively segmented into direct and indirect voice. Following recommendations from voice researchers, we have examined the use of social media for voice expression purposes (Martin et al., 2015b), across today's most used public social media. On the other hand, for indirect voice we relied on Barnes et al. (2019) who recommend studying the construct beyond the frequency of participation on Union activities and include the assessment of the perceived effectiveness of such activities, related with telework adoption.

The research model has taken into considerations the existing gaps in the literature and will contribute to cover them in several ways. First, through the collection of a large sample of primary data from experienced teleworkers after Covid-19 forced telework the research model will contribute to corroborating previous knowledge of telework or, to create new knowledge about post Covid-19 remote ways of working. Secondly, previous studies on perceived proximity have examined the antecedents of the construct but, to the best of our knowledge, no study, up to now, has investigated the implications of the latent variable in work related outcomes (e.g., employee wellbeing). Thirdly, the research model contributes to scarce knowledge about social connectedness in remote work contexts through the examination of the effects social networking sites in building psychological bonding between coworkers. Fourth, employee voice literature is extensive in office-based context, but this thesis proposes the exploration of employee voice mechanisms under regular telework contexts. Lastly, by focusing on the topic of employee voice, in both direct and indirect voice forms, the ability to influence employee wellbeing through stronger social ties and/or the provision of social support will also be assessed. Figure 3 shows the main latent variables that form the analysis undertaken in this dissertation.

Figure 3 - Research design and analysis variables

Source: Own elaboration

This dissertation attempts to illuminate this discussion in different ways. First, it explores the use and benefits of advanced ICT platforms in psychological distance. Findings from past research is indicative of the positive effects technology enabled interactions can have in telework environments; that is, overcoming geographical and physical distance, enabling informal encounters, or increasing collaboration through a broader range of channels used (Fay & Kline, 2012; Kok, 2018; Leonardi et al., 2010), to name a few. Recent research also points out the relevance of firm-wide social media usage to build collective identity in modern large organizations (Barnes et al., 2019).

Second, we intend to contribute to theory in perceived proximity by providing new empirical evidence on the contingent factors and to determine whether feelings of proximity with a coworker influence the employee's wellbeing. This approach responds to suggestions from remote communication researchers to further explore contextual factors affecting psychological distance in high intensity teleworkers (Collins et al., 2016b; Fonner & Roloff, 2012; Ruiller et al., 2019).

Third, this thesis investigates whether the employee's feel his/her Unions or representatives can act as an effective instrument to channel their telework-specific concerns; and assess the impact in their wellbeing. Past research is indicative of the positive effects this Union instrumentality can have in individual outcomes (Newman et al., 2019), yet little is known on telework-specific Union activity.

Lastly, this research attempts to shed new light into whether modern forms of employee direct voice (e.g., through public social media) affects affective wellbeing when regularly WFH. Former research on HRM and Industry Relations agree on employee voice is a key factor to succeed in modern workplaces (Della Torre, 2019). Voice researchers are showing increasing interest in the emergence of different mechanisms of employee voice and on their potential outcomes (Kim et al. 2018; Wilkinson et al. 2018; Della Torre, 2019); we aim to contribute to this line of research with new empirical data from experienced teleworkers, after Covid-19 lockdown period.

2. Literature review

In the previous chapter we have explained the concept of telework and provided an overview of broader gaps in the telework literature, showing the contributions this research study attempts to make. This chapter presents the overarching literature review, which provides the basis for the research designed in this dissertation project.

The chapter will be structured as follows:

- Section 2.1 – Antecedents of telework: provides a view of the antecedents of telework management practices with special focus on: previous studies on telework, psychological distance, and wellbeing. Additionally, we will provide an overview of the challenges faced by large firms when adopting telework, and the importance of telework as a source of competitive advantage for firms in the future.
- Section 2.2 – Theoretical frameworks: introduces the prominent theories of the research model and unveils the theoretical frameworks relevant to our research model. The theoretical framework described in subsections 2.2.x are referenced to each of dependent (affective wellbeing) and independent variables (perceived proximity and employee voice) of this study.
- Section 2.3 – Hypotheses: presents the reasoning and formulates each of the six hypotheses that make up our research model.

2.1 Antecedents of telework

Baruch and Nicholson (1997) defined the first framework of contingent factors of telework. It was early days for telework adoption when the pair of scholars raised a voice to break away from the concept of going “to” work. The Industrial Revolution had largely impacted the notion of work separating home and work. The pair of researchers found in WFH an opportunity for employers to significantly reduce their property costs and gain from a motivated workforce who was saving commuting time and staying in the comfort of their home. They raised the question: “*why isn’t every firm looking to maximize homeworking?*” (Baruch & Nicholson, 1997, p.15). The results from the interviews held during the study paved way to define a 4-factor contingent model: (1) Home/work interface – referring to a wide range of conditions such as having dependent children at home, available home office space, easiness of use of electronic channels or issues with privacy invasion at home, to name a few; (2) The person – where personality, individual differences adapting to WFH such as self-control, self-determination,... are included; (3) The job – which considers job attributes such as level of autonomy, availability of distance learning systems or the amount of demand for face to face meetings, such as client meetings; (4) The organization – covering critical aspects on the employer’s end as having a supportive culture, setting up measurable outcomes for those WFH, or the reactions from those staying at the office. These factors were presented as critical to ensure effective design and rollout of telework programs in organizations. Nonetheless, Baruch and Nicholson had left open a door for future evolution of the model.

Covid-19 health crisis challenged the concept of telework up to that point in time, with a sudden general view of telework as a security practice. Belzunegui-Eraso and Erro-Garcés (2021) re-assessed Baruch and Nicholson (1997) four factor model under the new social context. This pair of researchers

extended the model adding a fifth factor covering environmental, safety and legal factors. Environmental factors can be found in the origins of the concept of telework, with the oil crisis and the need to reduce the environmental impact of “going to work”; which, on the other hand are still valid today. The legal aspects of telework, largely the lack of regulatory body, have contributed to the slow adoption of telework. With regards to safety, prior to Covid-19 there had been few cases of implementation of telework as results to crisis situations (Donnelly & Proctor-Thomson, 2015); this situation is changing now as the intensive exposure to telework during Covid-19 is changing the paradigm of remote work (Carillo et al., 2021). In sum, the environmental, legal and safety factor proposed by Belzunegui-Eraso and Erro-Garcés (2021) is to be considered in the study of effective implementation of telework nowadays. This thesis partly relies on these suggestions by, for example, analyzing the existence of telework-specific company regulations in our data collection.

Between the years 2000 and 2009 scholars showed an increased interest in teleworking which declined on the upcoming years prior to Covid-19. A possible explanation of these variations in interest maybe in inconsistent rhythms of telework adoption (Athanasidou & Theriou, 2021). The circumstances of telework adoption prior to Covid-19 pandemic have led researchers to focus on (1) debate whether the outcomes of telework are good or bad, and (2) unveiling the challenges associated with its implementation. Extant knowledge from each of these two topics are briefly presented now.

On one hand, research on telework outcomes has largely focus on listing benefits and drawbacks from telework, deriving in often inconclusive, contradictory, and paradoxical outcomes (Boell et al., 2016; Gajendran & Harrison, 2007). Looking for positive outcomes for the employer side, telework is long known by increasing productivity (Bloom et al., 2013; Kazekami, 2020), organizational commitment (Blahopoulou et al., 2022), individual job performance (Golden & Gajendran, 2019; Golden & Veiga, 2008); and reducing absenteeism and intent to leave (Bloom et al., 2013; Maruyama & Tietze, 2012). Bloom and his team (2013) ran a large-scale telework experiment in a 16,000-employee company in China. The results were ground-breaking in favor of telework. Performance gains of up to 13% were reported during the pilot-phase. These improvements almost doubled (22%) when the company extended the practice to voluntary adoption.

Overall, telework adoption can enable companies to accommodate in the digital economy. On the employee side, telework is often known by its positive impact on job satisfaction (Anderson et al., 2015; Miglioretti et al., 2022), job autonomy and work-life balance (Loon et al., 2018). When WFH, employees benefit from increased autonomy, flexibility, and focus (Fonner & Roloff, 2012). Psychological needs of teleworkers have been found different to those staying at the office (Brunelle & Fortin, 2021). The need for autonomy, competence, or relatedness is higher on individuals WFH. When these needs are properly managed by the organizations, teleworkers consistently report higher levels of job satisfaction than their office colleagues. In this sense, effective remote talent management strategies can help employers maintain their competitive advantage (Illegems & Verbeke, 2004); this is especially critical in a globalized world (Contreras et al., 2020).

The negative consequences of telework should also be thoroughly understood. Felstead and Henseke (2017) found teleworkers often suffer from intensified working conditions and difficulties to separate personal and professional remits. It has been posited that nuanced team design practices may be needed under telework for it to be effective (Loon et al., 2018). In Japan, the distance from the employer’s premises have revealed undesired effects, loss of productivity, when telework hours were too long (Kazekami, 2020). The physical disconnect from traditional workplace setting can produce a sense of job insecurity (Mills et al., 2001). This may be induced by the additional burden to gain

organizational visibility and having access to career opportunities (Bloom et al., 2013; Maruyama & Tietze, 2012). Being away from the central office naturally isolates coworkers both professionally and socially (Donnelly & Proctor-Thomson, 2015). These findings are in line with the consensus scholars have around isolation during telework; workplace isolation is one of the most recurrent longer-term drawbacks resulting from telework arrangements (Bloom et al., 2013; Illegems & Verbeke, 2004). Precisely, Illegems and Verbeke (2004) field study with a large group of managers in Belgium evidenced that the only strong negative effect perceived by teleworkers was professional isolation.

In sum, findings from research focus on telework outcomes is not conclusive of the positive or negative effect of it. To overcome this lack of consensus, future research agenda calls for the investigation of new telework outcomes such as work engagement, job satisfaction, and emotional and physical wellbeing (Athanasidou & Theriou, 2021).

The second major challenge encountered with the effective implementation of telework is the tensions created between teleworker and non-teleworker (Athanasidou & Theriou, 2021). The emergence of an “us and them” feelings emerging between teleworkers and those staying at the office has been repeatedly found in the literature (Collins, 2005). Home workers tend to bond with other home workers for increased social support. Overtime, office-based employees, and teleworkers tend to disconnect (Collins et al., 2016b). Findings from Sewell and Taskin (2015) reveal teleworkers fear that those remaining office-based would be hesitant of teleworker’s commitment and the extent of their contribution. Here again, relationships seem to deteriorate due to lack of face-to-face interactions, in this case between coworkers. Also, an increasing complexity in managing mixed groups has been flagged (Lautsch et al., 2009). Tensions in telework environments are increasingly seen as normal, Allen et al. (2015) advise on the need to adopt high-contextual research approach to study the telework phenomena; the team of researchers is confident that an evolution from the paradoxical perspective will find “win-win” opportunities, in context-dependent situations. Like Baruch and Nicholson (1997), more recent research continues to suggest the application of multifaceted (person, the job and organization) approaches to further investigate the success of telework programs (Loon et al., 2019). A more individualized understanding of individual, job, and organizational contexts that shape positive experiences of telework may bring light into ways to overcome the challenges of adoption (Bloom & van Reenen, 2006; Felstead & Henseke, 2017).

Telework scholars are increasingly stressing the importance of segmenting the research based on telework intensity; that is, the amount of time spent working outside the employer premises (Bailey & Kurland, 2002; Bloom et al., 2013; Fonner & Roloff, 2010; Gajendran & Harrison, 2007). Typically, the amount of time spent WFH was not registered. It is not until recently that the extent of telework has been brought to analysis in scientific research (Allen et al., 2015). In this sense, scholars are gaining a close consensus of what constitutes *high-intensity* in telework: (Fonner & Roloff, 2010) defined *high-intensity* telework it as working at least 3 days a week; for Konradt et al. (2003) the distinction lies in those teleworking more than 50% of their time; Gajendran and Harrison (2007) theoretical framework define high-intensity telework in more than 2.5 days a week. The segmented examination of results, based on intensity of telework, provide valuable evidence for practitioners to make managerial decisions to design their specific telework working conditions. For example, job satisfaction is found to be at its peak for those that telework a moderate amount of time (Golden & Veiga, 2005), as opposed to those teleworking too much or too little working hours. The extent of time working away from the employer’s office has also been associated with the quality of work-related relationships. Only a few years later, the same authors found that extensive teleworkers

experienced highest levels of job commitment and job performance (Golden & Veiga, 2008). Additionally, the extent of telework has been positively associated with organizational commitment and negatively associated with intention to leave (Golden, 2006). Intensification of remote work arrangements plays a major role in the sound implementation of telework (Kossek et al., 2009). The frequency and intensity of telework determine the willingness to continue working from home. In other words, the more one works from home, and the longer one has experienced this arrangement, the stronger the willingness to continue doing so and report higher levels of self-perceived productivity (Labrado et al., 2022).

2.1.1 Previous studies on telework, psychological distance, and wellbeing

This subsection presents the set of previous studies that, to the best of our knowledge, most closely relate with the research question of this thesis. Table 1 below captures the essence of what is known on the influence of psychological distance with coworkers on affective wellbeing at telework. The research design of this thesis is built considering this previous knowledge and attempts to contribute to academia and practitioners by drawing conclusions from the new empirical evidence provided.

Employee wellbeing is a long known critical factor for achieving both individual and organizational outcomes in the workplace (CIPD, 2022). Employee wellbeing has both cognitive and affective components (Warr, 1987). In this sense, affective wellbeing refers to the subjective experience of work the experienced quality of work as well as an overall feeling of happiness (van de Voorde et al., 2012). A feeling of affective wellbeing is built in combination of positive affect and negative affect. Thus, for affective wellbeing to exist at work, an employee must evaluate positive emotions more frequently than negative emotions (Vakkayil et al., 2017). Affective wellbeing is pivotal to for individual and organizational outcomes at work. Today's digitized world of work has raised the levels of strain held by knowledge workers. The pressure from global workforce markets, the need to work until an older age to support retirement or the increased immediacy of demands at work are some of the reasons behind detriments in affective wellbeing at work (Renee Baptiste, 2008). The presence of negative affect at work (e.g., stress, other mental health issues) is among the top reasons for absence from work (CIPD, 2022).

Wellbeing at work can be looked at from multiple dimensions. Occupational researchers have referred to wellbeing from varied terminology, including general happiness (Ryan & Deci, 2001), overall quality of experience at work (Grant et al., 2007), work-life balance (Lautsch & Kossek, 2011), job satisfaction (Holland et al., 2016), or psychological health (Warr, 1990). From a HRM perspective, wellbeing at work is often interrelated with structural factors (e.g., work conditions, job security) and social ones (e.g., social support, team-leader support) (Clarke & Hill, 2012). Wellbeing can also be seen in terms of the intersection between individual and work life experiences (Bloom & van Reenen, 2006). Researchers adopting this work-life-balance approach consider the effect work and non-work events can have as antecedents of the positive or negative wellbeing at work. In this vein, social interactions, and effective management of boundaries between work and personal lives are found key to maintain wellbeing (Grant et al., 2013). Successful organizational strategies involve the consideration of work and non-work conception of wellbeing at work (Kossek et al., 2014).

Van Horn et al. (2004) segmented the study of employee wellbeing in five dimensions, namely: cognitive, psychosomatic, professional, affective, and social wellbeing (van Horn et al., 2004). Of all dimensions, affective dimension is pivotal to employee wellbeing and has thus received most

attention from researchers (Charalampous et al., 2019). In their systematic literature review, Charalampous and his team (2019) found job satisfaction, emotional exhaustion and organizational commitment are measures often used to assess affective wellbeing. This investigation also flagged the fact some authors combined affective and social wellbeing (the ability to function well in social relationships at work) in their investigations when, remote work was part of the context. This combined lens is of particular interest to our research model, the results in these investigations should closely mirror our research design.

The impact of telework in employee's wellbeing is far from clear and often controversial (van der Lippe & Lippényi, 2019). Some authors, for example, have focused on the impact of digital connectivity in wellbeing as results of WFH. At moderate levels of connectivity, it produces beneficial effects as it enables remote flows of work, autonomy, and work-life balance (Golden & Gajendran, 2019; Leung & Zhang, 2017). At high levels of connectivity, it can override the benefits of telework, by generating interruptions that may threaten teleworker's flexibility, autonomy, or focus (Fonner & Roloff, 2012). Too much demand of connectivity at telework can derive in specific health issues, such as "technostress" (Ayyagari et al., 2011; Tarafdar et al., 2007). The varied range of potential effects, together with the current increased share of teleworkers, points to the importance of wellbeing at telework when designing remote work conditions (Wöhrmann & Ebner, 2021). Other researchers have focused on the effect telework has in work and life boundary management. Here the results remain inconclusive. For example, Allen et al. (2015) found teleworkers suffered from increased difficulties to set boundaries at the home office, resulting on threats to the physical and mental health of the employee, such as extended hours, technostress, limited workplace support, or professional isolation (Allen et al., 2015). Others, like Oakman et al. (2020) found WFH produced positive impact in psychological and social wellbeing, derived from improved work-life balance, increased autonomy, and reduced fatigue. Despite the controversy over some of the outcomes of telework in employee wellbeing, researchers have seemed to reach consensus on the negative effect professional isolation has on the affective state of the teleworker (Cooper & Kurland, 2002; Marshall et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2020b). This negative correlation is accentuated as the number of hours WFH (Golden & Eddleston, 2020).

The articles in table 1 are a selection of studies with closest resemblance to this project. The number of selected articles is limited, but so is the amount of telework research where affective wellbeing is the dependent variable, and psychological distance with coworkers a mediating factor. The selected studies share concern on the detrimental effect social isolation can have on teleworkers' wellbeing. We echo this concern. Sardeshmukh et al. (2012), for example, found coworker support depleted in high intensity telework settings, negatively impacting the affective states of teleworkers. In line with these findings, (Golden & Veiga (2008) proved the opposite was also true. Past studies on social connectedness in telework environments have part ways in two opposite forms of measurement. Some researchers have chosen to gauge the absence of connection and social presence, thus relying on isolation construct (Becker et al., 2022; Canonico, 2016; Spilker & Breugh, 2021) to examine its effect on the psychological state of remote workers. Findings showed isolation had a direct detrimental effect on teleworkers health. Results were evidenced through increased work-life conflict, emotional exhaustion, and lack of organizational commitment. Other researchers have chosen to instrumentalize feelings of being close to distant coworkers using positive constructs such as frequency of contacts (Anderson et al., 2015; Lautsch et al., 2009), or qualitative evaluation of quality of relationships (Golden, 2006; Grant et al., 2013). Perceived proximity theorists fall into this second group of researchers. The segmented approach Perceived proximity offers is rooted in Construal Level Theory (CLT) (Trope & Liberman, 2010), to build instruments of psychological distance. CLT

studies the relation between psychological distance and mental construal. CLT bases its theory on the simple idea that a mental representation of a person, an event or an object can vary along a continuum level of abstraction (Soderberg et al., 2015). Through abstraction, individuals can cross distances that separates them from the person, event, or the object they have mentally represented. Thus, different level of abstractions will construct representations with different levels of details, which in turn has an effect in intentions and behaviors (Lee, 2019). Perceived proximity researchers (O’Leary et al., 2014a; Ruiller et al., 2019; van Zoonen et al., 2021b; Wilson et al., 2008) recognize the high symbolic value involved in building mental construal. Perceived proximity theorists are not included in Table 1 as none of them considered wellbeing as part of their research. This is one of the main contributions of the present thesis. Perceived proximity will be further detailed in section 2.2.2.

Close coworker and supervisor relationships repeatedly appears as inducive to positive affect states on teleworkers (Fay & Kline, 2012; Golden, 2006; Grant et al., 2013; Lautsch et al., 2009). Thus, developing close relationships while at telework had a significant positive impact on job satisfaction. Some researchers have specifically focused on informal remote interactions, voluntarily prompted by coworkers. In this vein, Fay and Kline (2012) found teleworkers holding positive relationships with coworkers were happier when WFH. This pair of researchers found in the informal social talk (e.g., ‘coffee talk’) a positive association with job satisfaction. This statement seems to also hold true during crisis-induced (Covid-19) telework (Becker et al., 2022). Maybe induced by the fact that the need for relatedness within remote workers is stronger than those shown by office-based employees (Brunelle & Fortin, 2021; Deci & Ryan, 2014). In sum, there seems to be a consensus amongst researchers on the risk of isolation in intensive, long-term WFH; although contextual research on social connections in telework remains scarce, researchers anticipate positive effect in wellbeing derived from successful social connectedness. Thus, the design and implementation of such strategies remains part of telework management dilemma.

Table 1 - Previous studies on telework, wellbeing and psychological distance.

Authors	Research Question	Theories	Findings	Dependent variable	Sample	Methods
Golden (2006b)	What is the impact of telecommuting in virtual relationships (supervisor, co-workers, family) and its influence in job satisfaction?	Leader Member Exchange Quality (LMX) (Wayne et al., 1997). Team Member Exchange (TMX) (Seers, 1989).	Coworker and supervisor relationships mediate the impact of telework in job satisfaction. This relationship is not linear, with too much telework the influential role of relationships in job satisfaction decreases.	Job satisfaction.	N=294 white collar experienced telecommuters from a large technological company.	Quantitative study. Survey. Regression analysis.
Gajendran and Harrison (2007)	What is the effect of telecommuting in three psychological mediators (autonomy, work-life conflict, and quality of relationships at work)?	Psychological contract ((Rousseau, 1995). Media Richness Theory (Daft & Lengel, 1986). Social presence (Short et al. 1976).	Telecommuting does not seem to damage social ties. Working relationships are not affected by WFH unless telecommuting is intensified. Overall telecommuting is a good thing.	Job satisfaction. Turnover intent. Role stress. Perceived career progression.	N=46 quantitative papers using survey techniques to measure telework outcomes.	Meta-analytic literature review.
Lautsch et al. (2009)	What is the impact of limited face time on managerial practices to maintain motivation, support work-life balance and encourage citizenship behavior?	Work-family theories (Duxbury et al. 1998).	Perceptions of proximity of supervisors increases wellbeing through reduced work-family conflict.	Supervisor performance rating. Employee helping behavior. Work-family conflict.	N=90 dyads of supervisors and subordinates from 2 US firms.	Mixed method study.
Grant et al. (2013)	What are the psychological factors affecting job effectiveness, wellbeing and WLB in telework?	Boundary management (Kossek et al. 2012).	Building relationships and maintaining contact with coworkers improves the psychological wellbeing of those working from home. The increased use of remote technologies seems to have a positive effect in wellbeing at telework.	Job effectiveness. Wellbeing. Work-life balance.	N=11 participants from UK based firms mature with e-working practices	Exploratory study. Interviews.
Anderson et al. (2015)	Does telework improved daily affective wellbeing?	Affective Events Theory (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1966)	WFH improves psychological wellbeing. Psychological wellbeing at telework increases as social connections outside of work increases.	Affective wellbeing.	N=102 experienced teleworkers from US federal agency.	Quantitative study. Survey. Regression analysis.

<i>Fay and Kline (2015)</i>	<i>What is the mediating role of informal communications in high intensity telecommuting?</i>	<i>Structuration theory (Giddens, 1984; Weick, 1979). Constructivist theory (Delia et al. 1982).</i>	<i>Teleworkers holding positive relationships with coworkers feel happy WFH. Job satisfaction and socializing/informal talk are positively related.</i>	<i>Organizational commitment. Job satisfaction. Coworker liking.</i>	<i>N= 112 full time employees, extensive telecommuters.</i>	<i>Quantitative study. Survey. Regression analysis.</i>
<i>Charalampous et al. (2019)</i>	<i>What is the impact of e-working on the five dimensions of wellbeing?</i>	<i>Wellbeing dimensions (van Horn et al. 2004)</i>	<i>e-workers suffer from social isolation. Enhanced ICT-based connections with coworkers positively improves affective wellbeing.</i>	<i>Affective wellbeing. Social wellbeing. Professional wellbeing. Cognitive and Psychosomatic wellbeing.</i>	<i>N=63 studies</i>	<i>Systematic literature review.</i>
<i>Spilker and Breaugh, (2021)</i>	<i>Which factors predict telework isolation?</i>	<i>Framework of isolation (Wright & Silard, 2021). Evolutionary theory of loneliness (Cacioppo and Cacioppo, 2018).</i>	<i>Feeling isolated while working from home has a negative effect in teleworkers happiness. Long established relationships help prevent feelings of isolation while at telework.</i>	<i>Job satisfaction. Telework performance (perceived by supervisor).</i>	<i>N= 244 telecommuters and their supervisors.</i>	<i>Exploratory study.</i>
<i>Brunelle and Fortin (2021)</i>	<i>Are psychological needs of teleworkers different from those at the office?</i>	<i>Self-determination theory: (Deci & Ryan, 1985).</i>	<i>Teleworkers have a stronger psychological need for relatedness, compared with their office-based colleagues. It is possible to counteract the negative consequences of telework (social isolation) through increased relatedness. Teleworkers are more satisfied than office colleagues.</i>	<i>Job satisfaction. Autonomy. Competence. Relatedness.</i>	<i>Single company case (Canada) N=448 teleworkers and office based.</i>	<i>Quantitative study. Structural Equation Modeling.</i>
<i>Becker et al. (2022)</i>	<i>How did job control and loneliness impact employee wellbeing during forced telework?</i>	<i>Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Job demands control theory of stress (Kassek, 1979). Social base theory (Beckes & Coan, 2011).</i>	<i>Feelings of isolation during forced teleworker is detrimental to employee's health. Social relationship at telework help counteract the negative impact on wellbeing during crisis-induced telework.</i>	<i>Emotional exhaustion. Work-life balance.</i>	<i>N=334 MBA students</i>	<i>Quantitative study</i>
<i>Mehta and Sharma (2022)</i>	<i>What is the impact of organizational support in employee engagement and job satisfaction?</i>	<i>Job-Demands Resources (Bakker & Demereuti, 2007)</i>	<i>Teleworkers feel engaged when they can express their concerns, which in turn predicts job satisfaction. Anxiety moderates this relationship.</i>	<i>Employee Engagement. Job satisfaction. Organizational commitment.</i>	<i>N=181 heterogeneous workers during de pandemic.</i>	<i>Quantitative study. Structural Equation Modeling.</i>
<i>Efimov et al. (2022)</i>	<i>What is the impact of virtual leadership in employee wellbeing and feelings of isolation (during crisis induced WFH)?</i>	<i>Health Oriented Leadership (Franke et al. 2014)</i>	<i>Supportive supervisor interactions positively influence wellbeing in their team members.</i>	<i>Wellbeing. Job satisfaction.</i>	<i>N= 19 studies</i>	<i>Literature review.</i>

Source: Own elaboration

This section has presented the findings from previous research on telework which is mostly relevant to the model of this thesis project. Much research effort has been dedicated to other perspectives such as environmental impact, architecture and interior design, occupational health, or employment relations, to name a few. These have intentionally been not referred to in the literature reviewed as the interest to the dissertation argument is reduced.

2.1.2 Telework: a source of competitive advantage in the future of work

What is the relevance of telework, as a source of sustainable competitive advantage? Relevancy of telework has increased in recent times where flexible remote working arrangements became the norm in shaping future workplaces (Yang & Lin, 2022). The antecedents of telework research have relied on varied theoretical backgrounds to determine the relevancy of such form of work from a strategic management perspective.

To test the relevancy, grounding management theories have been examined to determine whether (positive) telework experiences enrich the value telework has as a source of competitive advantage in the future of work. Resource-Based view (RBV) (Barney, 1991) posits superior organizational performance can be derived from sustainable competitive advantages. This theory understands HRM practices can have a substantial impact on the firm's financial performance (Uribetxebarria et al., 2021). Thus, positive telework experiences can be seen as a source of competitive advantage in the digital era as means to attract and retain the right talent tool via flexibility gains and increased job satisfaction (Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021; Illegems & Verbeke, 2004). Under the Social Capital theory (Bourdieu, 1986) lens, an organization can find in its social network a powerful resource in which to build a sustainable competitive advantage. Social capital resides in the social resources of the organization, its social relationships (Tsai and Ghoshal, 1998). Social capital is found in the individual, linked with the social connections he/she acquires and disposes to use for his/her advancement. Telework adoption causes changes in the social structures of the work environment. These changes need to be properly managed to avoid loss of organizational outcomes derived from detriments in collaboration, knowledge exchange or ability to innovate (Yang et al., 2022). To determine whether telework adoption will create or destroy social capital, close attention will need to be paid to the ability of managers and HRM to ensure existing social capital is not destroyed and, maybe, new sources of social capital are created,

In sum, according to RBV theory, telework is a valuable source of sustainable competitive advantage in present and future business contexts. Following Social Capital theory, the formation of social ties in the remote work environment and the valuable use of the social networks cannot be left unmanaged under telework settings. Given this relevancy, the following paragraphs will further explain this line of thought.

Resource-Based View

Barney (1991) introduces the concept of RBV by which a firm's resources are used to enable the design and implementation of strategies. He stresses that resource heterogeneity of the firm and its ability to manage these (attract, recruit, retain, combine, ...) can be a valuable source of competitive

advantage. Over the last three decades, RBV has served as foundational theory for many scholars attempting to understand what drives firm performance variance within and across industries (Pereira & Bamel, 2021). Resources are often defined as tangible and intangible assets, owned, or controlled by the firm (Martínez-Sánchez et al., 2007). Under RBV, heterogeneity of available resources is a source of differential firm performance. The firm's capability to manage these resources in innovative ways will enable the firm to thrive in competitive markets, harnessing the environment opportunities. To name a few, the list of strategic resources that are found to promote the firm's competitiveness include human resources, organizational processes, traditional factors of production, social relationships and coordinating mechanisms, etc. The firm's strategic resources can be categorized into three types: physical, human, and organizational capital (Wernerfelt, 1984). RBV places emphasis in human capital being one of the main levers to gain competitive advantage (Guest, 2017). Since its inception, RBV has offered firms practical options to achieve sustainable competitive advantages and that is, maybe, the reason why it has evolved to be the most used theoretical framework by scholars in management studies (Collins, 2021).

If analyzed under the RBV lens, telework can be source of superior firm performance, through increased human capital available in the firm. The flexibility offered by telework programs can help employers attract, retain, and engage with the right skills in the market. Signaling flexible work arrangements within the firm's employer brand, where potential existing and potential employees find benefits in their personal wellbeing has been recognized a main avenue to address the human capital challenge (Cañibano, 2016).

The first RBV analysis of the impact of telework on large organizations was developed by Illegems and Verbeke (2004) in Belgium. They stressed the importance of studying the longer-term effects of telework in the organization's competitiveness. Through flexible work arrangements of time and/or place of work, employers can strengthen their human capital base gaining access to workers whose knowledge and skills are valuable, rare, and difficult to imitate. With this talent management lens in mind, these pair of researchers moved away from examining hard characteristics of the employees (e.g., commuting time) and focus on more outcome-led variables (e.g., job satisfaction). The impact of employee job satisfaction in the organizational competency is critical. Telework can affect the extrinsic components of job satisfaction, such as working conditions. What is interesting about the model they developed is a two-step selection process. This selection process does not refer to the worker's eligibility to telework (e.g., based on their work function or telecommuting distance), in contrast it defines two conditions that need to be in place for telework to be effective. First, the human resource manager should test positive to perception of telework as a valuable source of company's resource base; second, current or potential adopters of telework are confident telework will not harm their job satisfaction, provided a broader HRM practices are in place to realize the positive impacts of telework adoption. Thus, the existence of telework scheme in a firm, in which HRMs truly believe in, and broader HRM practices in place (e.g., equal promotion possibilities for teleworkers, adequate work equipment and resources) are necessary conditions for telework adoption to generate superior business outcomes, through increased job satisfaction of the right talented workforce.

Kaplan et al. (2018) brought attention to another critical factor in the sound implementation of telework, the role of the manager. Manager's attitude toward telework has a direct implication in the overall experience the employee has when working from home (Kossek et al., 2009). The adoption of telework implies additional effort on the manager side to adapt to the new situation such as reorganizing how remote team members cooperate and complete their tasks from home or monitoring and controlling work done outside of the office (van der Lippe and Lippenyi, 2020). In cases, short-

term arguments towards telework adoption made managers reluctant of it; only when the negotiating power of those requesting telework allowance was sufficiently high would managers be willing to adopt Den Dulk & de Ruijter (2008). Borrowing from Illegems and Verbeke (2004) model, managers' perception of telework is critical to build a competitive advantage out of it. Managers need to adapt their priorities and managerial styles to the new telework conditions to ensure the talented workforce remains satisfied under the new work conditions (Dandalt, 2021). Following RBV theory, managerial evaluation of telework would include factors such as development of human capital, operational functioning, or efficiency gains. Empirical evidence on the manager's perception of telework highlight the existence of other, not so rational, factors such as trust in the teleworker's commitment to work or a sense of job insecurity by not being visible in the organization (Golden & Eddleston, 2020; Hynes, 2016; Lembrechts et al., 2018). Luckily, those non-rational factors are limited in number. In order of importance explaining the variability in manager's perceptions, Silva-C et al. (2019) found three factors which explained half the variance in manager's attitude towards telework: (1) the perception of the organization being supportive of telework, (2) the importance of the work performed in their area, (3) the compatibility of this work with telework arrangements. In a lesser extent, the manager's previous experience with telework and their individual self-efficacy levels were also influential.

For telework to be a valuable business resource the employee needs to find it equally valuable. For firms to have access to the best available talent through the provision of flexible work arrangements, such as telework, they need to ensure the current and future employees' find in the WFH conditions the expected results. Employees expect from WFH conditions positive effects such as flexibility, autonomy, and reduced stress from interruptions to name a few (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007). Employers need to also ensure the drawbacks from telework are, at least, mitigated. Loss of professional interaction, reduced opportunities for promotion and detriments in social/professional interactions are some of the main negative effects reported by teleworkers (Becker et al., 2022). Understanding what leads to employee perceptions of telework is relevant to practitioners wanting to strengthen their human capital resource-base with telework adoption. Telework characteristics (amount of time, equipment provided, support structures, ...) have a positive association with job satisfaction in telework (Niebuhr et al., 2022). Niebuhr et al. (2022) study noted the autonomy gains while WFH positively influenced the psychological wellbeing of teleworkers, who revealed their willingness to continue WFH after Covid-19 pandemic.

Thompson et al. (2022) recent work revisited the motivations that lead workers to want to telework. During this study the team of researchers revealed that avoidance of commute was most frequent, followed by the desire to reduce costs and work-life balance. Interestingly, productivity arose as fourth motive, providing evidence that traditional work environments at the office may not be conducive of modern work. Employee propensity to telework remains today of high interest amongst telework researchers (Beck et al., 2020; Labrado et al., 2022).

In a globalized world, recruit, retain, motivate talented remote workforce becomes crucial to maintain the competitive advantage (Avolio et al., 2014). As aforementioned, the design of digital work strategies should consider the inclusion of effective telework programs to ensure the right talent is attracted and managed in future work environments (Niebuhr et al., 2022). The accelerated uptake of telework as results to Covid-19 and the increased preference of digital workers to continue WFH sets an optimistic future for telework future adoption rates. With this scenario in mind, companies must provide the best possible work environment to ensure the right talent is engaged and the highest possible work efficiency levels are attained (Belostecinic et al., 2022).

Social Capital theory

Social Capital theory (Bourdieu, 1986) contemplates social relationships as productive resources that can facilitate actions between firm's resources. Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) theoretical model shows how social capital can create value for firms as results of the combination and exchange of resources. Social capital evolves around different aspects of the social context, such as social ties. Social networks within the firm act as value systems that facilitate the actions between the individuals in the network (Tsai & Ghoshal, 1998)). Achievement of common vision or shared values and objectives help develop social capital which, in turn, facilitate individual and collective actions that benefit the whole organization. Thus, social capital creates value for the organization. Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) built on this principle and categorized the different aspects of social context into three dimensions, namely: the structural, the relational, and the cognitive dimension. The structural dimension refers to the social relationships (e.g., social ties, the personal contacts that can be used to obtain specific resources); the relational refers to the assets in which these relationships are grounded (e.g., trust, confidence, ...); lastly, the cognitive dimension refers to the attributes of the relationships (e.g., shared code of conduct) that facilitate the achievement of common goals. Thus, modern organizations should think of new ways to virtually connect employees, providing a psychologically safe environment to develop social capital in the digitized world of work.

The Social Capital relies in the potential resources everyone has through their own individual network (Cha et al., 2014). Therefore, the social networks that are created or maintained through telework environments can greatly benefit the company. The intensified use of electronic communications during WFH (e.g., online meetings, enterprise social media posting, wikis, ...) provide researchers and practitioners a new source of data of how social capital is created and maintained within the organization (Yang et al., 2022). Thus, the study of the social contexts during telework arrangements becomes crucial to understand how social capital is developed in a digitized world of work.

Social capital theorists are interested in key topics such as open innovation, organizational performance, resource management or knowledge sharing, among other themes. For these academics, the significance of relations is at the heart of value creation, in the form of social action (Bourdieu, 1986). The central importance given to network ties is originated in strong interpersonal relationships resulting in trust, cooperation, and collective action. The ties created and nurtured via remote social relations can be powerful actors explaining relative success of organizations transitioning to telework such as innovation, talent development and retention, to name a few (Adler & Kwon, 2002; Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021). Thus, there can be a positive association between technology enabled social interactions and the creation of social capital in the firms (Chen & McDonald, 2015). In the advent of telework, finding ways to effectively manage remote social ties remains a management dilemma. In this sense, this thesis project represents an opportunity to examine how social contexts are shaped and nurtured in telework settings.

Working away from the employer's premises, coworkers and supervisors will impact how employees perceive work, among other reasons, by changing the frequency and media used on social interactions. The higher the intensity of telework, the higher the chances for technology enabled social relations, and less for face-to-face ones. Here lies the importance for practitioners to design tools and ways of working to ensure social capital is maintained in the digital workspace. If social interaction with coworkers and supervisors is reduced when WFH, social capital will not be created,

and teleworkers will suffer from professional isolation (Cooper & Kurland, 2002). Designing for social supportive remote environments, where remote coworkers can provide help and can bring task clarification can help reduce job ambiguity, role conflict WFH, and ultimately create social capital through effective interactions between engaged, happy teleworkers. Positive social support can then be seen as a key enabler of the employee's affective attachment to the organization (Moqbel et al., 2013). These interactions can be beneficial to employees WFH. New intellectual capital can be built from close remote interaction and conversations where language and code are shared (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998). When this support is not present in WFH, negative social relations in the workplace become distrustful, resulting in lack of reciprocal behaviors (Collins et al., 2016b), destroying social capital.

Socialization in the workplace thus plays a major role in the sound implementation of telework (Lautsch et al., 2009). Remote workspaces place implicitly challenge the structure, spatial and temporal dynamics of the workers networks (Mehta & Sharma, 2022). In this context, receiving support from the organization and colleagues are valuable assets to sustain job satisfaction at level (Fay & Kline, 2012). Hence, having compatible coworkers, with whom employees can both formally and informally communicate can be seen as a source of social capital in modern organizations.

2.2 Theoretical framework

In a telework setting, employees are located outside the employer premises, but are expected to maintain connection with the company, mainly through electronic communications. As results of this, it is relevant to understand which distinctive characteristics of the remote social interactions shape fruitful telework experiences. The expectancy is set for these experiences to have a positive effect in the affective state of teleworkers (Blahopoulou et al., 2022). In this sense, we place the focal point of this dissertation in *the impact of perceived proximity and employee voice in employee affective wellbeing under telework arrangements*.

The study of social ties in the workplace has guided the review of literature undertaken during this project. Three grounded theories have been identified instrumental to our research model. First, in Perceived Proximity Theory (Wilson et al., 2008), we find a framework to assess the antecedents of psychological distance with a coworker. Second, in Affective Events Theory (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996), we find a framework to anticipate the outcome of perceived proximity (psychological wellbeing). The affective events theory posits that daily work events can have an effect in the affective state of the workers. Lastly, Social Presence Theory will be applied (Short et al., 1976). Social presence is an inherent quality of the medium used to communicate. As most work communications will be held using remote communication technologies, we will theorize about the effect social presence can play in employee voice mechanisms in telework.

The following paragraphs will describe the contributions each of these theories bring to the research design. Table 2 summarizes the contributions found in previous research on telework based on these three prominent theories.

Table 2 - Prominent theories and contribution to research questions

Wellbeing at telework	Employee outcomes	Contributions to the research question	Contributing authors
<i>Physical wellbeing</i>	<i>Mental health, stress, anxiety, depression, techstress.</i>	<p><i>Social isolation are negatively related with stress WFH.</i></p> <p><i>Lack of knowledge or fear to use company social media is a source of anxiety in remote work.</i></p> <p><i>The overload and complexity of communication technology contributes to stress WFH.</i></p> <p><i>Permanent work contact via ICTs during Covid-19 forced telework may have implications on mental health (anxiety, depression).</i></p>	<i>Tarafdar et al. (2007); Leung & Zhang, (2017); Mann & Holdsworth (2003); Sakka & Ahammad (2020)</i>
<i>Psychological wellbeing</i>	<i>Job/ life satisfaction, positive affect, negative affect.</i>	<p><i>Social isolation during telework negatively impacts emotions (e.g., irritability).</i></p> <p><i>Daily interactions during telework positively affects wellbeing.</i></p> <p><i>The use of virtual spaces to create personal connections helps mitigate isolation WFH.</i></p> <p><i>Maintaining positive work relationships is crucial to maintain levels of energy and positive affect.</i></p>	<i>Anderson et al. (2015); Becker et al. (2022); Grant et al. (2013); Fomer & Roloff (2012); Charalampous et al. (2019); Mehta & Sharma (2022).</i>
<i>Social wellbeing</i>	<i>Social support, management support.</i>	<p><i>Social connectedness WFH improves affective wellbeing when supportive management support is in place.</i></p> <p><i>Management support of WFH is pivotal to affective wellbeing during telework.</i></p> <p><i>The need to rely on ICTs to obtain social support is a source of emotional exhaustion in WFH.</i></p> <p><i>Coworker support positively influences affective wellbeing WFH in a curvilinear (inverted U-shape) way.</i></p>	<i>Grant et al. (2013); Golden & Veiga (2008); Charalampous et al. (2019); Mehta & Sharma (2022); Sardeshmukh et al. (2012)</i>

Source: Own elaboration

The design of telework communications should be closely related with the desired state of social interactions within coworkers, management, and Unions (Fonner & Roloff, 2012). In the absence of physical presence during regular telework arrangements attention needs to be driven towards psychological distance. As remote communications at work are held through technology-based channels and media, the research model of this thesis places a focal point in the ability of these communications to provide feelings of closeness to distant coworkers. In doing so we ground our research design on Perceived Proximity theory (Wilson et al., 2008). Perceived proximity states that feelings of closeness are a cognitive and affective process, not dependent on physical proximity. Perceived proximity is rooted in Construal Level Theory (Trope & Liberman, 2010). According to Construal Level Theory the individual's perception of an event is dependent on the psychological distance he/she perceives, thus understanding psychological distance with coworkers is pivotal to test the research model of this investigation. In this vein, the perceived proximity model broadens the theoretical understanding of remote coworker communications by including the subjective perception. Wilson and her team propose a dyadic construct to measure how close or far a teleworker feels from a fellow coworker. In other words, the construct will measure the psychological distance between pairs of coworkers. Learnings from what leads to psychological proximity can benefit managers to attain the benefits of collocation (access to most valuable talent, reduced facility space, environmental taxation, ...). Further explanation in the applicability of perceived proximity framework in the research design will be provided in sub-section 2.2.2.

The choice of communication technologies used to socially interact in the workplace is relevant to the ability to invoke social presence (Short et al., 1976) According to Short and his team, Social Presence in electronic communications measures the ability to evoke a sense of closeness during remote work interactions. Past research has shown that the characteristics of communication media can influence the sense of being present with a distant other but also the participation among the members of a group (Wilson et al., 2008; Yoo & Alavi, 2001). The higher the social presence the higher the influence of social interactions in each other's behaviors (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). A daily, yet powerful, example of this is "Airbnb", where in a matter of minutes the user feels as if he/she will be already enjoying being physically at their next holiday rental house (Chang & Lee, 2021). Our research design leans on social presence to examine the perceptions of remote communications while WFH, and their ability to influence affective wellbeing. We will specifically apply this lens to investigate remote expression of voice. Higher social presence is expected to arise from synchronous (e.g., live chat, ...), interpersonal (e.g., face to face, videoconferencing) interactions. Text-based communications such as blog or wiki provide the lowest social presence scores, despite the collaborative intent of the tools. Proximal relations imply the exchange of material and affective resources (Golden, 2006). We will examine whether the use of public social media to express one's voice or the participation in online voice activities organized by Unions of can alter the psychological wellbeing of teleworkers.

What is ultimately relevant to the present investigation is if and to what extent proximal relations with coworkers, or the expression of one's voice at work, influences psychological wellbeing at work. The Affective Events Theory (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996) supports this view proposing that different work events affect workers affective states. Examination of positive and negative events experienced by teleworkers indicate teleworkers may be more inclined to perceive more job-related positive events than negative, compared with peer coworkers working at the employer's site (Anderson et al., 2015). The affective events theory has been determinant to design the data collection instruments of this

investigation, suggesting indication to examine nuanced views of electronic communications at work (e.g., inclusion of informal events; segmentation of events organized by the employer or prompted by one of the coworkers in the dyad). Anderson and his team found teleworkers were more inclined to positively perceive work-related events than their office-based colleagues.

The remainder of section 2.2 describes the theoretical framework in referencing order to each of the dependent and independent variables in our research model.

2.2.1 Wellbeing at telework

The World Health Organization defines wellbeing as a “state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, not merely absence of disease or infirmity” (World Health Organization, 1946: 894). In the workplace context, the study of employee wellbeing has always been found of strategically importance in the research of organizational performance (Clarke & Hill, 2012). Scholars have focused on the importance of wellbeing on its own right (Guest, 2017; Warr, 1990), but also on wellbeing as an important mechanism to drive individual and organizational performance (Blahopoulou et al., 2022; Grant et al., 2013; Peccei & van de Voorde, 2019). The researchers’ interest in wellbeing is also derived from the lack of theoretical model or scientific tools to measure wellbeing (Pradhan & Hati, 2022).

Warr et al. (1983) defined employee wellbeing more broadly, as an overall quality of an employee’s work experience. (Grant et al., 2013; p. 52) defined it as “the overall quality of an employee’s experience and functioning at work”. This broad definition covers the three dimensions that are widely accepted as the core elements of wellbeing: physical, psychological, and sociological. Employee wellbeing is a concept that contains different indicators, based on emotions, attitudes and moods (Fisher, 2014).

According to wellbeing researchers, wellbeing at telework should be measured as the overall experience of WFH (Warr et al., 1983), in this way it is considered an inclusive concept (Vakkayil et al., 2017). Following this idea, former researchers have studied various elements conducive to different affective states while WFH. Examples of these are workplace social support, willingness to reciprocate, cooperation, and perceived trust from supervisors or the employer (Grant et al., 2007; Guest, 2017). Practitioners often restrict this inclusive view to one dimension, such as job satisfaction. As this is not the case, Grant and his made one of the biggest contributions to holistically categorize employee wellbeing dimensions. The authors distinguish three dimensions of employee wellbeing: physical, psychological, and social. The physical dimension is often associated with health and mental health like injuries or work-related stress levels. The psychological dimension refers to the way in which an employee experiences work; it focuses on the subjective perception; it includes agency, satisfaction, self-respect, and capabilities (Grant et al., 2013). Finally, the social dimension refers to the quality of the relationships with co-workers, and the community (Vakkayil et al., 2017). Table 3, presents the key findings from wellbeing research relevant to the research question of this thesis.

Table 3 - Key findings from wellbeing at telework studies

Wellbeing at telework	Contributions to the research question	Contributing authors
<i>Positive impact in wellbeing at telework</i>	<p><i>Social connectedness WFH improves affective wellbeing, when supportive management support is in place.</i></p> <p><i>Management support of WFH is pivotal to affective wellbeing during telework.</i></p> <p><i>Maintaining positive work relationships is crucial to maintain levels of energy and positive affect.</i></p> <p><i>The use of virtual spaces to create personal connections helps mitigate isolation WFH.</i></p> <p><i>Coworker support positively influences affective wellbeing WFH, in a curvilinear (inverted U-shape) way.</i></p>	<p><i>Anderson et al. (2015); Charalampous et al. (2019); Grant et al. (2013); Golden & Veiga (2008); Charalampous et al. (2019); Mehta & Sharma (2022); Sardeshmukh et al. (2012)</i></p>
<i>Negative impact in wellbeing at telework</i>	<p><i>Social isolation during telework negatively impacts emotions.</i></p> <p><i>Lack of knowledge or fear to use company social media is a source of anxiety in remote work.</i></p> <p><i>The overload and complexity of communication technology contributes to stress WFH.</i></p> <p><i>The need to rely on ICTs to obtain social support is a source of emotional exhaustion in WFH.</i></p> <p><i>Permanent work contacts via ICTs, during Covid-19 forced telework, may have implications on mental health (anxiety, depression).</i></p>	<p><i>Becker et al. (2022); Grant et al. (2013); Fomer & Roloff (2012); Mehta & Sharma (2022). Tarafdar et al. (2007); Leung & Zhang, (2017); Mann & Holdsworth (2003); Sakka & Ahammad (2020)</i></p>

Source: Own elaboration

Maintaining a healthy and motivated workforce becomes crucial in current times, where changes are continuous. Affective wellbeing (Warr et al., 1983) is mostly applied in work-related studies, best explained using multiple dimensions such as depression, enthusiasm, anxiety, or comfort. Despite these difficulties, maintaining focus in the employee’s feelings during telework remains important; managerial or HRM expectations from telework will not materialized if the employee does not feel satisfied (Thompson et al., 2022). Results for examination of affective wellbeing for those that telework present high variability of scores. Such variability is related with individual differences, such as people’s tendency to ruminate or their individual social connectedness (Allen et al., 2015). Communication and support from coworkers emerged as important factors to balance the psychological aspects behind affective wellbeing (Grant et al., 2013).

Nowadays, employee wellbeing is becoming central theme in employer branding strategies to attract and retain key talent in the digital era (Grant et al., 2019). Employers recognize the value of introducing organizational measures to promote the health and wellbeing of their employees (Pagán-Castaño et al., 2020). Large multinational firms like Accenture, Deloitte, Fujitsu, IBM, include wellness in the value proposition to their current and future employees. Industry players place efforts on attaining public recognition of the living promise through worldwide known awards like Great Place to Work© (www.greatplacetowork.com). In line with these trends, research shows the importance of wellbeing in the outcomes and chances of survival of large organizations (Grant et al., 2013) by affecting costs related with illness and absenteeism, turnover, discretionary effort, and job performance, to name a few.

Unfortunately, telework wellbeing is an elastic term, meaning different things to different people (Ho & Kuvaas, 2020). The effects it can have on employees are relevant and varied. From increased job satisfaction (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007; Kazekami, 2020); to reduced work-family conflicts (Allen et al., 2015), and, in general, increased productivity (Bloom et al., 2013). However, the extent to which this practice is beneficial to employee wellbeing is still controversial (Becker et al., 2022; Golden & Gajendran, 2019). On the one hand, studies have shown that telework produces better work-life balance and less emotional exhaustion (Sardeshmukh et al., 2012), especially if perceived autonomy is increased during telework (Gajendran et al., 2015). This holds true in Covid-19 forced telework; despite the increased job demands telework measures brought increased job control acted as relief to the emotional exhaustion the crisis had already produced. On the other hand, telework can negatively affect wellbeing through social isolation, fatigue from videocalls, difficulty in managing digital communications or difficulty to effectively manage work-life balance (Adamovic, 2022). Also, as the effect of telework in interpersonal relations remain unclear, researchers find inconclusive evidence derived from these, for example: knowledge sharing or team performance (Coenen & Kok, 2014). With these, and more, inconclusive findings from wellbeing at telework, further context rich telework research is needed (Kossek et al., 2009; Memon et al., 2022).

The uprising of telework in contemporary times is enabled by an explosion of technology advancements employed by organizations, nonetheless the body of literature on how remote working practice may affect wellbeing is limited (Grant et al., 2013). Specifically, individuals involved in knowledge work can now access their work and relate with their coworkers and supervisors from anywhere and anytime. However, current evidence of research is not conclusive on the net beneficial effective of telework on employee's wellbeing (Charalampous et al., 2019). Albeit the importance of holistically addressing wellbeing at work, research points at the importance of individually examining the dimensions of wellbeing at work, as contradictory effects can be found across dimensions (Pagán-Castaño et al., 2020); in fact, few studies demonstrate the joint effect of the three dimensions of wellbeing. The remainder of this section will review the theoretical grounds and conclusions in each of the employee wellbeing dimensions.

The physical dimension

Physical wellbeing captures physiological indicators of health and wellness at the workplace such as stress, anxiety, or sense of energy (Grant et al., 2013; Guest, 2017). Physiological outcomes of poor wellbeing are found in memory loss, fatigue, or levels of alertness (Clarke & Hill, 2012). Employee stress is the major aspect that has widely been studied on this dimension. Telework researchers often relay on the Job Demand-Resource (JD-R) Model (Bakker et al., 2003) to investigate the impact of telework in employee's health (Peccei & van de Voorde, 2019; Scheibe et al., 2022). The JD-R model integrates the effects of job demands (e.g., workload, time pressure), which often consume energy and effort, with the motivational effect found in job resources (e.g., social support, physical resources) which are those that help the individual achieve his/her work goals. The resulting model helps predict levels of engagement or exhaustion in specific work contexts (Sardeshmukh et al., 2012). Examples of job resources in telework are found in autonomy, work equipment, caring culture, or leadership (Seinsche et al., 2023), to name a few. Job demands affected by telework are found in the need to learn new technologies, or increased workload (Wong et al., 2022). Reduced job demands or

increased job resources during telework, help reduce the level of strain and physiological effects of WFH.

Telework is often associated with a high demanding environment, although this is not necessarily associated with negative physical wellbeing, anxiety for example. Xia et al. (2020) found that is the limited access to job resources what triggers the health issues. Xia and his team found in low organizational support and task variety at telework the source of job dissatisfaction and anxiety manifested by the participants in their study. WFH arrangements are associated with the resource side of the JD-R model (Hoornweg et al., 2016) and its ability to affect employee wellbeing is directly associated with the value the job and personal resources provide to the individual.

Job autonomy has been raised as one of the prevalent resources from remote work. The increased autonomy experienced when WFH is positively associated with job engagement and satisfaction. Charalampous et al. (2019) associated job autonomy with reduction in strain, through the less perceived sensation of invasion of privacy. Autonomy at telework has also been proven valuable to reduce emotional exhaustion at telework. Interestingly, van der Lippe and Lippényi (2019) observed that autonomous teleworkers expressed increased collegial behaviors when they spend time at the office, to compensate for the reduced interactions when working in the comfort of their home office.

The effects of job autonomy can also affect the personal lives of teleworkers. For example, job related factors, such as low job control has been found to alter the stress levels which, in turn, impact dietary habits or consumption levels of alcohol or tobacco (Clarke & Hill, 2012). Also, when working at home, the presence of children, partners, having to contribute to household chores impacts the daily physical activity of those WFH (Galanti et al., 2021), in different ways. During an empirical study with British journalists, Mann & Holdsworth (2003) found the mental and physical health of WFH journalists suffered from higher levels of negative emotions (e.g., loneliness, worry, guilt) than their office-based employees. WFH can lead to over-work, irritability from loneliness or difficulties setting boundaries between work and home life. (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007). These situations can prevent the restorative effects of home, which can be now contaminated with work-related environment (Grant et al., 2013). In this vein, Tarafdar et al. (2007) developed the concept of *technostress* (strain due to the use of ICTs). The increased dependency on the use of technology in our daily lives has given name to a mental and physiological arousal resulting from the difficulties to cope with these technologies in a healthy manner. Factors contributing to technostress levels are found to include self-efficacy, technology complexity, pervasive connectivity, multitasking (Leung & Zhang, 2017). Technostress is a concept that has been generally studied in the context of virtual work. Earlier research focuses on the effect of ICT usage during work hours. Ayyagari et al. (2011) found work overload and role ambiguity a dominant source of technostress. Over time, a gradual shift has appeared to place lens on longer format, less predictable, longer form of after-hours work engagement through technology-enabled connectivity (Carillo et al., 2021).

Several segmentations of results have been analyzed in the literature. Gender distinctions, for example, were not conclusive enough. During a longitudinal study, Kim et al. (2010) found women WFH experience reduced levels of stress but increased fatigue due to their inability to switch off. Kazekami (2020) large scale panel in Japan found no impact on stress nor on happiness for Japanese women WFH. During the Japanese investigation, male teleworkers did benefit from reduced stress and increased happiness. Telework intensity has also been examined to test whether the number of days WFH was influential to impacts in wellbeing. Here, the findings are more conclusive. Golden & Veiga (2005), for example, found intensive teleworkers benefited from autonomy gains more fully.

Similar results were found during Covid-19 enforced telework (Galanti et al., 2021). The examination of telework conditions under the eyes of employees with disabilities is still scarce. Schur et al. (2020) studied the impact of telework across a variety of disabilities. The team of researchers found that employees in situation of mobility impairment can benefit from the adjustments available at home; people with complex communication needs can benefit from the use of by-default functionalities in online communications (such as text to speech, live transcript, or augmentative communication) or the new way of communicating remote work provides (e.g., use of chat, or videoconferencing). McNaughton et al. (2014) precisely studied the perceived implications of telework for a group of teleworkers with a certified mental disability. The participants worked from home at least 10 hours a week and were experienced in the use of augmentative communications. The benefits shared by the participants included efficiency gains from not having to commute to the office, reduced stress from working at the comfort of their home, and reduced fatigue from being able to take short breaks at home.

In sum, measuring the impact of work arrangements in employee wellbeing is not straightforward (Peccei & van de Voorde, 2019). Not only it depends on the arrangement itself (e.g., granting access to telework) but also on how such arrangement is implemented (e.g., job control measures or support structures in place) and the subjective experience of it by the individual (e.g., negative, positive emotions) (Xia et al., 2020).

The psychological dimension

Psychologists have long studied psychological wellbeing, which is based on the subjective experience of individuals. A distinction has been made between eudemonic and hedonic wellbeing. Eudemonic wellbeing is represented by finding meaning and fulfillment at work and is represented in forms of self-expression. Hedonic wellbeing is often represented as job satisfaction and is driven by needs of rewards/ pleasure, articulated in positive or negative feelings in individuals' judgements (Deci & Ryan, 1985) Employee psychological wellbeing has mostly been studied under the hedonic approach, commonly measured with job satisfaction. Eudemonic components of wellbeing are measured through engagement or purpose, as examples. Although less commonly found, some scholars prefer to use the eudemonic component; they argue job satisfaction is a passive state, predicting high levels of job satisfaction should not be interpreted as human interest in fulfilment or the realization of human potential (Grant et al., 2013). This theoretical lens of hedonic wellbeing features two characteristics: (1) the assessment of life satisfaction and (2) the superiority of positive feelings over negative ones (Fisher, 2014; Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996). The main operationalization of hedonic wellbeing is based on indicators of positive affect, negative affect, and life satisfaction (Hoffmann-Burdzińska & Rutkowska, 2015). Subjective wellbeing at work focuses on subjective experiences and job performance. Happiness at work measures both cognitive and affective states through elements such as satisfaction, affective wellbeing, or commitment at work (Pagán-Castaño et al., 2020). Workplace happiness leads to better performance, safety, and customer satisfaction (Fisher, 2014). Research to date anticipates happiness can be derived from improvements in work-family balance, reductions in stress levels, increased autonomy in time management and the lack of direct supervision to perform tasks (Anderson et al., 2015; Fonner & Roloff, 2010; Kossek et al., 2009). However, for this positive subjective experience to appear, both managerial and coworker support is required.

There is consensus on the positive impact WFH has on job satisfaction (Brunelle & Fortin, 2021; Gajendran & Harrison, 2007; Golden, 2006), but still, what makes telework experience a pleasant one is far from clear (Wöhrmann & Ebner, 2021). Maybe this is so because job satisfaction is an attitudinal variable, it represents a broad evaluation about the worker's job or circumstances, but it lacks the ability to measure the worker's affective state like job anxiety, enthusiasm, aspiration, or subjective competence. Fisher (2014) suggested that wellbeing should be approached as a combination of job satisfaction, engagement, and the affective perspective of organizational commitment. In simple terms, job satisfaction and affective wellbeing are distinctive concepts. The Affective Events theory (AET) (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996) is supportive of this distinction: job satisfaction is not an affective reaction to one's job or a situation but rather an evaluative judgement of it. The evaluation can be influenced by both the emotional experiences and the structural belief antecedents. Following this view, Avolio et al. (2014) recognizes both, cognitive evaluations and affect, can cross levels and influence employee wellbeing at work. The distinction proposed by AET leads quickly to the conclusion that different measurements should be applied for each phenomenon. Results from the recent crisis-induced telework period confirmed the cause-effect relation between both constructs: telework satisfaction predicts subjective wellbeing (Blahopoulou et al., 2022). Given the above, daily events in the workplace (e.g., remote communications, social interactions at work, ...) become proximal antecedents of affective experiences at work. Examples of these antecedents can be found in telework literature. Differences in the effect of WFH in psychological wellbeing have been found in gender (Kossek et al. 2009), job role (Leclercq-Vandelamnoitte, 2021), extent of telework (Golden and Veiga, 2005; Beauregard et al., 2019), or maturity of telework arrangements in the firm (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007), to name a few. The following paragraphs illustrate what is already known about affective experiences at telework.

In organizations where the employer provides for telework arrangement, this arrangement can be perceived by teleworkers as a sign their employer cares about their wellbeing (Moqbel et al., 2013). Some occupational studies have shown negative consequences reflected in emotional exhaustion from work intensification, tight deadlines, or unpaid overtime (Golden, 2006b; Sardeshmukh et al., 2012). Other authors pointed out teleworkers benefit from better work-life balance and reduced stress from distractions or toxic relations in the office (Fonner & Roloff, 2012; Kazekami, 2020).

The longevity of telework arrangements within an organization can also variate the expected psychological outcomes of telework. According to Gajendran and Harrison (2007) investigation, the lack of telework normative, can cause telework to be perceived as a "special" arrangement. In this situation, teleworkers are more likely to feel indebted towards managers or the company (Canonic, 2016). Over time, the maturity of telework adoption within an organization may be such that allowing telework arrangement becomes customary. With telework maturity, through company policies, may come the loss of a sense of being "special", thus deteriorating the reciprocity cycle (Beauregard et al., 2019a). With telework maturity also comes changes in the way work is done and supervised. (Grant et al., 2019) contribute to the literature of mature telework environments with the development of an *e-work life* scale. The *e-work life* scale, which examines the working experience of teleworkers, refers to the wellbeing dimension of study as the ability to self-manage wellness while teleworking. The ability to self-manage the quantity and quality of communications at telework was found critical. This finding is in line with the *connectivity* paradox (Leonardi et al., 2010) whereby the amount of connectivity has an effect in the affective state of teleworkers and these, as a reaction, can decide to self-manage how and when they are available to be contacted. The finding from Grant and the team is also relevant for the research questions in this thesis because it recognizes ICT-based interactions as affective events (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996) in remote work. Recent telework researchers have

coined the term “Zoom fatigue” (Bailenson, 2021), referring to the emotional effect of digital social connections in modern workplaces. Bailenson (2021) found it is not the frequency of use of social media that affects users but the emotional connection the users have with social media. Thus, the affective consequences of digital connections are increasingly seen as antecedents of wellbeing during telework.

The ability to telework during Covid-19 pandemic have provided unexperienced teleworkers the chance to stay focus on work and benefit from coworker and supervisor support, thus protecting the employee’s psychological wellbeing (Blahopoulou et al., 2022; Memon et al., 2022). Miglioretti et al., (2022) captured the learnings from Covid-19 WFH in a telework quality framework. These authors found a positive association between contextual factors (e.g., worktime flexibility or engaging management style) with high quality telework and employee wellbeing. In this line, Becker et al. (2022) recommends the use of virtual spaces to create more personal connections in future remote workplaces, as means to counterbalance the negative effect isolation has on employee wellbeing.

The research model in this thesis is based on the hedonic component to measure wellbeing at telework, the dependent variable. Specifically, the thesis will examine antecedent factors of psychological aspects of hedonic wellbeing of teleworkers, in large organizations. We attempt to contribute former research on psychological wellbeing of teleworkers by examining the influential role perceived proximity or the expression of voice can play in such wellbeing.

The social dimension

Social wellbeing at work focuses on the qualities of relations and interactions (Pagán-Castaño et al., 2020). These interactions can occur between employees, between employees and their supervisor, or the organization. The social dimension of wellbeing is recurrent in modern wellbeing conceptual models (van de Voorde et al., 2012). Social factors impacting wellbeing include relations with supervisors, ability to decide on work-life balance arrangements, or the existence of social support structures in the workplace, to name a few (Clarke & Hill, 2012). Coworker support during WFH reduces the risk of social isolation and provides means to solve any work-life balance that may occur. These benefits are found positively connected with job satisfaction and wellbeing (Irawanto et al., 2021). Internal communication programs are also critical for employee wellbeing; these provide means to stay tuned to organizational updates, available resources, or opportunities for development (Pagán-Castaño et al., 2020). This may be especially relevant during transition to telework adoption when awareness and access to newly accommodated work conditions are most relevant. Information campaigns from Unions about telework collective agreements are another example of internal communication programs relevant for those under telework arrangements. Although research on the shaping of social support structures in the telework environments is still limited (Collins et al., 2016b; van der Lippe & Lippényi, 2019), it has been recently advised the power of social media usage for work-related reasons in fostering employee wellbeing through employee brand advocacy (Sakka & Ahammad, 2020). Thus, it becomes clear that social relationships have an impact on teleworker’s wellbeing (Fonner & Roloff, 2012; Ho & Kuvaas, 2020).

Social wellbeing in telework is not free of added complexities. Telework inevitably reduces the number of face-to-face interactions, which may in turn reduce the level of richness in the relationship with coworkers or team members (Golden, 2006). Thus, social support is expected to deteriorate

during telework. The need for greater reliance upon ICT-based communications is expected to negatively affect trust, feedback, and conflict, which in turn can lead to emotional exhaustion (Sardeshmukh et al., 2012). The social acceptance of a telework program becomes determinant for its success (Kossek et al., 2009). After the large scale telework experiment Bloom and his team (2013) run in China (N=16,000), participants were asked whether they wanted to maintain the telework arrangements or return to the office. Every other participant volunteered to go back to the office, alleging social reasons (Bloom et al., 2013). The social dimension of wellbeing at telework finds antecedents in the social connectedness, organizational support, and colleague support available (Oakman et al., 2020). Each of these dimensions will be further analyzed under the social wellbeing lens.

Firstly, social connectedness at telework will be analyzed. Given the structure of work arrangements at telework (e.g., reduced opportunities of face-to-face encounters), there is a general concern that teleworkers may experience lack of social support (Mann & Holdsworth, 2003). In the past, teleworkers have shown higher levels of loneliness, in comparison with office-based employees. This loneliness has negative consequences in affective bond with the work environment. Nonetheless, results from Covid-19 indicate that social communications WFH became solid within existing networks (Yang et al., 2022). For example, the study of the network structures revealed that pre-existing connections within the firm strengthened during the telework period. The overall load of communications within the organization grew during the period but they were, for the most part, held with established conn. Hardly any new social ties were created. The authors imply this may have been the result of protective measures adopted by employees as results of the health crisis. Interactions with close connections are richer in information quality and emotional weight (Ruiller et al., 2019). Also, from a time-consuming perspective, maintaining a close tie is a less demanding activity than obtaining the same output from a new connection (Seinsche et al., 2022). In short, the results from Yang and his team foresee dreadful impact in innovation and collaboration in the firm, through lack of new social ties being made, but, in the other hand, positive results in team activity or existing social ties may be anticipated. In turn, the changes in the social connectedness in telework intensive organizations need further exploration with regards to its effects in employee wellbeing.

New or existing ones, healthy social interactions WFH are key to maintaining the levels of wellbeing (Grant et al., 2013). As healthy relationships require the exchange of both material and affective resources (Blau, 1964), the wide range of technologies available for communications requires for employees to effectively choose the appropriate channel for each type of exchange. In the absence of face-to-face interactions, the use of rich-media communication tools (e.g., videoconference) can give multiple cues such as face and, at least, partial body language. This richness should add a feeling of closeness in the communication (Ortiz De Guinea et al., 2012). The level of interactivity provided by certain tools (e.g., instant messaging) can offer the necessary affective resources (Burgoon et al., 2002). According to AET (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996) the teleworkers who experience positive events at telework will benefit from increased positive affect. Telework research using AET show that the effect of events in the affective states of employees is more beneficial the days they telework, compared with the consequences of the events experienced the days working from the office (Anderson et al., 2015). Interestingly, Anderson and her team found that increased social connectedness moderated the effect of positive experiences in positive affect when WFH.

Under WFH arrangements socialization mostly occurs over ICT-based interactions. Thus, social connectedness in telework is dependent on the ability to be present over technological means. In this sense, Social Presence theory (Short et al., 1976) argues presence relies in the quality of

communication medium; social presence provides a measure to its ability to evoke a sense of closeness. In other words, social presence is the degree to which a person is perceived as being “there” or “present” in mediated communication. Former communications theories believed the number of available cues in the communication (e.g., visual) are expected to produce the highest social presence (Daft & Lengel, 1986). Face-to-face, or videoconference for that matter would then be best placed to produce higher social presence (Burgoon et al., 2002). For example, instant messaging or phone communications present higher opportunities to clarify any ambiguity. In a similar sense, the use of lean communications such as email or wikis, where information can be accurately exchanged has been considered valuable to build social presence (Gunawardena, 1995). In sum, higher social presence is associated with greater personalized communication, communication richness and discussion, and it cannot be measured solely on the hard characteristics of the media (Burgoon et al., 2002). Fonner and Roloff (2012) examined social presence through a set of channels used in telework, namely videoconference, face to face, telephone, instant messaging, and email. These researchers found social presence was positively related with all media used except for email. Phone conversations (high in interactivity, low in visual cues) showed the highest levels of social presence. Overall, Fonner and Roloff found the higher the social presence in telework, the higher the affective attachment of the employee with their employer. With the advent of telework in the future of workplaces, finding ways to optimize social presence through effective combination of technologies in the organization becomes relevant to employee’s affective wellbeing at work.

Modern organizations are turning into the power of work-related social media usage to counterbalance the lack of office-based social connection. By doing so, the employers incorporate new communication channels without the need to train the employees on their use, because these are already part of their daily lives. The use of enterprise social media has multiple benefits for remote work organizations. For example, engagement with the enterprise social media enables the teleworker to relate to the organization, feel part of the company and the corporate culture (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). The informal interactions that are established with company stakeholders are found more authentic and personal (Dreher, 2014). A stronger identification with the employer brand is obtained. Gains in bonding with the company culture and increased social interactions have been found to positively increase the psychological and social wellbeing of teleworkers (Sakka & Ahammad, 2020). According to Sakka and Ahammad study, the beneficial effects of social media usage in employee wellbeing is derived from increased informal, close conversations with relevant members of the organizations, as well as proliferation of open conversations to exchange ideas or solve problems.

Telework environments can add complexity to manage the social connectedness of the organization. Transition to telework arrangements is found to produce changes in pre-existing social structures (Yang & Lin, 2022). In the absence of face-to-face interactions social identity becomes static and hard to expand. Researchers explain the development of siloes in intensive WFH contexts is a protective measure to thrive in a physically distant work environment. From a telework management perspective, there is an increased difficulty to track and remediate weakened connections amongst certain groups of employees as results of telework.

The second dimension of social relations refers to organizational and management support. This dimension is especially relevant to providing positive telework experiences (Kowalski & Swanson, 2005). The mere fact that, prior to Covid-19, access to telework was reliant on manager’s granting access to it, makes the role of the manager a determinant in today’s telework experience (Ruiller et al., 2019). Golden and Veiga (2008) studied the impact of superior-subordinate relationships in a group (N=379) of knowledge workers and found that relationship quality positively influenced job

satisfaction. Reciprocal affective behaviors were found in employees with supportive managers, regardless of the amount of time they spent WFH. Recent research highlights the importance of management support to maintain motivation and energy levels up during Covid-19 telework (Mehta & Sharma, 2022). Miglioretti et al. (2022) call the need of transformational leadership styles in post Covid-19 telework environments. In sum, simply providing for telework resources (e.g., technological infrastructure, training, ...) is not enough to provoke positive WFH experiences to occur. Other organizational and managerial support aspects (e.g., supportive leadership and culture) are required.

The development of supportive leadership styles in telework, though, needs to be understood from the cultural shift it implies in management paradigms, prevalent from contexts where face-to-face and colocation was the norm (Golden & Veiga, 2008). Managers and employees have long held different views on the expected outcomes of telework (e.g., productivity, autonomy, commitment) (Canónico, 2016). Teleworkers are more inclined to perceive the positive side of telework than their supervisors who, in turn, find in telework a much less favorable work scenario, with long, restrictive lists of conditions to grant access to telework (Silva-C et al., 2019). In short, managers are known to generally mistrust telework arrangements (Kaplan et al., 2018), deriving in attitudes which are not beneficial to teleworkers. Some remote managers have expressed their difficulty to break apart from traditional control management mode (Golden & Veiga, 2008). In general, they suffer from professional isolation (Spilker & Breaugh, 2021). The affective states of the managers have a direct impact in their team members affective states (Yang & Lin, 2022). Ruiller and her team (2019) found in increased shared identity and close communications a way for managers to build positive experiences at telework, through trustworthy superior-subordinate relationships. In sum, for organizational and management support to positively enhance social wellbeing during telework, companies and middle managers need to avoid unnecessary control of remote tasks and embark themselves in ways to develop a caring culture in the remote work environment (Mehta & Sharma, 2022).

Lastly, it's important to note the role of coworker relations in social wellbeing. Coworker support has significant influence on psychological wellbeing for those WFH (Grant et al., 2013). Some researchers analyze coworker relations based on the number of interactions held while WFH. Leonardi et al. (2010) found teleworkers may suffer from excess of connectivity with their fellow coworkers. During their study, Leonardi and his team found longer-term respondents revealed being forced to switch off the technology (instant messaging) to be able to work, as a strategy to become unreachable by their office-located colleagues. In other words, what initially was a source of wellbeing (work-life balance and job autonomy) transformed into a source of strain (inability to concentrate and work-family conflicts) derived from too much connectivity. According to Yang et al. (2022), during Covid-19 enforced telework, coworker communication shifted towards asynchronous channels (e.g., emails, instant messaging, shared repositories, ...). Results from this study at Microsoft Corp. revealed an increase of 50% in the use of instant messaging compared with pre-pandemic use. Other researchers, on the other hand, focus on the quality of the coworkers' interactions in the remote workplace. Fonner and Roloff, (2012), for example, believe social interactions in the workplace are not only informational but also emotional exchange. This emotional exchange should also be taken into consideration; through increased social presence, it can enhance the affective attachment between coworkers (Fonner & Roloff, 2012; Wang & Pan, 2018). In line with this approach Wilson et al. (2008) study resulted in subjective perceptions of distance being a stronger predictor of closeness than physical distance. The team of researchers led by Wilson found in coworker identity and coworker communication core processes where feelings of being close to a distant other were developed. Frequent and close social interactions within the firm's network

stimulates trust (Tsai & Ghoshal, 1998) through shared values and informal interactions. Cooperative behavior is expected when such close, trusting relationships exist.

Coworker relations and its effect in teleworker wellbeing are subject to change as telework maturity evolves in the organization (Fonner & Roloff, 2010). For example, potential problems in wellbeing from rapid transition to intensive forms of WFH may come from the social dimension of it: lack of teamwork, lack of information exchanges or even the uncertainty the use of new information and communication technology can create on employees (Stempel & Siestrup, 2022). On the other side, long term exposure to WFH has revealed positive effects on social wellbeing derived from the ability to stay away from unwanted coworker relationships that are otherwise unavoidable, when in the office (Collins et al., 2016b). In hybrid workplace environments, where some employees are office-based and others are home-based, home workers develop strong social support relationships with other home-based employees. This has led to the belief that home and office-based staff, overtime, tend to disconnect.

In sum, organization, managerial and coworker remote social structures in the workplace are generally connected with employee wellbeing (Fonner & Roloff, 2012), although this statement is not free from contextual dependency. Still today, changes in social wellbeing as results of remote work contexts remain inconclusive (Charalampous et al., 2019). Decisions on how to promote employee's wellbeing at telework need to be based on the best available evidence to optimize worker outcomes (Oakman et al., 2020). Overall, high quality relations at work are conducive of employee's wellbeing (Wöhrmann & Ebner, 2021). In distant work environments, social support at work acts as a health protective resource (Demerouti et al., 2001) but when not effectively managed, the loss of social identity, presence or connectedness can also lead to professional isolation or loneliness.

2.2.2 Perceived proximity

Extensive literature supports the importance of work environments on employee's affective wellbeing (Oakman et al., 2020). Collegial support, management support and job designs are examples of factors influencing such work environments. Forced transition to WFH during Covid-19 pandemic situation have accentuated the importance of such factors. The unexpected change has increased the levels of uncertainty in employees regarding role expectations, performance management, workloads, organizational visibility, or re-adapting ways to *stay in the loop*. The lack of social contact places a psychological demand on teleworkers (Seinsche et al., 2022). Communication patterns have changed, with increased asynchronous exchanges in detriment of richer-media synchronic ones, or social connectedness, such as reduced network ties and focalization in closer connections (Yang et al., 2022). These changes reflect the need for optimal remote interactions using methods that are appropriate for employers and employees.

To understand how perceived proximity influences remote coworker's wellbeing, we first need to understand the concept of psychological distance and perceived proximity.

Psychological distance is the distance an individual perceives with objects, events, and people (Lim et al., 2012a). Psychological distance is both a cognitive and affective perception of distance; for example, how far or close a person is (Marlow & Dabbish, 2012). Changes in this perception is seen to influence important outcomes such support of promotional campaigns, decision making, or social behavior, to name a few. Psychological distance has implications in the easiness/difficulty for people to relate with each other or expressing different levels of interactions, for example (Troe &

Liberman, 2010). Psychological distance manipulates the mental representation an individual builds over the world he/she lives in, across different dimensions, that is: temporal distance, spatial distance, or social distance (e.g., similarities with a group) (Soderberg et al., 2015). Thus, the overall representation of an object, event or person will be different based on the perceived level of distance with that object, event, or person (Lim et al., 2012a). The theoretical grounds of this effect were first produced by Liberman & Trope (1998) who demonstrated the effect of temporal distance in mental representations. Years later, these same authors rounded off their studies with the enunciation the Construal Level Theory (CLT) of psychology (Trope & Liberman, 2010), detailing the intriguing relationship between psychological distance and mental representations (Lee, 2019).

Perceived proximity is a measure of psychological distance, a subjective experience of the relational distance between two coworkers. It finds its roots on CLT (Trope & Liberman, 2010) which posits that humans build the subjective experience using abstract mental construal of the distant other. Construal can be high level, which means it will focus more on general characteristics of the self: central values, beliefs, and self-definitions. The abstract model resulting from a high-level construal is more stable overtime. On the other hand, low-level construal focuses more on less important features of the self and tend to change fast. Thus, the use of high-level construal to build a sense of similarity, identification with the dyad, can be useful to build subjective closeness when WFH. In this line, perceived proximity framework relies on shared identity as one of the two core processes (the other being the communication process) of its theoretical framework (Robert, 2016; Wilson, 2001). The mental abstract enables individuals to transcend the time and spatial situation they are currently experiencing and integrate other social perspectives, thus breaking apart from colocation needs or face-to-face contacts.

Sense of closeness has been repeatedly referred by Perceived Proximity and psychological distance theoreticians when describing the feelings of being proximal to another individual. O’Leary et al. (2014a) for example define perceived proximity as “a cognitive and affective sense of relational closeness” (O’Leary et al. 2014: 1). Zamani and Pouloudi (2021) paraphrase this definition. Chang and Lee (2021) treat perceived proximity and perceived closeness equivalently. Lim et al. (2012: 1366-1369) alternate the use of “bring (...) people closer”, “perceive (...) being closer”, “perceive (...) to be closer” referring to reduced psychological distance.

Although nuanced characteristics are appreciated amongst these terms, for clarity and comfort of the reader, in this thesis project references to the terms perceived proximity, psychological distance, or sense of closeness will be similarly applied.

Perceptions of proximity have a cognitive and an affective component (Wilson et al., 2008). The cognitive component refers to the mental assessment of how close or distant a group member is. The affective component, on the other hand, is subject to emotions and feelings. The affective component recognizes that people’s sense of being proximal is not purely reliant on rational assessment. The authors defined perceived proximity referring to dyadic relationships within three specific boundary conditions. First, like all perceptions, perceived proximity refers to individual’s feelings. Second, the model is intended to apply to members of work-related teams working on specific complex inter-dependent tasks. Inter-dependent, shared goals required team members to reach out to one another and find ways to effectively communicate and collaborate. Third, there is an expectation from the coworkers to continue working together in the future. Long-term relationships or the expectancy to work together again in the future amplify the factors in the model, such as identity, communication, or network structure.

The concept of perceived proximity in the workplace disrupted previous belief of what proximity entailed in the work environment. Work-related proximity has traditionally been studied based on the objective, physical distance between two employees to engage in a face-to-face interaction. Conventional wisdom argues that collaboration is more easily formed between those employees being physically proximal by generating an obligation to interact face to face with one another (Allen et al., 2015). This means that even those employees working at the employer premises who do not wish to interact with their co-workers will do so forced by the dynamics in central offices. Perception of distance is brought into scholar work to help explain the mixed results on the impact of geographical distance in teams' performance (Robert, 2016; Wilson, 2001). Wilson (2001) shed light during her doctoral investigation into paradoxical combinations of physical and perceived proximity in software developments teams. Her study of cross-functional teams in a large bank institution showed how being physically proximal is not determinant to feeling subjectively proximal to one another. She identified these workers were often left out from their teams, despite being in the same building as the rest of their team members. The empirical evidence in her study revealed treasury analysts often showed introvert personalities, they were rarely seen initiating conversations with their team members and showed little interdependence. She labelled them *treasure team members*. Treasure team members illustrated the "close-but-far" paradox, representing situations at the end of the scale: high physical proximity and low perceived proximity teams. The tensions in the literature about the optimal configuration (physical or distant) to build proximity are recurrent. Irving et al. (2019) found examples of how physical proximity can fail to materialize in collaborative encounters, despite most favorable situation is created. In the study, Irving and her team observed, and interviews workers located in a collaborative building. The participants developed strategies to avoid contact in multiple ways (e.g., reinforcing group boundaries, minimizing social interactions). In other words, despite the space and organizational provocations for employees to meet and collaborate outside their close connections, employees' subjective perceptions seemed most influential to the outcomes.

Years later, Wilson, alongside Metiu and O'Leary (2008), studied paradoxical phenomenon of feeling close to coworkers in distant geographical locations and proposed a model that predicts such feelings. Coworkers can be physically located next to each other yet be felt distant. Conversely, geographically distant colleagues can feel strongly connected and proximal. Wilson referred to this situation as the *far-but-close* paradox. The model explains an individual's perception of closeness to another is the product of two core processes (communication and identification) and the individual (openness to experience and previous experience to telework) and socio-organizational (network structure and structural assurance) factors affecting them.

In the age of dispersed collaboration and continuous enhancements of communications technology, the *far-but-close* paradox can be seen as an opportunity to revisit assumptions of the impact of physical proximity in intense telework environments and rely on perceived proximity potential to increase collaboration and address complex communication dilemmas (Wilson et al., 2008). The researchers shed light into the strong sense of perceived proximity showed by *Open-Source* software development groups. They labelled these teams *Open source* in reference to open-source projects where development is often done in public collaborative manner (e.g., Moodle learning platform or Linux operating system). *Open-source groups* present high perceived proximity because of effective and frequent communication and a strong sense of identity. In this early concept, workmate communication and workmate identification were identified as the two core mediator processes influencing the feeling of perceived proximity to a distant teammate.

Perceived proximity factor model was empirically validated years later by O’Leary et al. (2014b). Building on their previous theoretical work, they empirically compared how objective and subjective distance amongst co-workers shape the quality of relationships. Perceived proximity mediates the relationship between communication frequency and quality of relationships and between identification and quality of relationships at work. The key to these positive mediation effects arose from frequent communications that “*signal and symbolize their dependability, reliability, likability and informality*” (O’Leary et al., 2014b, p. 2). These findings contradict previous scholar evidence on the effects of distance (Kiesler & Cummings, 2002); the authors evidenced that it is perceived proximity, and not physical proximity, which positively shape feelings of being close.

During a qualitative study of the perceived proximity model, Ruiller and her team (2019) corroborated the model defined by O’Leary et al. (2014) but identified some nuances that were put to validation in future investigations. On one side they call for re-foundation of management practices under remote team configurations. On the other, close, communicative managers were decisive for WFH flexibility gains to be felt by employees. Apparently, the opportunity for ambiguous and unclear roles and expectations was higher during remote communications. A fine balance between face to face and digital experiences was revealed to be most significant in building perceived proximity. Lastly, the team of researchers (Ruiller et al., 2019) reinvigorate the idea of hybrid work configurations.

The perceived proximity model explained

Although physical distance can be objectively measured, different people can perceive the same objective distance quite differently. This explains why individuals working in the same office can feel quite distant from co-located colleagues. Physical distance is the basis of study of the perceived proximity model. As briefly introduced above, the individual’s perception of proximity to another individual is mediated by the communication and identification processes as well as by certain individual and organizational (social) factors that impact the dyad relationship. We now turn into the description of the model itself.

Perceived proximity was conceptualized as “one person’s perception of how close or how far another person is” (Wilson et al., 2008, p. 1). Perceived proximity is benchmarked in the open-source software development projects. Linux, for example was created crowdsourced from hundreds of developers working from over 30 countries (Tuomi, 2004). Although they may never physically meet, Linux developers felt closer to each other than with other co-located colleagues (Wilson et al., 2001). The perceived proximity construct is dyadic and asymmetric one. It refers to one’s perception of a teammate rather than an aggregated view of the team. The model is applicable to teams of workers performing complex, interdependent tasks. Such teams are expected to share goals and be in need to communicate frequently. Lastly, the authors note that the model is intended to apply for longer-term interactions; very brief interactions with no expectations of working together again are outside of the model. The authors also quote the prospect of working together in the future may amplify the mediating factors of their model. On the other hand, once a team discovers they share a sense of building to a social category (Ashforth & Mael, 1989), common ground is established from which they can work (Ruiller et al., 2019)

The perceived proximity construct is composed of the following processes:

- **Communication process:** the communication process influences perceived proximity by reducing uncertainty about the other's context. First, the frequency of communication can mitigate the "out-of-sight-out-of-mind" effect in distant work relationships. Second, the depth of the communication and the level of substance reduce the uncertainty about the other's context. The envisioning of this context may build a sense of closeness. Lastly, higher levels of interactivity during the communication will reduce uncertainty about each other and prevent feelings of isolation from appearing (Wilson et al., 2008). During their empirical research, O'Leary et al. (2014b) broadly tested communication frequency covering a whole array of media (from traditional telephone, e-mail to contemporary instant messaging or videoconferencing) but they failed to test the level of substance and interactivity in the communication. Fonner & Roloff (2012) also based their assumptions on the frequency of communications to study the impact of connectivity in building sense of social presence (Short et al., 1976). The results from their study revealed that, apart from email, the rest of communication media use had a positive relation with social presence for high intensity teleworkers. In sum, frequent, deep, and interactive communications reduce the level of uncertainty about the other's context and prevent feelings of isolation from arising (Kurland & Egan, 1999).
- **Identification process:** Identification process refers to the building of a sense of belonging to a social category (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). Here again, the identification reduces uncertainty. It sets a common ground for the relationship to build upon and generates positive attributions when data is not available. O'Leary et al. (2014b) measured shared identity with their colleagues based on age, gender, commitment to work and personal values similarities. Shared identity was found to be more proximal to relationship quality than communication frequency.

Fonner & Roloff (2012) suggest identification process should not be considered separate from the communication process. They reasoned there is an indirect relationship between communication and sense of membership. The reason behind this argument is the belief that organizational identification is built from both the cognitive component derived from being a member of an organization and the affective component related with the rewards employees' experience from being part of that organization. In other words, the quality of communication can impact the level of rewards perceived by being a member. When testing the effect of remote communications in regular telework, the pair of researchers found it too much connectivity negatively impacted the employees' ability to focus and complete the tasks, thus increasing the level of stress. This situation resulted in reduced perception of the rewards experienced by being a member of the company. Fonner and Roloff (2012) revealed that organizational identification can be negatively influenced by stress from media communication interruptions.

The model shows how communication and identification are core, interrelated processes to build a sense of closeness. The model also highlights the existence of individual and organizational factors (e.g., openness to experience, density of networking structures) to be considered when examining psychological distance. Individual factors have been marginally studied in the research of dispersed teams (Ruiller et al., 2019). Autonomy has been identified as a core competence to select individuals subject to telework; individuals with autonomy will be more willing to invest in communication and

identification processes that may return in stronger feelings of perceived proximity (Wilson et al., 2008). In contemporary times, the advent of large scale telework adoption reduces the applicability of such selection practices; this place additional challenges to practitioners and researchers to open new avenues to increase perceived proximity within a wider variety of individual traits found in each firm's employee community.

Extant empirical research has focused largely on the influence of communication frequency on perceived proximity, forgetting about the depth and interactivity labels out of the analysis. The analysis of varied levels of richness in interactions is crucial in the study of telework relationships; as face-to-face interactions are reduced (Golden, 2006). This segmented approach, following Wilson et al. (2008) model, is expected to draw a much richer understanding of the communication process effect in perceived proximity. The emphasis is again shifted to the use of information systems as “*pipes*” to convey shared meaning and symbolic value (O’Leary et al., 2014b). The level of substance and interactivity are interesting measures in electronic communications. The ability to engage the counterparts for a rich electronic interaction requires humanized ICT-based communications. Creative use of communication technologies (through conference calls, videoconferencing, and web-enabled meetings, to name a few) can substitute face-to-face interaction (Beauregard et al., 2019a); this may mean no limits can be found to perceived proximity to be developed in telework environments.

Perceived proximity is a multivariate theoretical contribution to organizational studies: it broadens the scholar work of proximity theory building by including the subjective experience of it; it proposed a reconciling avenue to conflicting findings regarding the effects of distant interpersonal encounters; it can have a profound effect on the effectiveness of remote teams (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). Probably, the most striking finding is the fact that objective distance had no effect on relationship quality. These findings are turnkey to telework research. Perceived proximity is a strong construct to shape outcomes in today's work environments as it “outweighs objective proximity” (O’Leary et al., 2014b, p. 16).

Perceived proximity in telework contexts

In prevalence of telework contexts, there is a growing interest amongst scholars and practitioners to understand which management practices help maintain adequate levels of psychological proximity while working remotely (Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021). Telework causes coworkers to remain physically distant for periods of time but, at the same time, provides for coordination to be delivered through advanced technologies. Past research has shown that home-based employees tend to build stronger bonding with other home-based employees, while gaining distance with their office-based coworkers (Collins et al., 2016b). Employees transitioning to telework arrangements for the first time are often concerned with the social isolation they may experience WFH (Maruyama & Tietze, 2012). The physical separation of work-related interactions is also a source of complexity for managers as it breaks a certain harmony of place, time, and interaction. It fundamentally changes the management mode (Ruiller et al., 2019), thus being especially difficult for those companies to successfully transition from office-based environments. Former telework research has shed light on the importance of superior attitude towards telework and the adoption subjective proximity practices for it to be successful (Lautsch & Kossek, 2011).

The psychological distance perspective is an integral part of the design of effective ICT-based work interactions (Marlow & Dabbish, 2014). The advancements on technology in which telework is based, providing visual cues of body language or a wide array of communication tools and channels raises the question as to whether remote communication and shared identity for intense teleworkers can create feelings of proximity as strong as for those employees sharing a location (O’Leary et al., 2014b). Research on telework often challenges the assumptions regarding the value of frequent face-to-face interactions in outcomes such as performance, quality of relations or work-related satisfaction. Current increase in the use of rich-media technologies (such as videoconference, web meeting conference, ...) is likely to increase closeness in remote work. Remote ICT provides means for telework to exist, it provides a spatial link between the employee and the central office. In such arrange of channels, the range of informational cues teleworkers have to interpret has radically changed (Burgoon et al., 2002; Golden & Veiga, 2008). But technology is only the tool, the key to success relies on how individuals respond to it (Adamovic, 2022). Increased use of technology in the workplace, and the new developments in available ICT tooling (e.g., collaborative tools, enterprise social networks, ...) imply changes for employees in terms of their working practices, behaviors, and skills (Grant et al., 2019) .

The research model of this dissertation project, following Wilson et al. (2008), proposes a segmented approach into three potential predictors of perceived proximity in telework contexts (workmate communication, workmate identity, and the use of ESNs). This approach is expected to draw a much richer understanding of the perceived proximity predictors in telework contexts. To better understand these antecedents, the remaining of the section will further discuss them individually.

Antecedents of Perceived proximity in telework – Communication

It is often recognized that effective electronic communication is key to teleworker success (Shockley et al., 2021); communication quantity and quality has been found determinant of employee performance and wellbeing. In terms of building relatedness and support, as people interact frequently with each other they can build a sense of closeness (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). Communication variables are not commonly found in remote work research yet extant research provides indication of the influential role it may play. For example, Derks and Bakker (2010) applied a Job-Demands-Resource approach to study e-mail communication frequency as an antecedent of wellbeing during remote work. Results from their study propose communication frequency produces different effects at different levels. E-mail use was found generally beneficial at low and medium levels, acting as a job resource when WFH, whereas, at high levels, it may reduce its resourcefulness, shifting to function as a demand, thereby positively relating to burnout. These findings are in line with those from their contemporary *connectivity paradox* (Leonardi et al., 2010).

The objective of communication is to reduce uncertainty; in this sense Media Richness Theory (Daft & Lengel, 1986) studies the inherent characteristic of the medium used and advises that different choices of media used impact the level of informational exchange. Examples of these characteristics can be found in feedback response times, number of cues or language variety (Yoo & Alavi, 2001). The theory of media richness is grounded on the authors’ assumption that organizations produce more information than can be consumed by its members. Thus, assessing the fixed characteristics of each media and ranking the richness it provides, can be a powerful tool to select the most appropriate media for each situation. Daft and Lengel (1986) defined information richness “*as the ability of information*

to change understanding within a time interval” (Daft & Lengel, 1986, p. 560). The reasons for richness include the number of cues, number of channels used, medium’s capacity for immediate feedback, personalization, and language variety. Following richness rank, media is ranked as follows (in ascending order): 1) number documents, such as reports; 2) impersonal documents, such as memos; 3) personal documents, such as emails; 4) telephone; 5) face-to-face communications.

Following this hierarchy of richness, the choice of communication channel can be optimized to the needs of the situation. For example, coordination activities between independent teams will rely on rich media to resolve differences and provide limited amount of information, rather than focus on extensive exchange of not-relevant data across teams. Face-to-face communications are most preferred media used when in need to deal with high levels uncertainty or when a rapid cycle of clarification is needed. High rich media is not always best placed; low rich media is recommended to exchange well understood messages and standard data. Analyzing the level of richness in communication events is crucial in the study of telework relationships; as face-to-face interactions are reduced (Golden, 2006). Nowadays, the list of available communication media is much more extensive than before. For example, electronic repositories support knowledge sharing; instant messaging, social media networks, videoconferencing, or online wikis, to name a few, provide communication and easiness of collaboration. The optimal communication profile for perceived proximity with a distant coworker is frequent, deep, and interactive communication (Wilson et al., 2008). For all the above, it seems reasonable to think successful telework communications will come from strategic choice to use organizational ICTs that best manage psychological distance in each instance (Robert, 2016).

Complementary to media richness approach, other theoretical lenses are often used by remote communication researchers. Media Synchronicity theory (Dennis et al., 2008), for example, distinguishes the effect that synchronous and asynchronous communications can have in communication quality. Synchronous communications occur when two-way interactions are held at the same time, such as instant messaging or online meetings. Synchronous channels are often richer media hence best placed to process rich information. Synchronism allows for immediate feedback, validation of interpretation; in sum, understanding and agreement can be easily achieved (Daft & Lengel, 1986). Asynchronous communications, on the other hand, involve interactions occurring at different times, such is the case of email, enterprise social networks, blogs, or wikis, to name a few.

Asynchronous channels are also an effective choice when focus is recommended to build a response. Asynchronous communications are known to increase the level of equality and satisfaction of the elaborated response (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). Although often associated with less rich media, asynchronous communications provide value in reducing uncertainty levels as larger amounts of data can be exchanged; answers to more specific questions can be obtained. Also, asynchronous communication plays an important role in ensuring some of the benefits of telework are achieved, such as work-life balance, boundary management and stress from interruptions (Boell et al., 2016; Fonner & Roloff, 2012; Leonardi et al., 2010). In sum, the depending on the contextual settings, segmented use of electronic communication attributes can be brought into play to effectively manage the perception of distance (O’Leary et al., 2014b).

Antecedents of Perceived proximity in telework – Coworker identity

Identity refers to mutual understanding, common knowledge. Feeling of holding a shared identity with other individual or the group is a process of self-categorization (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). The feelings of similarities and self-categorization to are associated with feelings of being close to the distant other (Wilson et al., 2008). Shared identification has multiple benefits within the organizations. For once, it supports subjective distance WFH. Also, identity researchers reflect on the fact that people uniformly make positive evaluations of the group they are members of. This identification leads to greater commitment, it directs behaviors in line with the group's standard, and there appears to be less desire to leave the group (Stets & Burke, 2005). In telework environments, shared identity with a fellow worker can help overcome feelings of isolation (Fay & Kline, 2012). The advancements of communication technology, increasingly its ability to include symbolic meaning can clearly benefit its organizational users. For example, at a role level it can automatically grants access to information based on the user profile; at a personal level grouping can be segmented within or across age, country of origin, tenure in the company, to name a few. At a social level it also brings a new world of possibilities for telework organizations adopting the use of social networking sites (e.g., finding new coworkers with whom one shares similarities, visibility of community memberships, ...) (Stets & Burke, 2005; van Zoonen et al., 2021b).

To understand how people convey a sense of proximity with their colleagues, researchers refer to the quantitative and the qualitative sense of communication (O'Leary et al., 2014b). A combination of frequency and shared identity between teleworkers communication is high in symbolic meaning, thus enabling finding similarities with the coworker. Shared identity may help reduce distance in remote work environments by increasing feeling of cohesion (Marlow & Dabbish, 2014). From a theoretical perspective, remote coworkers who have found a shared identity are more inclined to support each other (van Dick et al., 2018). Identity theoreticians stress the idea that shared identity needs to be maintained (Stets & Burke, 2005). In other words, the process of self-categorization needs to be cultivated over time. In this sense, Wilson et al. (2008) propose that communication frequency and shared identity interact in a recurrent manner, with the potential to mutually reinforce each other, and, in turn, promote perceived proximity.

Antecedents of Perceived proximity in telework – Use of Enterprise Social Networks

The employees working in large organizations in intense telework environments are confronted with difficulties to reach out for support as their co-workers become less visible and less accessible. One could think effectiveness can be achieved by simply throwing loads of information to employees for them to pick and choose which pieces are needed. This option is probably not only the least cost-effective but probably it also causes further isolation and loss of productivity. Poor social interaction in remote telework is derived from lack of personal interaction and informal relation (Cooper & Kurland, 2002). Organizations are no friends of employee isolation as it negatively impacts with loss of work effort and employee engagement (Davis & Cates, 2013). Researchers are suggesting Human Resource practitioners to adapt to new dynamics of work and make conscious efforts to maintain such feelings of belongingness. Compared with 20 years ago, technology today allows for a totally different form of virtual communication; it provides for means of higher social presence and higher influence of communication into how people behave. ESNs, for example, are communication platforms designed to connect users by creating information profiles, suggesting other coworkers to

create their own profile, and sending out emails or instant messages between each other (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Providing means for informal socialization to occur in the remote work context is found critical to effectively transition to telework, especially in high-intensity telework arrangements (Fay & Kline, 2012).

Little is yet known about the informal communications between coworkers while in high intensity telework, but the expectation is high for these to develop relationships and create a basis for positive work attitudes (Durakovic et al., 2023). Users of ESNs can participate and collaborate with disperse others, despite the physical distance between them (Lim et al., 2012b). ESNs facilitate the formation of a shared experience between the participants of the social interaction. Users can communicate and collaborate better with coworkers by perceiving one another being part of the same space and time. Sharing video or photo content is also a powerful method to increase social presence. Informal interactions through ESNs could be used to clarify perceptions of their beliefs or overall shared identity with coworkers (Fay & Kline, 2012).

Van Zoonen et al. (2021a) provide novel evidence on the effects of ESNs on perceived proximity. The single case study tested whether the characteristics of ESNs influenced perceived proximity or vice versa. Van Zoonen and his team examined the transparency of the messages being posted in the network as well as the transparency of which users were connected to who within the organization, as influential characteristics of ESNs. At the time of the study, six months had passed since the rollout of the firm-wide social network site. The analysis resulted in causal priority of perceived proximity over ESN characteristics, meaning that perceived proximity with a coworker encourages the dyad to participate in ESN posting.

Contemporary research is opening new debates to deepen the understanding of technology-mediated communications and ways of working. The findings will be applicable not only to those working remotely but to those working at the employer's premises or in any form of hybrid state as almost all individual employees and teams are likely to employ technology to coordinate tasks and accomplish work (Liu et al., 2022a; Niebuhr et al., 2022).

2.2.3 Employee Voice

There is a dark side to working from the comfort of our homes. Teleworkers often feel isolated, loose visibility of the organization and may feel disengaged with the company project (Davis and Cates, 2013). Likewise, not been seen or heard may result in not being fairly judged during performance reviews or even considered for future projects or open positions (Sewell & Taskin, 2015). Overtime, a lack of trust between adopters and non-adopters can be developed (Athanasiadou and Theriou, 2021). Teleworkers have long revealed their fear of being devaluated as results of their telework condition (Mann & Holdsworth, 2003); or having a negative effect in their career as results of the lower visibility. This effect has been known in the literature as *flexibility stigma* (Maruyama & Tietze, 2012). Flexible workers can be seen as less devoted to work compared with their office-based colleagues, thus impacting in opportunities for professional development and salary growth (Golden & Eddleston, 2020). Hence, to cope with the negative impact of telework in social structures (Yang et al., 2022) teleworkers need to purportedly take action to gain visibility back. Having ways to express

their voice directly (e.g., via enterprise social media) or indirectly (e.g., via Unions or working councils' online channels) will provide means for teleworkers to become visible again.

About Employee Voice

Hirschman (1970) is known to develop the first formal theory on employee voice. In his book “*Exit, Voice, and Loyalty*” he posits voice as an alternative to exit. He defines employee voice as individual or collective actions of communication seeking change. Hirschman posits loyalty is a necessary resource to neutralize dissatisfied employees from prospecting (Martin et al., 2015b).

Prior to Hirschman’s formal theory work, employee voice has long been studied for over 200 years, since its appearance in Adam Smith’s *Wealth of Nations* (Kaufman, 2013). In those very early days, Smith acknowledges the little effect employee verbal communication normally has on the employer side unless “animated clamor” is raised. The economist Karl Marx also uses the voice term. He intensifies the divergence of interest employer-employee and adds the idea that employer and employee are in a constant bargaining process whereby employees exercise labor power as a bargaining chip.

Most literature on employee voice touches base with psychological research (Hirschman, 1970). Different researchers have landed the concept of voice in different theoretical backgrounds. Some examples of this are Freeman & Medoff (1985) work on the impact of collective voice in organizational outcomes; the inclusion of employee voice in the Human Resource Management literature by Dundon et al. (2004); the model to explain the nature of social media communications developed by Martin et al. (2015), or the work of Yee et al. (2021) suggesting managers to lean on social media usage to foster employee participation in solution design activities.

According to Dundon et al. (2004), there are two motives for establishing voice systems: (1) to eliminate employee dissatisfaction and (2) to capture suggestions to improve business performance. Employee voice is often considered the expression of a challenge to improve the overall situation (Yang & Lin, 2022). Researchers often distinguish employee voice attending to the level of formality withheld in the communication process. According to Mowbray et al. (2015) review of the concept of voice, there is a consensus in the definition of formal and informal voice. Formal voice is defined as voice using prearranged structures (surveys, meetings, consultative committees, work council, intranet). Informal voice refers to the ideas expressed outside a structured process (informal discussions, email, grapevine, ...). At its simplest definition, employee voice describes how employees attempt to influence on organizational affairs impacting their work (Holland et al., 2016).

Despite the potential benefits, past research provides evidence that employees often choose not to express their voice and remain silent (Hao et al., 2022). Such behavior has been labeled as *organizational or employee silence*. Employee’s unwillingness to speak up has been associated with many individual and organizational outcomes (e.g., innovation, stress, depression, lower commitment, and job satisfaction) (Brinsfield, 2013). Employers often have more positive perceptions of workplace climate than employees (Wilkinson et al., 2018); these segmented views represent an added complexity for manager and workers to engage together (Becker & Huselid, 2006). Negativity in employment relations hinder employee satisfaction and wellbeing at work, causing an undesired negative impact on business (Wilkinson et al., 2018).

There is usually a constructive intention behind the expression of voice, rather than merely criticize. Ge (2020) posits this is so because voice behavior finds antecedents in psychological safety. In other words, employees will express their voice when they feel there is no negative consequence from doing so, whereas when they do not feel free, they will simply remain silent. In any case, the expression of voice consumes employee resources (e.g., time and effort to build an argument, risk of being exposed, ...). Effective promotion of voice brings benefit to both employers and employees. Employees are known for being a source of creativity, change and innovations in the organizations; failing to encourage voice expression can cause organizations to lose that potential (Huang et al., 2005). Organizations that have established voice mechanisms benefit from employee engagement, wellbeing, and increased performance, through enhanced decision making (Abdulgaliimov et al., 2020). For employees, it results in work satisfaction and improved mental health (Dundon et al., 2004).

This thesis will distinctively examine the effect of direct and indirect voice (also known as collective voice) expression of telework- related topics in employees wellbeing while WFH. The remainder of this subsection will introduce each of these concepts.

Direct voice refers to the direct communication of employee's suggestion, ideas, concerns to management. Through the direct expression of their voice employees attempt to influence the organizational views about topics that directly impact their work lives (Holland et al., 2011). Human Resource Management research has typically found in direct voice an opportunity to help improve organizational processes (Nechanska et al., 2020). Direct voice has also been studied from an opposite front: the absence of it, silence (Huang et al., 2005). This stream of debate sheds light into the environmental factors inhibiting the decision to speak up. A culture of silence can occur at organizational level. Lack of employee voice may hinder the organizations' ability to change and adapt to rapid changing market environments. Some researchers argue that "*remaining silent can be an employee's strategy to influence the decisions of supervisors*" (Huang et al., 2005, p. 461). Informal managerial behaviors, as simple as ignoring opinions, reject negative feedback or becoming annoyed with unwanted commentary can build a collective conclusion that speaking up is not welcome or could even be risky. Employees will be more inclined to speak up in open and supportive environments (Yang & Lin, 2022).

Over time, employee voice has evolved from a formal indirect system to an informal and more direct system (Estell et al., 2021). The proliferation of social media channels in employees' personal lives has caught the eyes of employers who have seen the potential to connect and engage with employees in remote environments. The choice of communication channels used to express voice will influence management in different ways (Boxall & Macky, 2014). With the advent of telework, organizations are turning to ESNs to foster direct participation and dialogue (Yee et al., 2021). The hard characteristics of ESNs (e.g., immediacy and visibility of communications) are an opportunity to be considered for exploitation. ESNs are known to promote peer-to-peer engagement (Abdulgaliimov et al., 2020); yet for it to be effective, it requires the target audience to respond to it. Social network researchers advise of the difficulties for ESNs to produce the expected outcomes. Company social networks have been used as channels for self-promotion or employee surveillance (Laumer et al., 2017). When this is the case, the acceptance of the tool (ESN) may be in danger, which may result in not sufficient use of it. It may also deteriorate the quality of the exchanges posted in the social network, as it turns into a space where authenticity is lost.

Forms of *indirect voice* (e.g., through Union or worker councils) also represents an important factor in the implementation of successful work practices. Unions are potential agents of change (Barnes et al., 2019; della Torre, 2019). Unions and management can collaboratively work towards the implementation of a new practice (e.g., telework). When Unions are involved in the solution of problems or negotiations of changing working conditions the effect is expected to have a formal consequence in the employment relation. This becomes crucial in disruptive situations like large scale transition to telework environments where aspects of working conditions such as home office accommodation, work time tracking, task assignment and completion traceability, safety at home office, or privacy protection are to be revisited.

Trade Unions have long been recognized as great channels for the expression of common concerns in the workplace (Barnes et al., 2019). Collective voice mechanisms are relevant to the firm's performance, which can directly impact the productivity of its workforce (della Torre, 2019; Kim et al., 2010). Still, proliferation of Unions has substantively declined in the last decades. Thus, research on the impact of collective voice in modern workplace remains scarce and has been simplistically instrumentalized on the existence of Union or Unionization rate (Wilkinson et al., 2018). Unfortunately, the simple presence of a Union is not an indicator of its ability to influence the organization; it is only when indirect mechanisms can have a voice and get involved with management that positive effects can be expected from this negotiation (della Torre, 2019). Uribebarria et al. (2021) recently studied different forms of employee participation in management decision making. The results from their study confirmed a direct relationship between voice and employee wellbeing; indirect voice was perceived by participants as the most real form of participation.

Following this introduction of the concept of employee voice, the following subsection will deepen in the scenario WFH represents for voice expression mechanisms.

Expressing one's voice under telework arrangements.

Voice mechanisms lead employees to feel more positive attitudes towards decisions made by his/her manager. Managers can suggest employees to express their direct voice as alternative to collective voice (e.g., Union) mechanisms. Employee satisfaction can increase for as high as 20% above average when some form of formal voice mechanism is in place (Wilkinson et al., 2023). Managers can also facilitate for employees to engage in a dialogue with other colleagues, share information and views and, on some occasions, participate in decision making. Employees who express their voice may feel more valued and respected (Burriss et al., 2013).

Contemporary telework researchers find in employee voice a source of today's organizational effectiveness (Liu et al., 2021). Let's explain why. Firstly, the uncertainty behind the outcomes of telework (van der Lippe & Lippényi, 2019). It may be in the employer's interest to maintain open channels of communication with employees during transition to telework. For example, gaining early access to difficulties encountered while adapting to WFH are a valuable source of information during telework implementation. Secondly, the current increased share of teleworkers points to the importance of transition to new regulated working conditions that consider the wellbeing of teleworkers (Wöhrmann & Ebner, 2021). In the absence of telework regulation or poorly managed telework environments, excessive control, or job insecurities may arise, opening the floor for telework

negative consequences (e.g., isolation, detachment from work, loss of collaboration, ...) (Kaplan et al., 2018). In the advent of such risky situation, it seems appropriate for employers to find ways to effectively engage in constructive conversations about telework-specific adoption topics.

Unions and worker's representatives have a role to play in the process of bargaining the new working conditions. In Europe, telework regulation is delegated by the European Commission to the European social partners and their country organizations to arrange autonomous framework agreements (Larsen & Andersen, 2007). In case of telework adoption, employers are obliged to provide written form of remote work agreement, following 91/553 directive. In Spain, the Royal Decree-Law 28/2020 regulate remote work for private employees and Royal Decree-Law 29/2020 does so for public employees. The country regulatory body leaves several provisions undetermined but provides for them to be arranged in case by case. It's in these case-by-case negotiations that telework voice expression becomes crucial. In accordance with the minimum legal requirements of the remote work agreement, the following issues need to be addressed by employers: allow for flexible working time, on-site working hours, a system to cover the expenses derived from remote working, the duration of the agreement and the conditions for reversibility.

Collective efforts to design such remote work normative can be an incentive for individual employees to engage in collective voice. But the new remote work scenarios are adding complexity for Trade Unions to remain connected and socially present in the eyes of their members and the rest of the company's workforce. On the one hand, Trade Unions are being placed in a central position to articulate effective telework regulations in organizations; on the other, they face the challenges of physical disconnect with employees as the rise of telework prevalence impacts all equally. In this context, trade Unions must turn to electronic forms of communications (e.g., social media, online bulletin board, ...) to embrace the opportunity these tools provide to break through such difficulties (Barnes et al., 2019). From an indirect voice perspective, social media has the potential to serve as a social networking tool where Trade Unions can engage with members and followers regarding telework-adoption specific topics. Social media allows the creation and exchange of user generated content (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010) that can result in successful avenues for Unions/ worker representatives to attract users to their informational resources and/or foster engagement with their online activities.

From a direct voice perspective, ESNs are also a suitable tool where conversations can arise without the need for management intervention (Moqbel et al., 2013). Research on voice expression on social media refers to two types of social media: internal social media expressed over ICTs provided by the employer (e.g., ESNs, company blogs) and public social media expressed over open, free of charge platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, ... (Lam, 2016). Given its popularity, companies have started to use social media platforms internally to encourage collaboration and communication (Martin et al., 2015b). Online blogs, social networking sites, media sharing sites, among others, have become daily consumable resources for many organizations (Martin et al. 2015). The immediacy of the message exchanges through these tools enables people responding and reacting to issues as they emerge (Holland et al., 2016). One could think this immediacy could somehow replace some face-to-face encounters in the office building. These technologies are also characterized by having high communication visibility (van Zoonen et al., 2021a). This visibility refers to transparency of the messages which are visible to anyone connected to the site. Together with the immediacy, this communication visibility, increases the chances of being seen/read. Lastly, ESNs provide for high translucence of the users' networks. In other words, the openness of these tools enables a user to ascertain who is the other person connected with, provided the employer has configured access to this

feature. For these, among other reasons, social networking sites (e.g., ESNs) are seen to foster employee participation (Yee et al., 2021). In this sense, company-wide social sites could take a central stage in the evolution of new forms of employee voice.

Expressing one's voice in the employer's social network is an example of direct voice WFH. Regardless of the potential benefits of ESN usage. Open social media (e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter, ...) provide access to the interactive capabilities the online world provides, with users being able engage, like/dislike content, and share their own content (Houghton & Hodder, 2021). The expression of telework-related opinion over social media (internal and public) is associated with organizational identification as it allows employees the ability to express views, share knowledge about work and engage in relationships with other professionals (van Zoonen et al., 2014). These theoretical benefits will never materialize if employees do not perceive them equally helpful and of value (Yee et al., 2021). Yee and his team found lack of motivation from ESN users to collaborate unless a positive impact on their reputation was expected. Hence, there is a managerial case to encourage the adoption of social media platforms as ways to express their voice.

Teleworkers can also indirectly voice their suggestions/opinions participating in collective voice mechanisms (e.g., Unions social media, Unions online activities, electronic billboard, ...). Unions have also shifted to new forms of online communications, especially in the second half of the twentieth century, as face-to-face forms of communication were becoming more and more difficult to sustain (Thorntwaite et al., 2018). Although mass meetings remained the predominant way for Unions to disseminate and make decisions, the role of Union journals or additional publications was becoming unclear. Early experimentation of alternative ways of communication, such as video, audiovisuals, or telex, started during this time. Unions see in social media an opportunity to reconfigure the engagement with their members, to enhance Union democracy and, overall, member voice (Barnes et al., 2019). Unions had previously experienced a decline in representation in favor of non-Union and more direct two-way communications (Holland et al., 2016). Unions are increasingly active in social networking platforms such as blogs, Facebook, twitter, telegram. These forms of Union social media are increasingly seen as new tools that can support Union transformation through revitalization of Union democracy. Union members to participate and express their voice. Previous studies on Union social media usage reveal that users often refer to Union social media channels to gain information about their rights, follow Union campaigns, or industry specific issues. Most active engagement in Union social media is seen in online campaign participation, hitting "like" in the Union social media page, and seeking information about a specific campaign (Thorntwaite et al., 2018). In sum, trade Unions adoption of social media to communicate with their members is a reality, yet the effectiveness of the Union communication is what is crucial for employee participation and engagement.

In section 2.2 we have presented the theories behind the key variables in our research model. To summarize the key takeaways from the undertaken literature review, the following statements are presented (1) Close, supportive relationships are of relevance to build psychological wellbeing in intense telework environments; (2) Workmate communication and workmate identification are core antecedents of perceived proximity; with higher significance of identity over communication frequency; (3) Previous causal relations have been found between Enterprise Social Network usage and perceived proximity; (4) The use of online voice mechanisms (e.g., social media) in telework arises as relevant for employees. They can either directly express their voice or connect with workers representative with regards to telework-specific topics.

Based on the above, the next section presents the formulation of hypotheses that will be statistically tested.

2.3 Hypotheses

In this section we will present the research predictions derived from our research questions. We will formulate six hypotheses which will provide the basis for the research design and discussion of the results. The hypotheses will be clear and concise, backed by extant literature. An explanation of the rationale of the hypotheses will be given in each case.

The social perspective of telework stresses the importance of work relationships when face-to-face encounters are interrupted (Becker et al., 2022). The risk of isolation is indisputable when the desire for social connection is not met (Marshall et al., 2007). When isolated, teleworkers require a greater expenditure of emotional and cognitive resources to perform work. Thus, social connectedness in today's digitalized workplace represents a valuable job resource in telework (Wong et al. 2022). To mitigate this situation, organizations have turned to ESN structures to foster dialogue and participation (Estell et al., 2021). They benefit from easy-to-use technology which can support internal communication, peer to peer interaction and collaboration. The adoption of these platforms in work-related environments is facilitated by the fact that such technologies are often consolidated in the teleworker's routines in his/her personal life (Neirotti et al., 2017).

Compared with the use of formal tools such as Customer Relationship Management, ESNs offer a more effective way to strengthen social ties amongst employees (Schneckenberg, 2009). Also, in contrast with most organizational ICTs, ESNs subscription choices are often self-defined, hence users control their relationship building activities, based on self-interests (Cohen & Richards, 2015). Through ESNs remote organizations have found new ways of keeping in touch and building relationships with colleagues. As employees increasingly work remotely, social media can increase contact between them.

Teleworkers may find in ESNs a platform to cope with situations related with telework conditions such as remote work best-practices, work intensification or work flexibility. The informal interactions held in social networking sites facilitates the personal connection between users (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020). Connecting with coworkers with similar needs or interests enriches the information and emotional exchanges (Wang & Pan, 2018). Social media technology is thus a valuable complementary form of communication in the remote workplace (Barnes et al. 2019). The use of internal social media improves the overall experience of WFH (Holland et al., 2016). Dispersed team members with similar interests, skills, values can voluntarily share experience and knowledge. Participation in communities of practice, for example, enhances coworker collaborations and allow employees to make their own decisions about who they connect and what information they exchange, thanks a much richer contextual environment (Schneckenberg, 2009). Employees engage voluntarily in valued conversations with coworkers about a wide arrange of topics. In turn, ESNs can create the space where the desire to connect is satiated (CIPD, 2013), where employees can *stay in the loop*. Some users find incremental gains in ESN usage, for example, by the reputational gain from being seen sharing knowledge (Yee et al., 2021).

Additionally, teleworkers can turn to ESNs to discover who is saying what (also known as *communication visibility*) in the organization, but also who is connected to who (also known as *network translucence*) (Van Zoonen et al. 2021). These two characteristics of ESNs, that is communication visibility and network translucence, are mostly valuable to mitigate the risk of isolation WFH. ESNs allow coworkers to become authors and publisher at the same time; it is intended to promote peer to peer interaction (Neirotti et al., 2017). ESNs smooth remote communications when WFH (van Zoonen et al., 2014). Immediacy of online social platforms enriches the communication flow in the workplace (Newman et al. 2019). Thus, teleworkers may create an online identity made visible to peers and the wider organization. Employees can voluntarily choose groups to subscribe to and customize features to accommodate to each employee's preferences. They engage rapidly in simultaneous conversations with coworkers, in multiple rich ways: photo postings, video postings, text emoticons and smiley faces (Bhatti et al., 2020). The contextual media is shared across the organization, thus creating social presence. Social presence reduces perceived distance (Fonner & Roloff, 2012).

Teleworkers may find in ESNs new ways to maintain informational and emotional proximity with remote, similar-minded employees (Cohen & Richards, 2015), both formally and informally (CIPD, 2013). ESN technology is designed applying knowledge from psychological distance (Marlow & Dabbish, 2014; van Zoonen et al., 2014). For example, sharing photos or videos increases the opportunities for these similarities to be found, reducing, in turn, psychological distance (van Zoonen et al. 2016). Frequent and close social interaction in the workplace stimulates trust within the members of the organization (Tsai & Ghoshal, 1998). Employee self-organizing groups are also known to engage in the exchange of relevant work information, humor, discussing difficulties with cases at work or generally offering coworkers emotional support (Cohen & Richards, 2015). Thus, the characteristics of ESNs seem appropriate to improve workmate identity in remote work. Recalling (O'Leary et al. (2014b), identity building was most relevant for perceived proximity to develop in coworker relationships. Teleworkers can find in ESN a new way to increase contact relations with other teleworkers (Newman et al., 2019), which, in turn, increases affective wellbeing (Fonner & Roloff, 2012). Thus, the following hypothesis is offered:

H1: The use of Enterprise Social Network WFH positively influences perceived proximity

Teleworkers may start feeling isolated when they perceive they are cut off from regular communications (Beauregard et al., 2019a). Workplace isolation is "a state of mind that one is out of touch with others in the workplace" (Golden et al., 2008: 1412). When face to face is no longer the preferred mode of communication electronic communications help overcome this feeling, recreating a sense of closeness between fellow workers (Leonardi et al., 2010). In this sense, advanced synchronic technologies (such as video calls, live chats) may have taken the spotlight in telework communications, due to their ability to bring clarity and shared meaning to the remote communications (Dennis et al., 2008). The use of video conference, for example, has been declared as of value to teleworkers. The available visible cues help understanding when spoken language was a second language, for example, building rapport (Olson & Olson, 2000).

Today, teleworkers are exposed to a varied range of remote tools such as email, blogs, intranet sites, online meetings, to name a few. This adds complexity to social relations WFH. All available information to interpret work-related context cannot be processed (Burgoon et al., 2002). Different theories point to different preferred channels, according to specific situations. For example, media

dependent theories note relationship quality is best achieved through the highest number of available cues (e.g., face-to-face, video calls, ...) (Daft & Lengel, 1986). Some channels have even been vetoed for certain activities, such as email to build rapport amongst coworkers (Yoo & Alavi, 2001). Social Presence (Short et al. 1976) is preferably built through synchronous channels (such as online calls). Simple comparison amongst communication format is not enough. Teleworkers are forced to self-manage who to relate with, when and through which channel to perform their daily jobs. At times, teleworkers may consider some available cues peripheral or distracting and will ignore them (Fonner & Roloff, 2012). During Covid-19 forced telework for example, lower media channels experienced a sharp increase in use (e.g., instant messaging, email), in detriment of other forms of communication (e.g., video calls) (Yang et al., 2022).

The myriad of options for electronic communications can be designed to manage perceived distance in remote work environments. Teleworkers will choose the use of IT systems that help them overcome physical distance in the workplace to increase cooperation and collaboration (Robert, 2016). The degree of interaction, synchronicity in each exchange will affect outcomes of psychological distance (Burgoon et al., 2002). Rather than limiting the use of high-media synchronic media and channels, dynamic combinations of channels can be used to ensure the appropriate connectivity is always provided. For example, concentrating topic-specific communications in knowledge repositories, instead of directly submitting to team members, this way the knowledge repository becomes the single point of reference and email inbound is reduced. Overtime, teleworker learn to enrich the quality of their electronic exchanges (Leonardi et al., 2010; Ortiz De Guinea et al., 2012). Also, user preferences can be taken into consideration (e.g., mail, videocalls, chat) to design communications; or the use of reminders to prevent communication breakdown.

Remote relations are not less social nor less proximate (Ruiller et al., 2019). Teleworkers will use ICTs to manage perceive distance adjusting the characteristics of the media (e.g., richness, interactivity, synchronicity) used in each interaction (Burgoon et al., 2002). Workmate communication is key to creating that subjective proximity (Wilson et al., 2008). Frequent, deep, and interactive communications reduce the level of uncertainty, thus building a sense of closeness (Fonner & Roloff, 2012). Remote workmate communications compensate for face-to-face encounters, reinforcing the communication process involved in perceived proximity (O'Leary et al., 2014b). In short, communication is pivotal to influence the sense of proximity with one another, providing symbolic meaning and shared value references (Ruiller et al., 2019). Strong bonds can be created among coworkers despite the lack of physical presence (O'Leary et al., 2014b); information systems act as vehicles for conveying perceived closeness and shared meaning. As people interact strongly and frequently, they can create a sense of proximity, regardless of their location (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). Thus, the following hypothesis is raised:

H2: Workmate Communications WFH positively influences perceived proximity

Feeling close or far from a coworker is an individual and subjective experience. Coworkers understand each other better when they have common grounds, between them. Common ground can be referred as the mutual understanding, common block of knowledge between the dyad. Shared backgrounds and experiences create a context where coworkers can share their concerns, specific knowledge, and so on. On the other hand, the absence of it would explain a feeling of separation (Wilson et al., 2008). For example, if an employee's need for belonging is not met through the identification with coworkers, he/she will experience relational deficiency, resulting in feelings of

isolation (Cacioppo & Cacioppo, 2018). Common ground is built from whatever cues are available at a specific moment. For example, a workmate's appearance in an online meeting or a coworker's behavior during a conversation can result in identity building process (Olson & Olson, 2000).

Shared identification is a self-categorization process, where one feels belonging to a same social category of that of his/her peer (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). Sense of identity may be built through the iterative use of feedback commentary; reaching agreement and commitment on achieving shared goals or hosting informal events to bring a personal context into the professional relationships. ICT-based interactions can be used to transmit the symbols of such shared values and identity, expressing what brings them together (O'Leary et al., 2014b).

This share sense of identity positively reduces psychological distance. Amongst studied potential bases for identification, shared personal values and commitment to work have proved most influential to build a sense of shared identity (O'Leary et al., 2014b). Individual affinity to telework would entail individuals are more willing to engage in identity-building activities, thereby enhancing the feelings of perceived proximity (Ruiller et al., 2019). Even in situations where impoverished media is used, shared identity results in higher quality of communications. The more common ground can be established, the easier the communication (Olson & Olson, 2000). Shared identity can create a psychological tie between distant coworkers, which in turn leads to perceived proximity (Wilson et al., 2008).

Psychological distance theories note the positive role shared identity has over achieving perceived proximity (Ruiller et al., 2019). Identification reduces distance by decreasing uncertainty (Wilson et al., 2008). Identification leads people to mitigate uncertainty with positive attributions of the other when the information/ behaviors are not visible. For example, when coworkers identify with one another they are more likely to receive the benefit of the doubt (Hinds & Mortensen, 2005). Finding common ground, reducing uncertainty, or throwing positive attitudes in case of uncertainty are mechanisms that naturally occur between individuals with a shared sense of identity (Ruiller et al., 2019). The symbolic meaning in communication with a dyad with whom one shares identity fosters perceived proximity (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). Workmate identification is a core element of psychological distance. Thus, the following hypothesis is raised:

H3: Workmate identification in work-from home positively influences perceived proximity

Telework conditions are important to shaping employee's wellbeing at telework (Sardeshmukh et al., 2012). Some intrinsic conditions of telework have been recognized as advantageous for employee's wellbeing (e.g., flexibility, autonomy, or lack of commute time). WFH offer employees some health-promoting effects like concentration, less interruptions, and more privacy (Leonardi et al., 2010). Negative feelings from work exhaustion may be ameliorated when working from the comfort of home (Charalampous et al., 2019). On the other hand, adapting to telework arrangements can give origin to additional physical and psychological strain; the most common health effects of telework are musculoskeletal problems, increased work, lack of social interactions, stress and isolation or depression (Niebuhr et al., 2022; Stempel & Siestrup, 2022). In sum, WFH is not necessarily good nor bad (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007), contradicting results are often explained by contextual elements (e.g., attitude of the manager, openness to experience, telework normative, support structures in place, to name a few) (Kossek et al., 2009; Lautsch et al., 2009; Leonardi et al., 2010).

Telework changes the distance between office and home, it shifts communication patterns towards ICT-based interactions, resulting in an altered work relationships that are likely to impact affective wellbeing at work. Turning the focus on reviewing the outcomes of telework on employee wellbeing, research evidence is still scarce. In the recent years, more intensely since COVID-19 pandemic, interest is building around contextual factors of telework (Beauregard et al., 2019a) such as quality of relationships, synchronicity of communications, or knowledge transfer dynamics, to name a few (Boell et al., 2016; Fay & Kline, 2012; Felstead & Henseke, 2017; Yang et al., 2022). Research shows consensus on the negative effect WFH has on workplace isolation, derived from detriment of interpersonal relations (Illegems & Verbeke, 2004). Isolation has been labeled as the biggest demon of telework (Adamovic, 2022; Beauregard et al., 2019a; Bloom et al., 2013). The lack of such psychological closeness can damage their health (Spilker & Breaugh, 2021), and affective state at work (Golden & Veiga, 2008; Marshall et al., 2007). Thus, the role of coworker support is vital in telework environments. Results of negative or positive affect depend on the individual's assessment of the quality and quantity of the social relations experienced in the workplace (S. Wright & Silard, 2021). Teleworkers who enjoy rich social connectedness WFH present improved affective wellbeing, compared with those that don't (Allen et al., 2015). Daily interactions with coworkers influence the affective state of teleworkers (Liu et al., 2022a). Self-regulation of those interactions helps teleworkers relativize professional issues at work (Ruiller et al., 2019). Such self-regulation can also help teleworkers maintain focus on their work and avoid unwanted office politics, in turn improving their affective wellbeing (Fonner & Roloff, 2010). A balance of formal and informal relations with coworkers of choice can create a sense of closeness, while positively influencing affective wellbeing (Oakman et al., 2020). In sum, perceived proximity between coworkers makes happy teleworkers (Dekker et al., 2015).

Results from research on the impact of psychological proximity in employee's wellbeing is inductive of a positive influence of perceived proximity in affective wellbeing. Those more socially connected tended to have more positive effect, and less negative effect, on wellbeing than those that stayed less connected (Allen et al., 2015). Coworker support has been found positively associated with affective wellbeing (Collins et al., 2016b; Grant et al., 2013). So, it is possible to assume that perceived proximity has a positive impact on affective wellbeing:

H4: Perceived proximity in work-from-home positively influences affective wellbeing

Work environments have a tremendous impact on the affective wellbeing of employees (Cooper & Kurland, 2002; Wilkinson et al., 2018). One approach known to be favorable to bring happiness in one's work life is employee voice (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020). Organizations that implement such mechanisms benefit from enhanced decision making, whilst employees benefit from improved health and increased job satisfaction. A management model based on trust amongst supervisors and employees and between coworkers is key when WFH (Avolio et al., 2014; Nagata et al., 2021). In telework settings, open channels of communications are important to solve problems. Communication efficiency between colleagues and within the organization brings satisfaction in the remote work environment (Belostecinic et al., 2022). Direct expression of voice provides employees with means to participate in decision making and engage in telework adoption discussions. If teleworkers are willing to engage in citizenship behavior expressing their opinions, ideas, or suggestions to do things differently, rather than focusing on mere criticism (Liu et al., 2022a), they will benefit from increased affective wellbeing.

Voice expression is typically seen as an activity that can increase job satisfaction, through its articulation in all directions (upwards, downwards, and sideways) (Budd, 2014). Budd (2014) notes that traditional categorizations of voice may have ignored new ways of engaging in employee-employee voice expression. In today's digitized world of work, new ways to socialize and express voice online are needed in remote work environments (Marshall et al., 2007). Social media is increasingly being associated with direct expression of employee voice (Barnes et al., 2019). Voicing over social media has enabled employees with the ability to directly express their voice and influence others (van Zoonen et al., 2014). This salient form of voice is challenging the previous knowledge of direct voice; providing with new means to have a say in the open forum and influencing other concerned with similar business challenges (Silverman et al., 2013). Social media use for direct voice expression has facilitated the capturing of wisdom of crowds of employees, accessible to all regardless of the size of the organization they belong to.

The use of social media for work-related purposes has been found valuable to increase psychological wellbeing of employees, derived from increased communication among employees (Sakka & Ahammad, 2020). Social media usage for voice expression provides a variety of technology-enabled features (e.g., sharing photos, emoticons, video posting, ...) to voice their concerns, suggestions, or support in multiple informal direct ways (Bhatti et al., 2020). With the evolution of employee voice towards informal, direct systems such as social media, public social media becomes a suitable candidate to comfortably express one's voice forms (Estell et al., 2021). Those who express their voice over social media are expected to receive increased coworker support (Han & Xia, 2020). Social support is a requirement for affective wellbeing (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Activities intended to participate in decision making positively influences affective wellbeing (Guest, 2017). Expressing one's voice on social media, teleworkers fulfill their need to autonomously express their ideas, suggestions, and opinions. The fulfillment of those needs is positively associated with affective wellbeing (Gillet et al., 2012). Thus, the following hypothesis is offered:

H5: Employee direct voice on public social media positively influences affective wellbeing when WFH

Effective employee voice mechanisms are designed to activate social processes such as channeling collective demands reducing uncertainties and promoting changes (Gillet et al., 2012). This maybe particularly interesting when transitioning to telework, where aspects of working conditions, such as home office accommodation, right to privacy, or right to disconnect need to be revisited. Employee voice, particularly Union voice, can help mitigate the negative effect of high demanding or high uncertain remote work settings on employee affective wellbeing (della Torre, 2019; Holland et al., 2016). Union voice is recognized on its ability to improve certain work-related outcomes such as productivity, engagement, and participation (della Torre, 2019; Wilkinson et al., 2018). These outcomes are determinant of the affective state of employees WFH (Guest, 2017).

Voice expressed through the Unions online channels can also play a role in building collective voice under telework arrangements (Barnes et al., 2019). The internet has the potential for Unions to be a tool for informing about telework-specific conditions, rights, or request for support. Unions online channels are also valuable for informing union and non-union members about the results of their negotiations (Smith & Duxbury, 2020). If employees perceive Unions activities fruitful, they will increase their participation in events and campaigns and this, in turn, has subsequent positive impacts in work related outcomes such as job performance and trust in management (Newman et al., 2019),

fostering positive affect at work. In high demanding work environments like today's, those who express their voice receive higher coworker support (Holland et al., 2016). Here again, social media is significantly positively related with employee voice.

Unpacking the role of systemic processes, such as information sharing about collective negotiations or supportive relationships to place a suggestion, are core to support employee wellbeing (Guest, 2017). Through effective Union voice mechanisms one can expect teleworker feel heard, supported, and able to join Union's efforts to achieve greater benefit for the crowd (Newman et al., 2019). This perceived organizational support positively predicts affective wellbeing (Gillet et al., 2012). Thus, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H6: Employee indirect voice positively influences affective wellbeing when WFH

2.4 Model

This thesis is a quantitative study. It collects new data using existing constructs but also takes the opportunity to test theoretical grounds on new context: large sample of experienced teleworkers. Structural Equation Modelling will be used for this type of research. This seems an appropriate method which allows to relate scores from several latent variables (e.g., perceived proximity, employee voice, affective wellbeing, ...) forming chained causal relations.

The main research question is: What is the impact of perceived proximity and employee voice in wellbeing under intense work-from-home contexts?

The dependent variable in the study is affective wellbeing of those WFH in large organizations. This thesis is not intended to explore broad impact of telework in wellbeing but rather it examines whether two specific factors (coworker perceived proximity and employee voice) influence affective wellbeing of employees WFH in large organizations. We will apply iterative analysis of the causal relations of variables in the model. Thus, first three potential antecedents of perceived proximity will be analyzed. Namely, the use of enterprise social networks, the workmate communication, and workmate identification will be tested against their ability to influence perceived proximity. Past researchers have empirically found positive and significant influence of communication and shared identity on perceived proximity (O'Leary et al., 2014b; Ruiller et al., 2019). The inclusion of the use of ESNs represents a contribution to perceived proximity theory. Second, the impact of perceived proximity on affective wellbeing will be assessed. Following a similar approach, a second research perspective is developed. Through this second perspective, the model investigates a range of employee voice mechanisms in telework environments supports positive or negative affect in employees. Here again, a range of modern communication channels and media will be assessed, to construct valuable evidence for researchers and practitioners. Figure 4 shows a visual representation of the research model, outlining the key *independent variables* to be studied under each research perspective: Perceived Proximity and Employee Voice.

Hence, given the little knowledge of the antecedents of affective wellbeing in future work scenarios, the design of the model attempts to provide a rich contextual analysis of what improves wellbeing WFH. Individual contextual factors contemplated in the study include indicators like previous experience WFH, telework longevity, telework propensity or telework intensity. At the organizational level, the employer's telework maturity or the existence of telework conditions in collective

agreements are also relevant factors for the study. Regarding electronic communication with a coworker, the research model contemplates a revision of the main communication technologies available in modern organizations today. Examples of tools considered include videoconference, social networking sites, email, instant messaging (e.g., Teams, WhatsApp, ...). We have also segmented formal and informal communications. Perceived effectiveness of ESN usage in building a sense of closeness will also be assessed.

Other context-rich variables included in the model are related with employee voice mechanisms. Examples of these are the choice of public social media used to express direct voice; perceived effectiveness of Unions/working councils' contribution to the adoption of telework arrangements; perceived usefulness of Unions/working council communications, or participation in different online activities organized by Unions/working councils (e.g., social media campaigns, electronic bulletin boards, informative webinars, ...).

Figure 4 - Research model

Source: Own elaboration

3. Methods

The primary goal of this study was to test the stated research question that relate perceived proximity, and employee voice with affective wellbeing. To answer the research question, six hypotheses have been formulated. First, three hypotheses have been raised to examine three antecedents of perceived proximity (namely use of ESNs, workmate communication and workmate identification). In all cases a positive relation between the independent variable and perceived proximity is assumed. Then, perceived proximity is tested on its influence to improve affective wellbeing; the result from this assumption has not been tested before. The last two hypotheses evaluate the influential role both direct and indirect employee voice have on affective wellbeing. We expect that both forms of expression of voice positively affect the wellbeing of the teleworkers. Figure 4 – Research model above visually explains this situation. The methodology employed to test the research questions is explained in this chapter. The chapter is organized into 4 sections: (b) sampling procedure, (b) instrumentation, (c) methodology used for statistical analysis.

3.1 Sampling procedures

3.1.1 Selection of participants

The target population of this study is skilled workers and managers somewhat experienced WFH.

Our aim is that the sample is representative, free of sampling errors and bias and sufficiently large. A total of 10 industry sectors were represented although there is a dominance of Services (56.4%), Communication, Gas and Sanitary service (11.6%) and Public Administration (10.6%).

542 responses were collected. Participants were mostly based in Spain (83.87%) but also in other countries (e.g., England (5.3%), other European countries (7.8%), and non-European countries (3.2%)). Most informants (71.6%) worked in large organizations (business with more than 250 employees).

Telework researchers advise of the need to further investigate contextual factors when analyzing telework outcomes. (Allen et al., 2015; Leonardi et al., 2010) In this sense, the societal and work context in which this project collected data is unique. With stagnant regular telework adoption rates circa 5.4% of the working population in EU-27, prior to Covid-19 pandemic (Eurofound, 2020), the large proportion of skilled teleworkers in the present study draws attention to analyze additional contextual factors. Demographics of the data collected revealed 75,6% of the respondent accumulated more than a year of experience WFH. Additionally, 51,7% of the participants were intensively WFH (more than half of the workdays) at the time of the study.

The average age of informants is slightly over 46 years old, ages ranging from 20 to 73 years old. Most participants (74%) lived with a partner; 43.7% did not hold childcare responsibilities at the time, 50.1% had 1 or 2 children living with them; 6.2% were raising 3 or more children. With regards to teleworkers gender, 53.9 % were female and 43.4% male. In terms of education 43.5% reported having a college degree, 5.8% having beyond college degree, 43.7% had achieved up secondary education degree, and 6.8% only had a primary education degree.

Table 4 - *Participants based on gender, age, number of children, partner status* summarizes the sample demographic characteristics 52.4% (n=284) of the participants were line managers to other employees; 139 of which were female, 145 were male. 56.4% of managers in the sample had attained college or higher degrees, 4.9% held up to primary education.

Table 4 - Participants based on Gender, Age, Number of children, Partner status

	N (542)	%
Gender:		
Female	292	53.9%
Male	235	43.4%
Age:		
	M: 46.13	SD: 9.15
<30	46	8.7%
30-35	23	4.3%
36-41	47	8.9%
42-49	225	42.4%
>=50	190	35.8%
Children:		
	M: 1.07	SD: 2.18
None	227	43.7%
1	107	20.6%
2	153	29.5%
3	27	5.2%
4+	5	1%
Living with a partner:		
Yes	401	74%
No	110	20.3%
I'd rather not say	31	5.7%

Source: Own elaboration

Longevity and intensity in telework are relevant characteristics for the present study. Average tenure in the employer at the time of the study was 11.75 years. Out of all respondents, 13.1% had changed employer within the last 23 months. 76.9% of participants held a permanent full time employment relationship with the current employer, 4.6% were permanent part time employees. In terms of experience with telework. Figure 12 - *Telework longevity funnel graph* (Annex I) shows the spread of longevity WFH. 60.1% of respondents had between 1 and 2 years of experience WFH; 6.3% of respondents had not experienced WFH yet. Figure 13 - *Telework intensity funnel graph* shows the distribution of telework intensity in the data collected. 51.7% of respondents were currently WFH more than half of their working time; 9.3% were not WFH at the time of the study.

For 9.3% of respondents the employer had regulated telework-specific labor conditions; 37% of respondents did not, 14.9% did not know and 38.8% of respondents claimed telework regulation was being negotiated at the time of the survey. Only 5 out of 542 respondents manifested being affiliated to Unions; 467 respondents chose not to answer this question.

Telework literature reflects on the importance of two additional factors which will be relevant to analyze the results: (a) organizational tenure having an impact in employee voice behaviors (Holland et al., 2016), (b) supervisors having a different experience of telework both in voluntary and crisis-induced situations (Lautsch et al. 2009, Donnelly & Proctor-Thomson, 2015; Lautsch et al., 2009). Table 5 displays the participants included in the study based on tenure with current employer, and employee category (*line manager* was defined as holding supervisory responsibilities over other people at work).

Table 5 - Participants based on Tenure and Category

	N (542)	%
Tenure (years):	M: 11.75	SD: 10.00
<5	188	35.6%
5-9	67	12.7%
10-14	74	14.0%
15-19	77	14.6%
>=20	122	23.1%
Category:		
Line Manager (Yes)	284	52.4%
Line Manager (No)	254	47.6%

Source: Own elaboration

3.1.2 Sampling procedure

According to the Spanish Statistics Institute (INE), at the time of the survey there were 19,6 million workers in Spain, of which 1,5 million were working at home most of the time, and 1 million were doing so occasionally (less than half of their working time) (ONTSI, 2021).

The study was conducted using a single source of documentation: online questionnaire. The questionnaire attempted to capture the psychological experiences in times of lockdown. As there was contact restriction imposed for pandemic control, the link to the research site was shared online, through LinkedIn social media platform and email. Online survey is a usual tool in telework research studies. The survey was designed and published using Google forms. Figure 5 is an attempt to represent the survey design in line with the proposed research model. We followed a snowball sampling strategy to recruit a large group of respondents with a varied socio-demographic set of backgrounds. Snowball sampling implies that initially identified participants, on voluntary basis, take an active part identifying members of the target population, thus assisting the researcher. The participants were able to access the link and complete the questionnaire that took less than fifteen minutes to complete. Participation in the study was voluntary, no reward was offered in return to taking part in the study. Participants were informed about the anonymity of the study. Initially targeted individuals were asked to pass on to other colleagues so they could answer too. Snowball sampling can be effective when initially exploring new phenomena (e.g., intensive work-from-home environments in Spain) and reaching to populations that hard to locate (e.g., due to Covid-19 restrictions). Although the adoption of this non-probabilistic sampling technique precluded the generalizability of the findings (Mendonça et al., 2022) we found the technique appropriate given the limitations imposed by Covid-19.

The online questionnaire contained room for comments to receive a more complete impression of the respondents' answers. A copy of the proposed questionnaire can be found here <https://forms.gle/FhxtEJLrnBtKcdmV8>.

Two separate phases of questionnaire development were included as part of this study.

Phase I - Academic validation

The first phase included the validation of the first version of the questionnaire by a group of international academic authors experts in the related field. On 31st March 2021, an email introducing the study and an online copy of the questionnaire was sent out to 17 authors of 11 studies relevant to the literature review conducted as part of this dissertation, this included experts in empirical research about perceived proximity (Michael O’Leary), telework (Ravi S. Gajendran) or wellbeing (Anne Arvola). Complementary to this action several academics from the Doctorate school at Complutense University of Madrid and Toulouse School of Management were consulted. We are very grateful to each of the thirteen academics that provided valuable feedback on the first version of the questionnaire. Each commentary and suggestion were carefully considered to include in the questionnaire. A second version of the online questionnaire was elaborated to be used in Phase II.

Phase II – User test

From 14th April to 1st May 2021 a user test phase was undertaken. On the start date, an email/ message was sent to a selected group of 30 users requesting their participation and feedback on the questionnaire. The participants were instructed to take the survey for testing purposes and report back on their impressions, difficulties, understanding and overall feeling about each of the questions. To run this test the questionnaire was modified adding a commentary field after each question to facilitate the feedback process. Participants in the user test were also given the opportunity to provide feedback verbally or over email.

Feedback from the user test participants was carefully considered and final adjustments were made. To mention some examples of such comments: users and academics reported a sense of repetitiveness in the perceived proximity scale; re-wording of the privacy statements was suggested; considering social network channels such as WhatsApp/Telegram in employee voice, among other valuable ones.

Phase III – Data collection

The online questionnaire was first launched in Spain (9th May 2021) in Spanish and English. To avoid some of the drawbacks of online surveys, such as perception of junk email, respondents lack of online expertise, feeling impersonal or unclear answering instructions (Evans & Mathur, 2005), the questionnaire was launched via LinkedIn social network. LinkedIn is the world largest professional network with millions of users and one of the fastest growing social networks. Through this network members can create and share their online identities and build professional networks (Bonsón & Bednárová, 2013). 79% of companies use LinkedIn, mostly to engage with current and potential employees. Previous studies on telework have relied on LinkedIn to collect data, namely: van Zoonen et al. (2014), Kok (2008), Müller and Niessen (2019); Ipsen and Kirchner (2020), Spilker and Breaugh (2021), and Blahopoulou et al. (2022). Thus, LinkedIn seemed like an appropriate platform in which to launch the online survey, as opposed to email lists or other online contact solutions.

The online survey was launched using two initial LinkedIn posts (in English and Spanish) sent from my personal LinkedIn user account. The posts introduced the scope of my dissertation, provided the link to the online survey (one link for each language), clarified privacy and security issues (e.g., the security of transmissions and how data will be used). To arrive at a diverse range of respondents with sufficient variation on the variables studied, we followed the strategy of (Spilker & Breaugh, 2021) who used LinkedIn and other contacts to collect a sample of employees who represented a variety of

jobs and worked for several employers. We then used a snowball sampling strategy to find employees within those networks that were currently or had recently been WFH.

Specifically, we used two methods. First, we contacted individuals from the professional network who might be able to get access to teleworkers. We sent LinkedIn private messages to these individuals and asked for their participation in a study involving telework practices. Apart from requesting their individual response in the survey we suggested them to forward the access to the survey to members of his/her professional network experienced with telework. Thus, the sample developed using the snowball approach. Second, we solicited participation from members of telework-specific LinkedIn groups such as “*Teleworking and smart working*” or “*Telework in Spain*”, to name a few. Besides completing the survey, the participants of these groups were asked to distribute it with their professional network colleagues at and out of the platform. Respondents were explained that individual responses would be anonymized. Individuals who agreed to participate voluntarily followed the link to the Google Forms containing the consent form and the survey questions.

The online survey was designed following the guidelines from Evans and Mathur (2005) to mitigate the potential weakness of online surveys. To avoid perception of junk survey access to the survey link was preceded by a LinkedIn post explaining the academic nature of the investigation, supported by Complutense University of Madrid. To mitigate respondent lack of online survey expertise, clear instructions were provided to access the survey via an URL embedded; also, an email address was provided in case any support or help was needed. The survey was pretested on several devices (laptop, tablet, mobile) to ensure participants did not suffer from technological variations. Clear privacy policy statement was visible underneath the header of the survey.

Choosing an online survey as platform to collect data in this project provide intrinsic value to the data collection process. Some of the key benefits of online survey considered when choosing the data collection method include: speed and timeliness (this was very relevant to the study as the evolution of the social distancing restrictions in most European required for a rapid reach to a large-scale sample of participants); array of diversity in the question structures to maintain the scales used by previous authors in the instruments used; ease of data entry to ensure a high completion rate; lastly, low administration cost was a considered decision factor (Evans & Mathur, 2005).

3.2 Instrumentation

The survey participants provided demographic information such as age (in years), gender (0=’Male; 1= ’Female; 2= ’non-binary; 3=’I’d rather not say) and co-living status (*Do you live with a partner?* 0=’Yes; 1=’No; 2=’I’d rather not say). They indicated the number of children living at their house and whether they had other caretaking responsibilities (0=’Yes; 1= ’No).

Participants in the survey were also asked to answer questions about their jobs. They were asked whether they supervised the work of other people (0=’Yes; 1=’No), their employment type from a pre-populated list that included 6 employment type from permanent fulltime to freelancer/contractor), the size of the company (number of employees) they were currently employed at (=0’Between 1 and 10; 1=’Between 11 and 50; 2=’Between 51 and 250; 3=’More than 250), or the tenure with the current employer (number of years). Regarding telework contextual factors they were asked about their previous experience WFH (0=’I have not yet; 1=’Under 6 months; 2=’6-12 months; 2=’13-24

months; More than 24 months); the intensity of their current telework arrangement (number of days per month) and the existence of telework normative in their company (0='No; 1='I don't know; 2='It's currently being negotiated; 3='Yes, it's company-specific agreement; 4='Yes, it's sector-wide agreement). Lastly, they were asked whether they were affiliated to a Union/working council (0='Yes; 1='No; 2='I'd rather not say).

The systemic view provided by Baruch and Nicholson has provided powerful insights to the design of measurement instruments (questionnaire) in the present study; specially in the definition of control variables included in the survey. To name a few, the following variables have been included to cover all four factors in Baruch and Nicholson framework:

- Home/work interface: marital status, children, extent of telework, skills and usage of online collaborative ICT tools, training support needed, ...
- The person: Telework longevity, education levels, direct employee voice, telework preference, ...
- The job: Employee characteristics, company-tenure, co-worker communication process, co-worker identification process
- The organization: Company characteristics, existence of Enterprise Social Networks, telework regulation, indirect voice mechanisms.

Figure 5 - Survey design alignment to research model

Source: Own elaboration

3.2.1 Outcome variable: Affective wellbeing

To address the research question, employee affective wellbeing will be used as dependent variable. Wellbeing at (tele)work will be measured using Warr (1990) scale. The questionnaire consists of eighteen questions rated on 4-point scale responses (from 1='Never to 4=' Almost all the time). The complexity of definition of concepts in psychology (Gonsalves and Neves, 2011) extends the number of items required in a scale to produce acceptable psychometric results. The items measure the positive and negative affect separately. Participants were asked to reflect on how they had felt in the last two weeks. Examples of positive affective questions are: 'Have you ever felt particularly excited or interested in something?' 'Have you ever been full of energy?', or 'Have you ever felt really cheerful?'. Questions assessing negative affect include: 'Have you ever been afraid of might happen?'; 'Have you ever felt really tired?', or 'Have you ever felt like crying?'.

The general model of affective wellbeing has been used to describe the subjective estimation of individual wellness. A degree of pleasure or satisfaction may be accompanied with a certain degree of activation (high or low); the same that can happen with feelings of displeasure or dissatisfaction. Positive, and negative affect are statistically independent (Bradburn, 1969) when measured counting number of positive and negative experiences; that is, desirable and undesirable experiences generally arise from uncorrelated episodes. Positive and negative affect are statistically independent and correlate differently with other variables. Bradburn found positive affect is associated with high levels of social contact or participation in new activities; such activities are shown to be uncorrelated with negative affect.

Warr (1990) borrowed from Bradburn (1969) initial scale but modified the Bradburn's response mode (counts of positive and negative experiences within a timeframe) to a rating in the form of proportion of time below and above the personal norm. Warr's changes to previous scales was based on the new evidence of wellbeing response modes producing relevant differences in statistical results. Warr (1990) examined an alternative form of response measured as a proportion of time and found strong negative correlations between negative and positive affect.

Peter Warr also introduced the concept of general affective wellbeing into workplace studies. He classified work-related emotions following general affective wellbeing dimensions. This dual axis model, see Figure 6, gave way to the positive and negative affect scale. The pleasure axis has been often measured through reported job satisfaction. Occupational studies are often interested in the research of the diagonal axis 2 and 3. Factorial analysis of work-related wellbeing may be understood as a multidimensional phenomenon; depression, comfort, anxiety, and enthusiasm seem to be the best factorial solution. When tested in a work-related environment, the axis enthusiasm-depression showed stronger correlation with intrinsic job satisfaction than the anxiety-comfort axis.

Figure 6 - Affective wellbeing measurement dimensions

Source: Own elaboration inspired by Warr (1990)

3.2.2 Perceived proximity measures

The first quantitative study on perceived proximity (O’Leary et al., 2014a) was undertaken using a large-sample international survey. The team of researchers were interested in assessing the impact of objective and perceived distance in the quality of working relationships. Results from the mixed method investigation shed light into the evolved richness of ICT-based interactions, the symbolic value of communication and the identification processes and its significance in the creation of a sense of proximity. Contrary to previous findings, O’Leary et al. (2014b) found distant relationships can become as personal and close as collocated ones. These findings are turnkey to telework management practice. Perceived proximity is a strong construct to shape outcomes in today’s work environments as it “outweighs objective proximity” (O’Leary et al., 2014b, p. 16). Qualitative results from the study reveal that the relationship between objective distance and perceived proximity is mediated by means like rich conceptions of technological mediums, the history of relationships, or member identity.

- Perceived proximity was first quantitatively measured by O’Leary and his team to measure the dyadic construct using a 6-item scale. This scale asks participants to think of a distant coworker and rate the extent (from 1=’Strongly disagree’ to 5=’ Strongly agree’) to which they agree/disagree with the provided statements. Examples of the statements are: “Psychologically, this colleague feels close”, “I feel closer to this colleague than the actual physical distance would suggest”. Before the actual launch of the questionnaire to participants we performed a pilot test with a group of people and requested validation from several academics. Feedback from these activities influenced the decision to adapt this scale and reduce the number of items included. Academic and user participants in the pilot study reported some of the statements in the scale felt equivalent, thus making the survey completion a repetitive experience. Adaptations to this scale were made taking into consideration the academic validation and the feedback from users. Figure 14 (Annex I)

displays the original items used in by O’Leary et al. (2014). In Figure 15 we have reflected a snapshot of the items used in our online questionnaire.

- Workmate identity scale literally followed the method applied by O’Leary et al. (2014a). The participants were asked to rate the similarity to their colleague based on values, commitment to work and hobbies. Their choices ranged from “not like me at all”, “not like me”, “somewhat like me”, “exactly like me”, and “I don’t know”.
- Workmate communication was formed by combining the measure O’Leary et al. (2014a) applied for communication frequency and added modern remote work medium (e.g., videoconference) and formality levels (e.g., formal events versus informal events). Following the scale applied by O’Leary and the team, participants were asked to indicate how often (from 1= ‘Never to 5= ‘More than 5 times a week) do they communicate with a colleague of choice during an average week. Sample measures included statements like “Videoconference formal meetings”, “Instant messaging (MS Teams, WhatsApp, ...)”, “Informal events organized by employer”, or “Informal events organized by employer”. The scale used by O’Leary et al. has been adapted to incorporate videoconference media and to distinguish formal and informal communications with coworker. Table 6 reflects the adaptations made.
- ESN usage is added to pre-existing perceived proximity model. Following Moqbel et al. (2013), a single item scale assessed the existence of ESNs in the participants’ company (“Yes and I use it”, “Yes; but I hardly use it”, “No”). Those participants that did not account for an ESN in their company were asked to skip this section. For those respondents who confirmed the existence, domain of use and internal orientation was assessed. Following the method applied by (Neirotti et al., 2017) on ESN usage was divided into two reflexive constructs.
 - First, we measured the perceived effectiveness of ESN usage by asking participants to rate the effectiveness of communication (1=’Strongly disagree, 5=’Strongly agree) via ESNs in four different internal domains (“Unions and affiliated members”, “Worker representatives”, “Company management”, and “coworkers”).
 - Then, the potential benefit of ESN usage was measured. These items were operationalized by using a 5-point Likert scale with responses ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree” in which respondents had to evaluate whether ESNs led to a significant impact on a series of 4 items. Specifically, the items used to measure the perceived benefit of ESN usage were: “The social network helps build a sense of belonging to the company”, “The social network contributes to feeling closer to fellow workers”, “I have discovered new coworkers with whom I share ideas, hobbies”, “The social network contributes to feeling closer to fellow workers”, “My line manager supports me in the use of the social network”. Following Avolio et al. (2014) suggestion that affect may emerge from managers behavioral reaction to adoption of new technologies, one last item was added in the scale: “My line manager uses the social network”.

3.2.3 Employee Voice measures

Employee voice will be assessed through multiple scales to represent a composite structure. The scales used are first presented in the list below and individually described afterwards:

- Affiliation to Unions
- Telework regulation (included/not included collective bargaining)
- Indirect voice:
 - Perceived effectiveness of Unions contributions to telework adoption topics.
 - Communication channels used by Unions to engage with employees.
 - Employee participation in Union online activities.
- Direct voice:
 - The usage (channels and frequency) of public social media as a channel to express their voice.

Building on previous analysis of *collective agreements* on telework in Spanish firms, participants were asked to respond about telework-specific collective arrangements. Before the pandemic outbreak, only 27% of Spanish firms have introduced telework (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020). Given the state of transition at the time of the survey, the existence of collective arrangements was assessed with the following statements “No”, “I don’t know”, “It’s currently being negotiated”, “Yes, it’s company-specific agreement”, and “Yes, it’s sector-wide agreement”.

Hirschman (1970) and other voice researchers define voice not simply in terms of the expression of concerns but also the mobilization of opinion. Such mobilization can be operationalized using member participation data as the measure for Union voice. Employee voice measures (direct and indirect) used is inspired by the work of Barnes et al. (2019), Thornthwaite et al. (2018), and the new telework legislation passed in Spain in 2020.

Indirect voice

Thornthwaite et al. (2018) analyzed Union member experiences with Union social media services; a year later, the same team studied how trade Unions were using social media to communicate with and represent their members’ interests. Indirect voice was operationalized following the method used by Barnes et al. (2019).

- The frequency of use of Union communication channels was measured following Thornthwaite et al. (2018) method. In the context of telework adoption, survey participants were asked to assess the frequency (from 1= “Never”, to 5 = “Always”) of use to *gain information* about ‘your rights’, ‘Union campaigns’, and ‘about What’s happening in the industry’. To complete this indirect voice scale, two additional questions were added to measure the frequency of access to Unions to ‘raise a complaint’ or ‘make a suggestion’.
- Unions/worker council contribution to improving WFH arrangements was operationalized with a scale measuring their involvement in the negotiation of topics defined under minimum legal requirements (Royal Decree-Law 28/2020 for private employers and Royal Decree-Law 29/2020 for public employers). Participants indicated their agreement (from 1= “Strongly Disagree” to 5= “Strongly agree”) with seven statements reflecting the underpinning

contribution in the aspects established by law such as home office ergonomics, the right-to-disconnect, equality of gender and minority groups, or digital communication amongst co-workers.

- The frequency of Union activity with regards to telework adoption is measured in a nine-item scale inspired by Barnes et al. (2019) scale of Union activity. Participants were asked to rate how frequently (from 1=“Never” to 5=“Always”) did they receive useful information about working arrangements through several Union activities such as email, digital bulletin, meetings with workers representatives, public social media, company social media, public relations with an affiliated officer, Union’s webpage or WhatsApp/telegram groups.
- The frequency of employees undertaking an active role in Union social media is operationalized using the method applied by Thornthwaite et al. (2018). Participants indicated their frequency of participation (from 1= “Never” to 4= “Often”) in online Union activities such as “online campaigns (e.g., Change.org)”, “Like’ the account (Facebook, Twitter, ...)”, “comment on Union/worker council posts”, or “attend online meetings and events.

Direct voice

- Respondents were asked about their frequency of use of most popular social media platforms to express their voice regarding work arrangements. Building on Barnes et al. (2019) a standard 5-Likert scale was used with answers ranging from “never” to “always” on the use of 8 social media platforms (LinkedIn, Glassdoor, Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, WhatsApp/Telegram, Instagram, and Vimeo). The list of social media platforms used was modified. Google+ and Flickr were taken off the list used in Australia and replaced by Glassdoor and WhatsApp/Telegram as they have gained popularity as channels for employees and Unions to express their voice.

3.2.4 Summary of measurements used

Table 6 shows the list of dependent and independent variables used in the model. Table 7 takes up the rest of variables selected for this research model and details the associated measurement instruments.

Table 6 - List of dependent and independent variables

Variable	Description	Scale
Wellbeing (Warr, 1983)	Affective wellbeing. Positive and affective wellbeing scale.	4-point Likert (1= 'Never', 4= 'Almost all the time') 18-item scale. Distinctive measurements for positive and negative affect. Rate of feelings in the past 15 days (e.g., 'Have you ever felt really cheerful'; 'Have you ever felt really tired').
Perceived Proximity (O'Leary et al., 2014)	Subjective experience of coworker proximity (Based on Wilson et al. 2008).	5-point Likert (1= 'Strongly disagree', 5= 'Strongly agree') 4-item scale. Rate agreement/disagreement with statements about perceptions with distant coworker (e.g., 'Psychologically, this colleague feels close', 'Even when we are not working in the same place, I still feel close to this colleague')
Coworker Identification (O'Leary et al. 2014)	The process of building a sense of belonging to a social category (Based on Ashforth and Mael. 1989).	5-point Likert (1= 'Strongly disagree', 5= 'Strongly agree') 3-item scale. Rate of agreement/disagreements with statements about similarities shared with the same coworker in mind (e.g., 'values', 'Commitment to work', 'Hobbies, taste').
Perceived effectiveness of ESN usage (Neirotti et al., 2017)	Perception of effectiveness and benefits of usage of company social networking sites.	5-point (1= 'Strongly disagree', 5= 'Strongly agree') 5-item scale. Rate agreement/disagreement with statements about perceived benefits of ESN usage (e.g., 'I have discovered new coworkers with whom I share ideas, hobbies', 'The social network helps build a sense of belonging to the company'). 5-point (1= 'Strongly disagree', 5= 'Strongly agree') 4-item scale. Rate agreement/disagreement with statements about perceived effectiveness of ESN as company communication channel with others (e.g., 'Workers representatives', 'Company management', 'Coworkers').
Workmate communication (O'leary et al., 2014)	Frequency of communication with distant coworkers through different channels (Based on Wilson et al. 2008).	5-point Likert (1= 'Never'; 5= 'More than 5 times a week') 3-item scale. Frequency of communications with the same coworker through different channels (e.g., 'Videoconference', 'Formal meetings', 'Instant messaging (MS Teams, WhatsApp, ...)'), 'email').
Direct voice (Thornthwaite et al., 2018)	Social media usage to express telework-related topics.	5-point Likert (1= 'Never', 5= 'Always') 6-item scale. Frequency of use of social media platforms to work-related voice. (e.g., 'LinkedIn', 'Twitter', 'WhatsApp/Telegram').
Indirect voice – (Barnes et al., 2019)	Frequency of participation in online events organized by unions.	5-point Likert (1= 'Never'; 5= 'Always') 3-item scale. Frequency of proactively communicating with unions/workers council regarding telework adoption topics (e.g., 'Gain information about my rights', 'To raise a complaint', 'To make a suggestion'). 5-point Likert (1= 'Never'; 5= 'Always') 3-item scale. Frequency of participation in activities organized by unions/workers council (e.g., 'Online campaigns (e.g., Change.org', "Like" the account (Facebook, Twitter...)', 'Comment on union/work council posts').
	Perceived effectiveness of unions activities in telework-related topics.	5-point (1= 'Strongly disagree', 5= 'Strongly agree') 7-item scale. Rate agreement/disagreement with statements about perceived contributions of unions/workers council to improve WFH conditions (e.g., 'Home office ergonomics', 'The "right to disconnect"', 'Work life balance'). 5-point Likert (1= 'Never'; 5= 'Always') 9-item scale. Frequency reception of useful information from unions/workers council activities (e.g., 'Digital bulletin', 'Company social network (Yammer, Oracle ...)', 'Web page').

Source: Own elaboration

Table 7 takes up the rest of variables selected for this doctoral research and details the possible measurement tools associated with.

Table 7 - Rest of variables in the model

Variable	Description	Scale
Extent of telework (Gajendran and Harrison, 2007)	Extent, frequency, also known as intensity of telework. Often measured in the number of days per week/ month employed working from home.	6-point (0= 'None', 1= '1-5', 2= '6-10', 3= '11-15', 4= '16-20', 5= '21+', 1-item 'On average, how many days a month do you currently work from home?'
Telework longevity (Golden, 2006)	Length of time (often measured in years) working under telework arrangements.	5-point (0= 'I haven't yet', 1= 'Under 6 months', 2= '6-12 months', 3= '13-24 months', 4= 'More than 24 months'). 1-item 'How long have you been working from home?'
Telework propensity (Labrado Antolín et al., 2022)	Willingness to telework, measured in number of days per month/week.	7-item (0= 'I wouldn't like to work from home', 1= '1-2 days a month', 2= '1 day a week', 3= '2 days a week', 4= '3 days a week', 5= '4 days a week', 6= '5 days a week'. 1-item scale 'If you were free to choose, how often would you prefer to work from home?'
Union affiliation (Based on Barnes et al., 2019)	Holding a membership to a union.	3-item (1= 'Yes', 2= 'No', 3= 'I'd rather not say'). 1-item 'Are you affiliated to a trade union/worker council?'
Telework collective arrangement (Belzúnegui-Eraso and Erro-Garces, 2020)	Company teleworking arrangements are regulated in the company's collective agreement.	5-item (0= 'No', 1= 'I don't know', 2= 'It's currently being negotiated', 3= 'Yes, it's company-specific agreement', 4= 'Yes, it's sector-wide agreement'). 1-item scale 'Based on your knowledge: is telework adoption part of collective bargaining in your company?'

Source: Own elaboration

3.3 Methodology

Two characteristics of the model that we propose condition the choice of the technique of statistical analysis of the data. On the one hand, *latent* variables are used, that is, *constructs* that are not directly observable, but that are revealed by means of other variables that are observable and whose values are those obtained through the questionnaire used. On the other hand, it raises the existence of a series of causality relationships between latent variables that are complex and cannot be captured by means of a regression model. In a regression model there are several independent variables, the X, which influence a dependent variable, the Y. When the model becomes more complicated and variables appear that are simultaneously dependent and independent, causes of some and consequences of others (one variable X influences other Y, which in turn influences other Z, etc.), we are in the presence of a *path model* (Mair, 2018), which generalizes the conventional regression models and must be analyzed with some statistical tool that takes into account its peculiarities and its greater complexity. *Structural Equation Models* (SEM) are an appropriate analysis tool in a situation like this (Grace, 2006; Hair et al., 2019; Kline, 2016), since they allow modeling complex relationships (path models) between unobservable constructs (latent variables).

SEM models arise as an extension of the classic Factor Analysis model. Factor Analysis model allows to raise, in a somewhat rudimentary way, the existence of latent variables, usually called *factors*, which are revealed by means of a series of observed variables, the indicators, whose values are those that are measured and used in the analysis. However, in factor analysis the relationships that are considered between latent variables, that is, between factors, are very simple, only the existence of correlations between factors is considered, and other possible complex relationships of interdependence between factors are not considered, as it would occur in a path model. SEM type models arise when complex relationships between latent variables is present in a factor analysis model.

In a factor analysis model, a conventional distinction is usually made between Exploratory Factor Analysis, and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (Mair, 2018; Uriel & Aldás, 2005). Exploratory Factor Analysis has, as its name suggests, a character essentially descriptive of the available observations. There are *n* observations of *p* variables, which will therefore be the observed variables, e.g., the indicators. The Exploratory Factor Analysis raises the possibility that these *p* observed

variables are manifestations of a smaller number, q , (with $q < p$) of latent variables, the factors, which would explain in a simpler way the values adopted by the observations.

In Exploratory Factor Analysis, no a priori assumption is made about the possible number of factors, nor about the relationship between factors and latent variables; rather, the number of factors, and the relationship they have with the indicators, arises from the analysis itself in a purely mathematical way. What we are looking for is, among all the possible models, the one that best fits the observations. For this purpose, models with different number of factors are tested to select the one that provides the best results. In Exploratory Factor Analysis it is also common to assume as a starting point that all the factors affect all the indicators and that the factors are uncorrelated with each other. As a result of the analysis, the factors that are related to each indicator will be determined. The coefficients that indicate the relationship between each factor and each indicator are called *factor loads*. For example, if v_1 is an indicator, i. e., an observed variable, and if as a result of the analysis it is found that this variable is a consequence or is affected by three factors, f_1 , f_2 and f_3 , this fact can be expressed mathematically by the following equation:

$$v_1 = \lambda_{11}f_1 + \lambda_{12}f_2 + \lambda_{13}f_3 + \delta_1 \quad (1)$$

The coefficients λ_{ij} are the factor loads and indicate the weight, or influence, that each factor has on the observable variable v_i . There is also an error term, δ_i , which reflects the fact that v_1 will not be totally determined by the factors f_1 , f_2 and f_3 , but that there will be other elements not considered and other random causes that will influence v_1 to some extent. This error term can also consider measurement errors of the variable v_1 .

It is conventional in factor analysis and structural equations to represent latent variables with a circle or ellipse, and observable variables with a square. Then a relation like the one indicated in equation (1) would be represented graphically like shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - Structural equation graphic representation

Source: Own elaboration

In practice there will be several indicators (v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots), and for each one of them there will be an equation like (1), each one also with its respective error term, δ_i . Obviously, the number of factors appearing in each equation will depend on each case.

In general, the process of estimating the model, both in factor analysis and in SEM, involves starting from the matrix of covariances, S , between the observed variables. This is the empirical covariance matrix, which is obtained by calculating the covariances between the indicators using their observed values. This empirical covariance matrix is compared with the theoretical covariance matrix, Σ , which is calculated according to the proposed model.

If there are p indicators, the matrix of covariances between them, S , is a matrix of dimensions $p \times p$, but, as it is symmetric, it will only have $\frac{p(p+1)}{2}$ independent elements, since the elements below the main diagonal will be equal to the elements above it. The theoretical covariance matrix according to the model, Σ , is calculated from the relationships expressed in equations as (1). For example, the covariance between the indicators v_1 and v_2 (the element $\Sigma_{12} = \text{COV}(v_1, v_2)$ of the matrix Σ) is calculated taking into account that these variables are expressed from the factors such as $v_1 = \lambda_{11}f_1 + \lambda_{12}f_2 + \lambda_{13}f_3 + \delta_1$ and $v_2 = \lambda_{21}f_1 + \lambda_{22}f_2 + \lambda_{23}f_3 + \delta_2$, or in a similar way, depending on the model proposed in each case. Equations like $v_i = \lambda_{i1}f_1 + \lambda_{i2}f_2 + \lambda_{i3}f_3 + \delta_i$, which reflect the relationships between latent variables and indicators, can be expressed in a matrix form as:

$$v = \Lambda f + \delta \quad (2)$$

In this expression we have that v is a column vector with the p indicators, f a column vector with the q factors, δ a column vector with the error terms of the indicators, and Λ a matrix of dimensions $p \times q$ with the factor loads that will be estimated.

To facilitate the calculations, it is also usually assumed that the factors have zero mean ($E(f_i) = 0$), that they are uncorrelated with the error terms δ_i , and that their variance is unity. Given these assumptions, the model expressed by equation (2) implies that the matrix of covariances between the indicators, i. e., the matrix $\Sigma = \text{var}(v)$, can be calculated as $\Sigma = \Lambda \cdot \text{var}(f) \cdot \Lambda' + \text{var}(\delta)$. In this expression Λ' is the factor loadings matrix transposed, $\text{var}(f)$ the matrix of covariances between the factors, and $\text{var}(\delta)$ the covariance matrix of the error terms. In exploratory factor analysis it is also assumed that the factors are uncorrelated, and their variance is 1, so the matrix $\text{var}(f)$ will be the unity matrix ($\text{var}(f) = I$). In confirmatory factor analysis, the factors are correlated, so their covariance matrix will be a symmetric matrix of dimensions $q \times q$ ($\text{var}(f) = \Phi$), and whose elements will have to be estimated. It is also generally assumed that the error terms are independent

of each other, so the $\text{var}(\delta)$ matrix will be diagonal. Calling this matrix Θ , we have that the general model of confirmatory factor analysis is expressed as:

$$\Sigma = \Lambda\Phi\Lambda' + \Theta \quad (3)$$

In the case of exploratory factor analysis, being the factors f uncorrelated we will have that $\Phi = I$, so the above equation (3) reduces to $\Sigma = \Lambda\Lambda' + \Theta$.

The estimation process seeks to calculate the parameters of the model (mainly the factor loads λ_{ij} , which are the elements of Λ , but also the elements of Φ and Θ) that minimize the difference between the matrices S and Σ . This process of model fitting, or estimation, the search of the parameter values that minimize the difference between S and Σ , is a numerical optimization process that is usually quite complex and for which there are several estimation methods available (Kline, 2016; Uriel & Aldás, 2005; Whittaker & Schumacker, 2022), usually maximum likelihood, but also least squares, generalized least squares, and others.

Intuitively, the essential idea of a factor analysis model, or of a SEM model, is to try to explain the existing variability in a set of observable variables by proposing a simpler model of latent variables that are related with or influence the observed variables, which are the visible manifestation of the latent ones.

A commonly used illustrative example (Uriel & Aldás, 2005) would be the case that the grades of a group of students are available in a series of subjects, Language, Natural Sciences, Foreign Language, History, Mathematics, Physics, etc. These grades are the observable variables. A factor analysis model can be used to see if these grades depend on a reduced set of latent variables, the factors. Estimating the model with an exploratory factor analysis, it could be seen that, indeed, there is a factor with high factorial loads in the grades obtained in subjects such as Language or Foreign Language. That factor could be identified as Verbal Intelligence. There could be another factor with high loads in subjects such as Mathematics, Physics, etc., and which could be identified as Numerical Intelligence. So on, other types of intelligence, e. g. Spatial, could be identified. The result would be that the grades obtained by students in the different subjects are the result of a small number of factors not directly observable such as numerical intelligence, verbal, etc.

In the case of a Confirmatory Factor Analysis, it is no longer a question of discovering how many factors exist or which of them influence each observable variable, but rather a model is proposed in which these aspects are already known, and it is a question of estimating the parameters of the model and testing its significance. The structure of the model and the number of factors is determined based on previous studies, theoretical considerations, etc. Also, it is neither assumed that all factors can influence or be related to all indicators, but it is stated in the model that each indicator is linked to a limited set of factors (although one factor can influence several indicators). In a Confirmatory Factor Analysis, it is also commonly assumed, and incorporated into the model, that there will be correlations or covariances between the factors.

For example, a model of Confirmatory Factor Analysis with 6 indicators and in which it is stated that there are two factors, f_1 , which influences the indicators v_1 , v_2 and v_3 , and f_2 , which influences the indicators v_4 , v_5 and v_6 , is shown in the Figure 1. The correlation between both factors is

represented by the curved line with arrows at both ends that joins them. The label associated with this line, ϕ_{12} , indicates the covariance between the factors.

Figure 8 - Confirmatory Factor Analysis example

Source: Own elaboration

A relevant issue when estimating a factor analysis or structural equations model is that of the model identification. When estimating a model such as the one indicated by equation (3), what is done is to replace the matrix of covariances between indicators, Σ , by its empirical version S , and look for the values of the elements on the right side of the equation, $\Lambda\Phi\Lambda' + \Theta$, which minimize or make zero the difference $S - (\Lambda\Phi\Lambda' + \Theta)$. This ultimately consists of solving a system of equations, where the number of equations is the number of elements of Σ , or of S , that are independent, and that are, as was previously mentioned, $\frac{p(p+1)}{2}$, and the number of variables is that of the parameters in

$\Lambda\Phi\Lambda' + \Theta$. These parameters are the factorial loads, λ_{ij} (the elements of Λ), the covariances between the factors (the elements of the matrix Φ) and the variances of the error terms δ_i (the elements of the matrix Θ). To obtain a unique solution of this system of equations it is necessary to have the same number of equations as variables, as in basic algebra, where three equations are necessary if we have three variables, four equations if we have four variables, and so on.

A factor analysis or SEM model will be identified when in equation (3) the number of variables is equal to the number of equations. The model is under if there are too many parameters to estimate, compared with available equations, so there will be infinite possible solutions for the parameters, and it will be necessary to add constraints on their possible values to obtain a unique solution. The model is over identified if there are more equations (i. e., observed covariances) than parameters to estimate.

In such a case the model can be estimated, and its goodness of fit can also be tested using a χ^2 test. This is analogous to a regression model, where there are more observations than parameters to be estimated, and its goodness of fit can be calculated. The difference between the number of available equations (covariances of the observed indicators) and the number of parameters to be estimated is the number of degrees of freedom of the model, which must be greater than or equal to zero:

$$\text{Degrees of freedom} = \text{Number of observed covariances} - \text{Number of parameters to be estimated}$$

When the model is under-identified, there is an excess of parameters whose value must be set for the model to be identified. By doing so, the number of parameters will be equal to the number of existing

equations and the model can be estimated. There are several ways to set the values of some of the parameters so that the model is identified. In the case of exploratory factor analysis, any rotation of the factors, given by a matrix H that verifies that $H'H = I$, provides valid factors, since introducing $H'H$ in equation (2) we have that $v = \Lambda f + \delta = \Lambda H'Hf + \delta = \Lambda^* f^* + \delta$, where $f^* = Hf$ are the new factors, and $\Lambda^* = \Lambda H'$ are the new factor loadings. In this situation it is usual, to get the model identified, to impose restrictions such as that $\Lambda'\Lambda$ or $\Lambda'\Theta^{-1}\Lambda$ are diagonal matrices (Peña, 2002). In confirmatory factor analysis, to ensure that the model is identified, the values of certain parameters to be estimated are usually set (Kline, 2016), for example, by setting the factor loadings of each factor on one of its associated indicators at 1, or by setting the variance of each exogenous factor at 1. This can be done because of being the factors non observable variables, their scale is essentially arbitrary. Determining by hand the number of parameters to estimate, to see how many parameters must be fixed in order to get the model identified, can be quite cumbersome, so it is usually the software that performs this task and that deals with setting some constraints that allow the model to be identified. There are also some heuristic rules of thumb in the literature that provide a high (but not total) certainty that the model will be identified (Beaujean, 2014; Kline, 2016; Uriel & Aldás, 2005).

When Factor Analysis is combined with Path Analysis we are in the presence of SEM. As indicated, Path Analysis is a generalization of regression models in which the variables, which in Path Analysis are observable, can be simultaneously endogenous and exogenous. They influence each other in a more complex way than in a regression model, where there is simply a set of independent (exogenous) variables, the Xs, which influence a dependent variable (endogenous), the Y. In Path Analysis all the the variables, whether endogenous, exogenous or both, are observable. When some of these variables are allowed to be latent, unobservable variables that manifest themselves through a series of indicators, it is when we find ourselves in the presence of a Model of Structural Equations.

A SEM consists of two parts, a *measurement model*, which indicates the relationships between each latent variable and its indicators, and a *structural model*, which shows the relationships between latent variables, that is, the relationships of influence or causality between them. Of course, it may happen that some of these variables of the structural model are observable, in which case they are “indicators of themselves”, so to speak. A conventional regression model is a particular case of these models, where all variables are observable and some of them are endogenous and the rest exogenous, but none of them can be both endogenous and exogenous. In fact, in a simple regression of one variable, y , on another, x , the coefficient β_1 of the regression model $y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot x + \delta$, is essentially the covariance between x and y , specifically $\beta_1 = \frac{\text{cov}(x, y)}{\text{var}(x)}$, and these variances and covariances are those that are estimated when fitting a SEM model.

The goal of a Structural Equation Model is to try to explain the relationships between a series of observable variables or indicators postulating the existence of some latent variables, the factors, that, on the one hand, are expressed or manifested through the indicators, and, on the other hand, can maintain complex relationships between them.

In a Confirmatory Factor Analysis Model, there is only the measurement model, described by an equation such as (2), since, because there are no relationships between latent variables, there is no structural model. In a SEM model, a structural model reflecting the relationships between factors must be added to the measurement model of equation (2). This structural model is described by a

matrix equation such as the following:

$$f = \Gamma f + \zeta \quad (4)$$

In equation (4) f is a vector with the different factors of the model, Γ a matrix with the coefficients that indicate the relationships between them (analogous to the β coefficients of a conventional linear regression model), and ζ is a vector of error terms that affect the factors that act as dependent variables in the structural model. These error terms account for the effect of variables not collected in the model that have influence on the dependent variables (the error terms are null for the factors that act as independent variables in the structural model).

Combining equation (4), which specifies the structural model, with equation (2), which specifies the measurement model, yields an equation such as $v = \Lambda \Gamma f + \Lambda \zeta + \delta$, which describes how the structural equation model is by indicating how the indicators v relate to the factors f . From this equation it is possible to calculate the matrix of covariances between the observable variables, $\Sigma = \text{var}(v)$, in a similar fashion as with equation (3) for the simpler case of confirmatory factor analysis. This covariance matrix is as follows:

$$\Sigma = \Lambda \Gamma \Phi \Gamma' \Lambda' + \Lambda \Psi \Lambda' + \Theta + g(\Psi) \quad (5)$$

The matrix $\Phi = \text{var}(v)$ is the matrix of covariances between the factors; $\Psi = \text{var}(\zeta)$ is the matrix that allows for incorporating the covariances between the error terms of the factors; $\Theta = \text{var}(\delta)$ is the matrix of covariances between the error terms of the indicators, and $g(\Psi)$ is a function of the matrix Ψ which incorporates the covariances between the factors f and the error terms ζ . The equation (5) is obtained by assuming that all variables are standardized to have zero mean, and that the error terms δ are uncorrelated with each other and with the factors f and the error terms ζ . The process of fitting the model consists of finding the parameters, essentially given by matrices Λ and Γ , that make the matrix of covariances between indicators according to the model, Σ , as similar as possible to the empirical covariance matrix, that is, to the matrix S of the observed covariances between those indicators. Analogous to confirmatory factor analysis models, there is a wide variety of numerical procedures to fit the model, such as maximum likelihood and others (Kline, 2016; Uriel & Aldás, 2005; Whittaker & Schumacker, 2022).

In general, properly assessing the fit of a Structural Equation Model is a complex issue that has been widely debated and researched (Kline, 2016), without it being possible to say that there is a systematic and clearly established procedure to assess such a fit. It is convenient in any case to differentiate the "global" fit of the model from the "local" fit of each of its elements, since it is perfectly possible, and usual, that a model does fit well locally many of its elements, but not all, so the global fit could be bad. Such a model can be a perfectly valid one to test a part at least of the hypotheses raised.

The usual starting point for assessing the overall fit of an SEM model (or factor analysis models that are cases of it) is a χ^2 test. This test is derived from the conventional theory of maximum likelihood

estimation (Peña, 2002). When estimating the parameters of a model by maximum likelihood it is assumed that the random variables involved in the model follow a certain probability distribution, for example normal, and what is estimated are the parameters that characterize this distribution (for example its mean, variance, etc.). For this, a "likelihood function", f , is maximized. This function is the joint probability density of the observations, considered as a function of the parameters to be estimated. To check if a certain parameter of the model (or several of them) is significant, we compare the model that includes that parameter with the same model without including the parameter (that is, with the value of the parameter taken as zero). The model with the parameter is a more complex one and will always fit to the observations better than the simpler model without the parameter, but if the improvement in fit is small enough, the parameter will be not significant. In this case the parameter contributes essentially nothing to the model, so we can reject the complex model and prefer the simpler model without the parameter.

The usual way to implement this procedure is through a hypothesis test, where there is a null hypothesis, H_0 , which assumes that the simpler model is valid, and an alternative hypothesis, H_1 , which assumes that the more complex model (the one with more parameters and that generalizes the simpler one), is valid. If $f(H_0)$ is the value of the estimated likelihood function under the hypothesis H_0 and $f(H_1)$ the estimated value under H_1 , then it always be $f(H_1) \geq f(H_0)$, but if the difference between these two values is small enough, then H_1 is rejected, since the most complex model does not improves almost anything with respect to the simplest. To compare $f(H_1)$ and $f(H_0)$ we use their quotient, $\frac{f(H_0)}{f(H_1)}$, called the likelihood ratio. Asymptotically, i.e., for large

samples, and with certain cautions, if H_0 is valid, the value of $\lambda = -2 \log \left(\frac{f(H_0)}{f(H_1)} \right)$ follows a χ^2 distribution. The number of degrees of freedom of the χ^2 distribution is the difference between the number of parameters of the models corresponding to H_0 , and H_1 . A large value for λ will be unlikely under H_0 , thus ruling out this hypothesis. The usual practice is to set a significance level, α , typically $\alpha = 0.05$, and if $\text{Prob}(\chi^2 \geq \lambda) < \alpha$ the null hypothesis is rejected. This kind of hypothesis tests are called likelihood ratio test.

In the case of a SEM model, to assess its overall fit by means of such a likelihood ratio test, this model, which is considered the simpler model in the test, that is, the one corresponding to H_0 , is compared with a more complex one, that is usually called a "saturated" model. In the saturated model all the parameters (the covariances of the matrix Σ) can vary freely, and the existence of relationships (e.g., correlations) between all the variables in the model is allowed. Hence, a saturated model has a maximal number of parameters, and its covariance matrix is estimated simply as the sample covariance matrix, S , which is directly provided by the observations. The number of degrees

of freedom of the χ^2 used in the test is the difference between the number of independent values in the covariance matrix S , that is, $\frac{p(p+1)}{2}$, and the number of parameters of the model under H_0 .

In a SEM model, when making a likelihood ratio contrast to assess the overall significance of the model, it is taken as a starting point that the proposed model is valid (this is what H_0 would indicate), and this hypothesis is only discarded, in favor of H_1 , if there is sufficient evidence to the contrary. That is, in a SEM model we are interested in maintaining the null hypothesis. This is a way of proceeding opposite to how it is done when contrasting the significance of a variable in a regression model, in which it is proposed as a null hypothesis that the variable is not significant, and what interests us is to reject that hypothesis, which is done only if there is sufficient empirical evidence for it.

Although a likelihood ratio test based on χ^2 is an interesting starting point to assess the overall fit of a model, the truth is that it poses many problems, since in small samples it may not detect differences between H_0 and H_1 , and with large samples the opposite may occur, that very small differences cause the null hypothesis to be ruled out (Kline, 2016; Uriel & Aldás, 2005; West et al., 2023). Consequently, it is a test that must be used very carefully.

As an alternative to the χ^2 tests, and trying to solve its deficiencies, many measures of global adjustment of the model have been proposed, generally called indices or averages or approximate statistics, or ad-hoc (Beaujean, 2014; Kline, 2016; Uriel & Aldás, 2005; West et al., 2023). The most relevant and used are described below (although there are dozens of them that will not be considered here -see for example Beaujean (2014) or Whittaker & Schumacker (2022)

- CFI (Comparative Fit Index), proposed by Bentler (1990). It is an incremental adjustment index, which measures the improvement of the proposed model with respect to a simpler model that is taken as a reference and that is the "independent", or "null" model, in which it is assumed that there is no relationship between the variables of the model, with which the covariance between them is zero. Since χ^2_{indep} and df_{indep} are the values of χ^2 and the degrees of freedom of the independent model, and χ^2_{model} model and df_{model} those of the proposed model, the CFI is defined as:

$$CFI = 1 - \frac{\max(\chi^2_{model} - df_{model}, 0)}{\max(\chi^2_{indep} - df_{indep}, \chi^2_{model} - df_{model}, 0)}$$

The CFI takes values between 0 and 1, with 1 being the best result (best fit), which is obtained, essentially, when the value of χ^2_{model} is small enough. CFI values above 0.9 are typically considered to indicate a good fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Kline, 2016; Whittaker & Schumacker, 2022).

- SRMR (Standardized Root Mean-Square Residual), this is the standard version of the RMR index, which is essentially an average of the residual covariances, the differences between the observed empirical covariances (S_{ikh} elements of the S matrix) and the covariances estimated according to the model (σ_{ij} elements of the Σ matrix). The RMR has the problem that by using non-standardized values it can adopt values in a range that depends on the scale of measurement of the observable variables, which can be difficult to interpret. Standardizing the RMR (to obtain the SRMR) ultimately means using correlations matrices instead of covariances, resulting in an index that takes values between 0 and 1 and is much easier to interpret. An SRMR value equal to 0 means a perfect fit of the model to the data, while values below 0.10 are usually considered acceptable (Kline, 2016; Whittaker & Schumacker, 2022). SRMR is defined as (Hu & Bentler, 1999):

$$SRMR = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^i \left(\frac{s_{ij} - \sigma_{ij}}{s_{ii} s_{jj}} \right)^2}{\frac{p(p+1)}{2}}}$$

- RMSEA (Root Mean-Square Error of Approximation), proposed by Steiger (1990), is a measure of goodness of fit of the model that takes values between 0 and 1 (although in some cases it may be greater than 1). The adjustment will be better the closer you are to 0. RMSEA is defined as (Hu & Bentler, 1999):

$$RMSEA = \sqrt{\frac{\max(\chi^2_{\text{model}} - df_{\text{model}}, 0)}{(n-1)df_{\text{model}}}}$$

In this expression n is the number of observations. It is generally considered that an RSMEA value < 0.08 means that the model fits the observations reasonably well (Whittaker & Schumacker, 2022). An interesting characteristic of the RMSEA is that its probability distribution is known, which allows estimating confidence intervals for its value (Browne & Cudeck, 1992), with a confidence level typically taken from 90%, and obtaining a p -value for the hypo. null thesis that the RMSEA is below a certain value, typically 10 to 8% (or 5% if you want to increase the power of the test, that is, reduce the probability of a false negative, to accept erroneously that the model fits the data well).

In any case, although all these measures of goodness of global adjustment of the SEM models are useful and widely used, none is without problems, such as their sensitivity to sample size and others, so they should not in any case be valued uncritically but should be seen as one more element along with many others, which contributes to an idea of the quality of the estimated model.

Local goodness-of-fit measures are extraordinarily important, since a model may present a deficient overall adjustment simply because of adjustment problems in a small part of it but be perfectly valid and useful as regards the rest of its elements.

The measures of local adjustment are mainly the residuals of the model and the measures of significance of the estimated coefficients of the model, especially of the coefficients of the structural model that shows the relationships between the latent variables.

The residuals of the model are the differences between the elements of the matrix of covariances between observed variables, matrix S , and the matrix of covariances according to the model, matrix Σ , that is, they are the elements $s_{ij} - \sigma_{ij}$ of the matrix $S - \Sigma$. Large values for these differences will indicate a bad fit (Bollen, 1989), although only a local bad fit, for the affected variables. Logically, values close to zero for these residuals will indicate a good fit (also local).

However, the range of values that can be taken by covariances between variables depends on the scale at which these variables are measured and is not limited to any range of values, making it difficult to assess whether a particular value is sufficiently close to 0 or not. For this reason, standardized waste or, especially, standardized waste is usually used. The normalized residuals are calculated as

$$\frac{s_{ij} - \sigma_{ij}}{\sqrt{\text{var}(s_{ij})}}, \text{ while the standardized residuals will be } \frac{s_{ij} - \sigma_{ij}}{\sqrt{\text{var}(s_{ij} - \sigma_{ij})}}.$$

If the sample is large enough, the values of the standardized residuals can be considered as Wald test statistics that allow to contrast the null hypothesis that $s_{ij} - \sigma_{ij} = 0$. According to this, values for standardized residuals greater than 1.96 (or less than -1,96) would lead to rejecting the equality between the sample correlation and the model-derived correlation with a confidence level of 95%. Normalized residuals are also often considered as *z-test* statistics (Beaujean, 2014; Whittaker & Schumacker, 2022), although they would not be properly so, since their values are smaller than those of standardized residuals (Kline, 2016), so it would be more appropriate to consider that it has a fundamentally descriptive character.

With respect to the significance of the structural model coefficients estimated when fitting the SEM model, it is usual to evaluate it by means of Wald test, in which the estimated value of the coefficient is divided by its standard error, to obtain a statistic, z , which is distributed as a standard normal and allows to contrast the null hypothesis that the coefficient is zero. As usual, this null hypothesis is rejected for a significance level of 5% if $|z| \geq 1.96$.

4. Results

4.1 Introduction

This study intended to investigate the effect of perceived proximity and employee voice in wellbeing when WFH. Additionally, it explored the effect of new variables ESN perceived effectiveness, public social media usage in employee voice activities or the intensity and previous experience WFH. This chapter presents the results of the data analysis for the six stated hypotheses.

The structural equation model is estimated using the lavaan package of R. The package is executed by means of commands and accepts as input a text file containing a description of the model to be estimated using a syntax that allows us to specify the measurement model (e.g., the relationships of the indicators with their respective latent variables) and the structural model (the relationships between latent variables, which are the ones we are particularly interested in). This text file describing the model analyzed is shown in Annex III.

4.1.1 Exploratory analysis

With the collected data, we performed exploratory analysis of antecedents of willingness to telework. The unprecedented situation derived from the health crisis-induced period is an opportunity to explore as many variables as possible given the indicators included in the survey. In this additional study we assessed previous experience WFH and telework intensity as antecedents of willingness to telework. We also investigated the self-reported productivity indicator and found that as people spend more time WFH, they feel more productive. 84% of the participants that had worked from home for over 23 months would like to maintain this formula permanently. Our study contradicts the belief of adverse long-term effects of telecommuting such as reduced productivity, arising feelings of isolation or reduced commitment to the company project.

In a crisis-induced telework period there is need to investigate the effects enforced telework measures has had in employee's outcomes. The participants in our survey were also asked to assess the overall experience WFH. Participants indicated their agreement (from 1=" Strongly Disagree" to 5=" Strongly agree") with seven statements describing different dimensions of the working experience. Some of the statements used were "I feel more productive WFH", "I feel enabled to use the online technology required to perform my job".

Additional analysis on the data collected were done to assess whether the experience WFH and the frequency of days WFH influenced (1) the desirability of teleworkers to continue after the social distancing restrictions, or (2) the self-reported productivity while at telework. To test these new hypothesis, two simple regression models were used, thus considering willingness to telework and self-reported productivity as dependent variables in this additional study (Labrado et al., 2022). Although not significant differences were found in self-reported productivity between men and women in relation to WFH, the former did express more desire to continue WFH than the latter.

The results obtained serve to verify with scientific rigor what seems like a rumor of society to explain why the experience WFH is positive, and employees feel more productive. The autonomy and flexibility gained from WFH may have paid off (Labrado et al., 2022).

4.2 Testing the hypotheses

The measurement model is shown in Figure 9, in which, following the usual convention for representing structural equation models, the indicators are represented by rectangles and the latent variables by circles or ellipses.

The structural equation model is estimated using the lavaan package of R. The package is executed by means of commands and accepts as input a text file containing a description of the model to be estimated using a syntax that allows us to specify the measurement model (e.g., the relationships of the indicators with their respective latent variables) and the structural model (the relationships between latent variables, which are the ones we are particularly interested in). This text file describing the model analyzed is shown in Annex III.

As can be seen in Figure 9, a model with 9 latent variables is proposed: PROXIMITY, ENTERPSNET, COMMUNICATION, IDENTIFICATION, WELLBEING, D_VOICE, I_VOICE, IV_PARTIC and IV_EFFECT.

The latent variable WELLBEING measures wellbeing and its indicators are WELLB_01 to WELLB_18. The latent variable PROXIMITY measures perceived proximity and its indicators are PERC_PROX_01 to PER_PROX_04. The latent variable ENTERPSNET measures the use of internal company social networks, and its indicators are SM_EFFEC_01 to SM_EFFEC_04 and SM_BENEF_01 to SM_EFFEC_05. The latent variable COMMUNICATION measures the intensity of communication with co-workers and its indicators are PP_COMMUN_01 to PP_COMMUN_04. The latent variable IDENTIFICATION measures the degree of identification with co-workers and its indicators are PP_IDENTITY_02, PP_IDENTITY_04 and PP_IDENTITY_05.

The latent variables D_VOICE and I_VOICE measure respectively *****I don't know what*****. The indicators of D_VOICE are D_VOICE_01, D_VOICE_03, D_VOICE_04, D_VOICE_05, D_VOICE_06 and D_VOICE_07. I_VOICE is a second-order construct, which is measured by the first order constructs IV_PARTIC and IV_EFFECT. IV_PARTIC measures the degree of online relationship with unions and workers' representatives and its indicators are IV_PARTIC_01, IV_PARTIC_03, IV_PARTIC_04 and IV_PARTIC_05. IV_EFFECT measures the amount of information received about working conditions through various channels, and its indicators are IV_CHANNEL_01 to IV_CHANNEL_09. These two first-order constructs, IV_PARTIC and IV_EFFECT, are auxiliary in nature, and no hypothesis is made about them.

Figure 9 - Measurement model

Source: Own elaboration, extracted from R.

The structural model is shown in Figure 10, which shows by arrows the relationships between the constructs of interest in the model, each of which corresponds to one of the hypotheses proposed.

Figure 10 - Structural model

Source: Own elaboration, extracted from R.

The regression coefficients obtained by estimating the model using the lavaan package are shown in the following table:

Table 8 - Regression coefficients in the Model

Regression Coefficients in the Model					
	Estimate	Std. Err.	z	P(> z)	Standardized Estimate
<u>Regression Slopes</u>					
<u>WELLBEING</u>					
D.VOICE	-0.06*	0.03	-2.37	.018	-0.146
I.VOICE	0.04	0.03	1.69	.090	0.105
PROXIMITY	0.09***	0.02	5.71	.000	0.360
<u>PROXIMITY</u>					
COMMUNICATION	0.48***	0.09	5.11	.000	0.337
IDENTIFICATION	0.47***	0.13	3.61	.000	0.232
ENTERPSNET	0.21**	0.07	2.96	.003	0.181

*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001

The table shows the estimated value of each coefficient (Estimate), the standard error for the coefficient (Std. Err.), the quotient between these two values ($\frac{\text{Estimate}}{\text{Std. Err.}}$), called z, since it would be distributed as a standard normal under the null hypothesis that the coefficient is zero, and the p-value ($P(>|z|)$) that is obtained when testing this hypothesis, and which allows us to discard it, so that the coefficient would be significantly different from zero, if the p-value is sufficiently small (conventionally, less than 0.05).

The estimated values of the coefficients of the structural model can also be seen in Figure 11, in which the statistically significant effects are marked with a red arrow:

Figure 11 - Coefficients of the Structural Model

Source: Own elaboration, extracted from R.

A final column has been added to the table with the values of the standardized regression coefficients (Standardized Estimate). These coefficients show the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable measured in standard deviations, e.g., they indicate, for a one standard deviation change in the value of the independent variable, the change in value of the dependent variable measured in standard deviations. These coefficients make it easier to compare the intensity of the effect of each independent variable, since by using them the effect of the scale on which each of them is measured is eliminated, so that it can be considered that at least approximately twice as large a coefficient has twice the effect on the dependent variable.

As can be seen in the table, the effect of PROXIMITY on WELLBEING is positive and statistically highly significant (with a p-value of less than), which confirms our hypothesis H4. However, the effect of I_VOICE on WELLBEING, although positive, is not statistically significant at a confidence level of 95%, but it would be significant at a level of 90% since the p-value (0.09) is below. It can then be assumed that there is a marginally significant effect of I_VOICE on WELLBEING. As for the effect of D_VOICE on WELLBEING, although it is statistically significant at 95% (with a p-value of less than), the sign of the coefficient is surprisingly negative, opposite to that posited in our hypothesis H5. There would be then, according to the result obtained, a negative association between D_VOICE and WELLBEING, frequent participation in public social media with work-related issues would be associated with a lower level of wellbeing.

Regarding the effect of ENTERPSNET, COMMUNICATION and IDENTIFICATION on PROXIMITY, all of them are statistically highly significant and with positive coefficients, which would confirm our hypotheses H1, H2, H3, correspondingly. As for the magnitude of the effects on PROXIMITY of each of the variables, it can be seen that, as shown by the standardized coefficients in the last column of the table, the greatest effect would correspond to COMMUNICATION, and this effect would be approximately 40% greater than that of IDENTIFICATION and almost double that of ENTERPSNET (the magnitudes of these effects being understood as changes in the values of the variables measured in standard deviations, as explained above).

The basic measures of overall model fit are presented in the following table:

Table 9 - Overall Model Fit measures

Model	χ^2	<i>df</i>	χ^2/df	<i>p</i>	CFI	RMSEA	SRMR
Model 1	4,463.24	1,521	2.93	< .001	0.76	0.06	0.07
Ideal Value^a	—	—	< 2 or 3	> .05	≥ .95	< .06-.08	≤ .08

Source: Own elaboration. As proposed by Schreiber et al. (2006).

The overall fit of the model is moderate. On the one hand, the value of the statistic is very high, which would reject the null hypothesis that the model is valid. However, as indicated, this test is sensitive to sample size and tends to reject the null hypothesis except for small samples, so it should be used with caution and cannot be considered as the definitive criterion for assessing the fit of a model. With respect to other means of model fit, the CFI has a value of, which is low, since it should be greater than or, but the RMSEA and SRMR do have values that indicate that the overall model fit is not poor.

Other relevant information, e.g., estimated values for factor loadings and covariances, can be obtained with the summary function of the lavaan package and is provided in Annex IV.

5. Discussion

In the preceding chapter, the presentation and analysis of data have been presented. This *Discussion* chapter consists of a summary of the study, discussion of the findings, implications for practice and recommendations for further research. Once the findings are discussed, the purpose of the latter sections is to expand upon the concepts studied in this project. Conclusions from the findings are discussed in relation with good telework management practice. The possible influence in HRM practice, and presentation of suggestions for further research on successful implementation of remote work practices will also be provided. Finally, a synthesizing statement is formulated to capture the substance of what has been presented.

5.1 Summary of the study

This thesis studies how perceived proximity with coworkers, and employee voice, influence the affective wellbeing of teleworkers. The study included one main research question: *What is the impact of perceived proximity and employee voice in wellbeing under intense telework contexts?* To answer this research question two research perspectives will be applied:

- (1) The Perceived Proximity perspective (Wilson et al., 2008), where the potential of rich ICT-based interactions to build a sense of closeness and, interestingly, wellbeing, has been assessed.
- (2) The employee voice perspective, where online forms of voice expression has been assessed in its ability to influence employee wellbeing through the provision of social support in the adoption of WFH practices.

Using a 2021 dataset of 542 professionals, the model includes the analysis of constructs such as perceived proximity or employee voice to assess the results of the outcome variable (affective wellbeing). Additionally, the role of technology to build social presence will be thoroughly examined. Structural equation modeling was applied to analyze the results.

These research perspectives lead to the formulation of the following 5 hypotheses: 1) H1: The use of ESNs positively influences perceived proximity; 2) H2: Workmate communications positively influences perceived proximity; 3) H3: Workmate identification in telework environments positively influences perceived proximity; 4) H4: Perceived proximity positively influences affective wellbeing; 5) H5: Employee direct voice on public social media positively influences affective wellbeing; 6) H6: Employee indirect voice positively influences affective wellbeing. All hypotheses were quantitatively tested.

Our findings show that the use of ESNs, workmate communication and workmate identity are significant antecedents of perceived proximity. At the same time, perceived proximity has a significant and positive impact on affective wellbeing. This means that teleworkers who feel symbolically close to a distant coworker will improve his/her wellbeing at work. Our hypothesis on direct voice was rejected, the results reveal a negative relation between direct voice on public social media and affective wellbeing. We did not find support for the idea that telework-related indirect voice mechanisms have a positive effect in the wellbeing of those regularly WFH.

The findings from this study reveal the need to re-design telework conditions in a post-pandemic scenario (Carillo et al., 2021). The dysfunctional effects of WFH have been extensively studied (Gajendran and Harrison, 2007). Remote communication researchers have warned of the dangers of workplace isolation highlighting the importance of social relations (Adamovic, 2022; Collins et al.,

2016a; Ruiller et al., 2019). We have attempted to go a step further broadening the framework of the “*far-but-close*” paradox in a number of ways: (1) first we examined the perceived proximity construct with a large data sample of experienced teleworkers, (2) we found a new antecedent of perceived proximity, the effective use of ESNs, (3) lastly we discovered that the *far-but-close* paradox (Wilson et al., 2008) has positive effect in the affective state of teleworkers. We are, thus, confident to say the *far-but-close* paradox (Wilson et al., 2008) can be sustained in future forms of remote/ hybrid work through frequent, meaningful interactions between coworkers.

Additional aspects of the practice of telework arise from the exploratory analysis of the results. The first is that the more teleworkers work remotely, the more they want to continue WFH. This is true not only for telework longevity (measured in the number of months the respondents have worked from home) but also in the intensity of telework (measured in the number of days the respondents work-from-home in a month). Experience and frequency allow to develop routines and rituals to handle telework demands. Such experience can have a positive influence in the perception of telework that determine the preference to telework.

The second is that the accumulated experience of WFH as well as intensive telework have a positive effect in the productivity reported by the respondents. The adjustment of the arrangements of the workplace, reduced interruptions from ICT-based work communications (Golden & Veiga, 2005), or increased autonomy (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007), among others, are reasons that can help explain the positive association telework longevity and intensity have shown a higher level of self-reported productivity.

The topic of this thesis is of considerable importance to firms’ competitive advantage (Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021; Neirotti et al., 2017). Telework increases job performance (Blahopoulou et al., 2022), but only if it results in the expected positive outcomes. The first results from this thesis were published in International Journal of Manpower under the article “A time after time effect in telework: an explanation of willingness to telework and self-reported productivity”.

5.2 Discussion of the findings

The goal of this thesis is to assess three variables (perceived proximity, direct employee voice, indirect employee voice) in their ability to influence the affective wellbeing of teleworkers. In the advent of hybrid forms of work, there is a need to design appropriate telework conditions for occupational wellbeing (Stempel & Siestrup, 2022). Wellbeing at work is increasingly gaining attention from researchers and practitioners to design successful future work environments (Blahopoulou et al., 2022; Mendonça et al., 2022; Niebuhr et al., 2022). Wellbeing researchers reinforce the idea work arrangements should be understood through the lens of working relationships (Golden, 2006). We follow this approach questioning whether our independent variables are per se a source of affective wellbeing. This approach represents a step forward in telework research, contributing to previous design where the focal lens was placed in direct outcomes of WFH. In this thesis we have examined coworker perceived proximity and voice mechanisms as potential antecedents of affective wellbeing. Previous knowledge on the effect of telework in social relations agree on the risk of professional and social isolation in WFH (Adamovic, 2022; Becker & Huselid, 2006; Blahopoulou et al., 2022; Collins et al., 2016b; Ruiller et al., 2019; Stempel & Siestrup, 2022).

There is an urgent need to find ways to overcome this threat (Durakovic et al., 2023). Thus, in this thesis we attempt to contribute to this gap through the examination of our hypotheses using a new large-scale primary dataset from experienced teleworkers.

This section discusses the implications of the findings for each of six research questions and the structural model created.

5.2.1 Hypothesis 1: ESN usage → Perceived Proximity

The finding resulting from research question one indicates a positive and causal relationship between the ESN use and perceived proximity with a coworker (H1 accepted). In other words, the effective use of ESNs like MS Yammer, or Oracle, for example, influence the feelings of closeness with a fellow coworker under telework settings. This finding is in line with the general belief that ESNs are intended to promote peer-to-peer engagement (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020). This result extends previous knowledge that ESNs provide for higher social presence than other organizational ICT platforms like blogs or collaborative projects. The visibility of messages being posted, the reactions from users and customizable notifications are system features through which social presence is generated. (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Through ESNs, coworkers connect and “follow” other workmates with whom they share similarities. In some cases, this bonding is followed on conversations outside of working hours (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020). According to our data, this communication visibility may have turned into a useful way to feel proximal to a distant workmate.

The benefits of ESNs usage in telework environments help prevent isolation WFH. H1 findings may indicate that ESNs become a preferred platform for teleworkers to find what other coworkers have to say or comment, over other ICT options such as blogs, content portal, ... (Leonardi et al., 2010). Although early results from crisis induced WFH indicate a hard stop of networking activities beyond the boundaries of existing close ties (Yang et al., 2022), the results from our data are indicative that experienced teleworkers find in ESN usage a platform in which to expand and connect with the wider organization, building perceived proximity.

Perceived proximity theorists (Wilson et al., 2008) noted that the density of the company’s network structure is favorable to subjective proximity. The network dimension in the perceived proximity framework has been scarcely researched. In this sense, the implementation of company-wide ESNs where density of the network is reachable by any employee who can freely engage in meaningful connections with workmates, seems like wind in the sails of successful WFH experiences. In the past, firms have often failed to get the theoretical benefits expected from ESN adoption. Users did not find value in ESNs due to fear of being visibly exposed in the organization. To the best of our knowledge there is only one study that has empirically examined the relation between ESN use and perceived proximity, van Zoonen et al. (2021). Van Zoonen et al. (2021a) data was collected prior to Covid-19 outbreak. Their empirical results showed that having perceived proximity with a workmate influenced the use of ESN between the dyad. This finding implies that messages posted by coworkers with whom one feels close to are more visible than those from not-so-close coworkers; meaning that perceived proximity had causal priority over the technical feature of the platform. Van Zoonen and his team instrumentalized ESN use on a scale of frequency of daily interactions with the platform. The results from H1 add to this finding through the examination of the perceived effectiveness of ESNs to build perceived proximity. Acceptance of H1 indicates that teleworkers have a found in ESN’s communication visibility a valuable tool to connect with workmates, discover new workmates, etc.

Contrary to findings from pre-pandemic telework (van Zoonen et al., 2021a), ESN is now a valuable platform that builds proximity with coworkers. This result may be another example of how forced telework challenges previous knowledge of telework outcomes (Becker et al., 2022; Kitagawa et al., 2021); where perceived proximity has shifted from being an antecedent to being a consequence of ESN usage.

It is possible to say that the use of ESNs supports building a sense of perceived proximity with a distant coworker. This seems especially interesting for the *far-but-close* paradox. The grounding belief that frequent communication and strong identity contributed to feeling close to a distant coworker (Wilson et al., 2008), is now proven applicable to participation in social networks within the firms. Apparently, the high visibility of communication paved the way to perceiving a distant other as proximal. The result from our data notes the consideration that the perceived effectiveness of ESN usage (e.g., finding new coworkers with whom one shares similarities, connecting with coworkers) new is a key contributing factor in the perceived proximity framework. The founding authors of Perceived Proximity theory (Wilson et al., 2008) posited that dense professional networks, referring to those where “*all team members are connected by strong relationships*” (Wilson et al., 2008: p.5), encourage communication, which, in turn, fosters perceived proximity. Our result highlights a nuanced approach to how professional networks improve perceived proximity; leaving aside the condition of network density (the fact all team members have good relationships) the perceived usefulness of the existing ESN tools is a direct antecedent of perceived proximity with a coworker. We assume those teleworkers who find in ESN a valuable tool will make daily use of it to communicate with coworkers, which, in turn, predicts perceived proximity. Future research on ESN use should consider our finding when deciding the appropriate instrument to collect data. Our finding suggests a new approach to ESN should be considered to examine the value perceived, as opposed to frequency of use, for example.

This finding shows organizational ICT implementation have a crucial role in achieving desired organizational outcomes (e.g., increased peer-to-peer engagement, increased collaboration, etc). Findings from H1 reflect the idea that home-based teleworkers value ESNs as a tool to engage with distant others, whether these are coworkers, company management or workers’ representatives. They have found in ESN an option to remotely build new social ties with whom they have similarities. When this value is perceived, perceived proximity with coworkers is increased. During the pandemic telework time the social context of the workplace has radically changed. Most workers have drastically reduced the activities to expand their network ties, and organizations seem to have not found the way to reproduce informal interventions online (Yang & Lin, 2022). After Covid-19 WFH experiment, effective implementation of ESN platforms are powerful tools to engage with fellow workers in an informal and collective manner (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020).

ESNs are an appropriate platform for coworkers to engage with other peers with similar interests. Despite the favorable technical features of the platform, there are certain inhibitors that may prevent employees to accept the technology and embrace its adoption. First, the quality of information exchanged through the platform must be valued by the users. Former data evidenced employees often perceived the platform as a vehicle for self-promotion or employee surveillance (Laumer et al., 2017)). When this happens there is a loss of quality in the social interactions held through ESNs. Second, management can use the tool to monitor employees. This would be perceived by employees as a loss of power and privacy. These words of caution should be taken into consideration when designing the implementation strategy of the platform and ensure coworkers can open search and find other coworkers in the firm’s social network. The result from this hypothesis (H1) may be a sign of

hope for future workplace arrangements. With effective ESN use comes feelings of being close to distant coworkers, directly mitigating one of the biggest drawbacks of telework, isolation. Practitioners can invest in carefully design and monitor communication exchanges through ESNs to ensure the expected value is generated and, thus, healthy social support structures are created.

5.2.2 Hypothesis 2: Workmate communication → Perceived Proximity

Results from the analysis indicate a positive and significant relationship between workmate communications and perceived proximity with coworkers (H2 supported). In other words, the more you communicate with a fellow coworker the more likely you are to feel psychologically close to that person. Previous studies on psychological distance at work note the favorable effect communication frequency has on feelings of closeness amongst teammates (Cha et al., 2014; Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020; O’Leary et al., 2014b). Bonding remotely requires more effort (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020), the lack of face-to-face communications implies a loss of symbolic meaning that needs to be re-conveyed through ICT-based interactions (Davis & Cates, 2013). Earlier studies note the importance of communication media for workmates to connect and bond, with videoconference use, for example, providing higher cohesion than lower media usage (e.g., email or instant messaging) (Hambley et al., 2007). The results from our data (H2) though, do not reflect such media richness causal priority and are more in line with alternative views as the level interactivity (Burgoon et al., 2002) or even a discretionary use of technology that best suits each situation (Fonner & Roloff, 2012). Focus on hard characteristics of technology may not be suitable for today’s digitized workplace (Chang & Lee, 2021). We infer that through the experience gained WFH as results to Covid-19, teleworkers have managed to find symbolic value across a range of media used in workmate communication. In other words, it’s not the media you use but how often one maintains contact with the dyad and how o symbolic value is found in each human interaction. Remote employees are known to proactively select the choice of media that best suits their need in each situation (Leonardi et al., 2010). Such effective and frequent use of technology communications can result in close exchanges with coworkers which, in turn, reduce perceived distance (Robert, 2016). Our finding is relevant to the design of future workplaces, where virtual collaborations becoming the new norm. Although a mix of face-to-face and virtual communications is preferred (Ruiller et al., 2019), the finding from our study confirms frequent workmate communications during telework builds subjective proximity with a distant other (O’Leary et al., 2014b). Today’s companies have empowered their organizational ICTs for better communication, we suggest that focus of future research should be on how to make good use of communication technology to recover symbolic meaning lost by the lack of face-to-face (Yang & Lin, 2022).

Studies undertaken during Covid-19 forced telework advise of the significant decrease in synchronous and rich communication and imply a loss of collaboration as results of this (Yang et al., 2022). In our sample, lower media was also mostly used by participants (e.g., more than half of respondents used email and/or instant messaging more than once a day); whereas reliance on rich media (videoconference calls) was used daily in 26,01% of the cases. 28,41% of respondents attended non-video online meetings at least once a day. Figure 16, in Annex I, visually represents the count of frequency of use per media assessed. In this thesis we examined the outcome of workmate communication, perceived proximity. Acceptance of H2 implies it cannot be concluded that loss of rich media has a negatively impact on collaboration. On the contrary, one could anticipate enhanced

coworker support and collaboration results from increased proximity (Cha et al., 2014; Collins et al., 2016b). In sum, what initially can be found quite despairing, the loss of synchronic or rich media communication in favor of asynchronous or lower media ones, may not be so daunting after all. Asynchronous communications can bring clarity and avoid the presence of bias in the communication (Daft & Lengel, 1986). The results from H2 confirm the frequent, meaningful communications, independent from technology characteristics, have a positive and significant effect on perceived proximity. Asynchronous communications, for example, like email, allow the user to take time to build a response, which leads to focus and enhanced quality of the exchange (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). Instant messaging has also been found relevant to maintain bond between colleagues at remote work. Both email and instant messaging are technologies well known by the users, thus ensuring a permanent bond is kept between team members (Ruiller et al., 2019). At the time of our study, less than 5% of participants held daily face-to-face contacts, which gives strength to the belief that geographically distant relationships can be felt as close as collocated ones (*far-but-close* paradox). The focus then may not be placed in the hard characteristics of the communication channel used but in the discretionary choice of experienced teleworkers (Leonardi et al., 2010).

The finding from H2 contributes to current knowledge of remote communications by validation of the *far-but-close* paradox in a new sample of experienced teleworkers, after Covid-19 forced telework. Wilson et al. (2008) paradox arises from open-source software development teams which are known to have a strong “hacker” identity. Open-source project teams engage thousands of developers across the globe to produce successful and reliable products such as Linux Operating System or Apache Web server, providing access to IT advancements to many public and private entities at no cost. The data collected in our study is representative of a different population, that is, a cross-sectional sample of European knowledge workers experienced WFH, after Covid-19 outburst. The result from H2 validates it is possible, through workmate communication to build a sense of proximity with distant coworkers. Conclusions from remote work researchers are in line with our finding from H2. Morrison-Smith and Ruiz (2020), for example, found behaviors of self-disclosure built close relationships within virtual team members. In work-from-home, such self-disclosure is manifested through remote communications. According to Liu et al. (2021) teleworkers who actively engaged in communications with others benefited from increased coworker support, compared with those that remain silent at work. Thus, it is possible to be far and yet feel close to your workmate while WFH. We believe this finding is of relevance to practitioners concerned about work relationships in the future of work. The threat of professional and social isolation from the organization is important in telework contexts (Spilker & Breaugh, 2021; Wang et al., 2020b), where collaboration and coworker support act as critical job resource (Seinsche et al., 2022). Our finding shows communications in the remote workplace are valuable to teleworkers, through perceived proximity, thus mitigating the risk of isolation. In other words, for employers considering the adoption of effective telework environments, should play close attention to if and how perceived proximity is created among coworkers as results of work-related interpersonal relations.

5.2.3 Hypothesis 3: Workmate identification → Perceived Proximity

The research question assessed the impact of workmate shared identity on perceived proximity. A contrast testing this prediction produced a positive significance correlation (H3 supported). In other words, the more shared identity with a fellow coworker the closer you may feel to that person. These

results are in line with the highly symbolic value attributed to identity on several theories, namely CLT (Trope & Liberman, 2010), Social Identity (Ashforth & Mael, 1989), or Perceived Proximity (Wilson et al., 2008). This symbolism comes from sharing of personal information, demonstrating one's values, hobbies, commitment to work or one's dependability (O'Leary et al., 2014b). Marlow and Dabbish (2012) revealed similar results in globally distributed teams; interestingly, in this case shared identity was actioned through online photo sharing amongst coworkers. The enhanced contextual information provided by the photos allowed for perceived similarities to be found between members of the group, which resulted in reduced psychological distance. In our data the similarities in commitment to work and values were found most relevant to perceived proximity. Age and gender did not significantly affect bonding between participant dyads. This may be indicative that, under regular telework situations, employees feel closer to those with whom they share similar levels of commitment to work, or values, regardless of their age and gender. Being away from the central office can create feelings of insecurity or fear of unequal treatment in the workplace (Latorre et al., 2016). Managers often mistrust their employees WFH (Kaplan et al., 2018). Thus, being engaged with likeminded people in terms of commitment to work may allow dyads to become closer around common ground in topics like job satisfaction (Brinsfield, 2013), career ambition (Beauregard et al., 2013), access to promotion or salary raise (Golden & Eddleston, 2020), or simply the willingness to continue WFH (Thompson et al., 2022), which in turn makes one feel close to the other.

Other theoretical lenses sustain our finding from H3 and the idea of a positive correlation between shared identity and psychological distance. In Social Identity theory (Ashforth & Mael, 1989), for example, social identification is based on a sense of belonging to the same social category. Under this view, once a shared identity is in place, the dyad would benefit from default sense of bonding which manifest, for example, in default positive attributions to one another. On another instance, CLT states that psychological distance is a mental representation of physically distant people and situations (Fujita et al., 2006). According to CLT, mental representations of a geographically distant workmate refer to the intrinsic characteristic of the other, such as values or beliefs (Trope & Liberman, 2010), in line with our finding from H3. The results from H3 contributes to academic knowledge validating that experienced teleworker in today's digitized world feel closer to workmates with whom they share similarities on values or commitment to work. This is true even in the case of missing "hard" data or invisible behaviors (Ruiller et al., 2019). Shared identity is the "glue" that fixes the psychological bond. This is mostly valuable for practitioners designing collaborative workplace settings. Paying attention to identity building interventions must be an integral part of post-Covid-19 organizational design.

The regular adoption of telework gives birth to a new social paradigm (Brunelle & Fortin, 2021) in the workplace, where contextual settings need to be provided for workmates to interact and engage with each other. In this sense, organizational ICTs and usage procedures that allow identity building processes become much more relevant in the future of remote work. The findings from this thesis (H2 and H3) contribute to this line of thought confirming it is possible to feel closely connected with distant coworkers while WFH. Experienced teleworkers find in workmate communication and identification valuable antecedents of perceived proximity. Workmate communication and identification are closely intertwined in the process of building perceived proximity (Ruiller et al., 2019). In this sense, the more workmates identify and communicate with each other, the closer they will feel and the more positive relations they will build. The design of telework conditions in a post pandemic world need revisiting (Carillo et al., 2021). Much knowledge is still needed to better understand which practices do management have to create successful social environments where identity can be shared, and fluent close communication is maintained. Specifically, we believe further

studies are needed on the opportunities to build shared identity through the design of informal social events in the workplace, that have been found one of the hardest obstacles to successful adoption of telework (Carillo et al., 2021).

5.2.4 Hypothesis 4: Perceived proximity → Wellbeing

The finding resulting from this research question indicate a positive and significant relationship between perceived proximity and employee wellbeing (H4 supported). In other words, the closer a teleworker symbolically feels to a faraway workmate, the higher the positive impact in his/her affective wellbeing. This result is a novelty in the study of perceived proximity theory. To the best of our knowledge, the mediating effect perceived proximity can have on employee outcomes has not been tested yet. WFH have provided workers with the opportunity to keep remotely in contact with colleagues and benefit from their support; hence it is reasonable to expect that those that best cultivate those relationships will mostly benefit. The acceptance of H4 validates the importance of nurturing remote relationships in the workplace, especially for teleworkers, who are in higher psychological need for relatedness (Golden & Veiga, 2005). Having coworkers with whom one feels close to may contribute to making telework a more positive experience. Some authors have noted the positive effect of coworker connectivity on job satisfaction (Brunelle & Fortin, 2021), but the link between perceived proximity and wellbeing was not explored.

During Covid-19 pandemic, positive telework experiences have protected the wellbeing of work-from-home employees (Blahopoulou et al., 2022). Work relationships are vital to the provision of such positive experiences (Adamovic, 2022). In turn, coworker support and close social exchanges during WFH become a must-have resource for positive telework (Seinsche et al., 2022). The higher the job resources in telework, the higher the wellbeing (Miglioretti et al., 2022). Previous studies from non-crisis induced conditions are also in line with these findings. Charalampous et al. (2019) note social support is determinant to affective wellbeing of teleworkers. In the past, intensification of telework has led to detriments in coworker support, directly damaging wellbeing through emotional exhaustion, but, when teleworkers can rely on workmates with whom they feel close they experience improved affective states (Grant et al., 2013). In other words, perceived proximity and isolation are two sides of the same coin, positively or negatively influencing the affective wellbeing of teleworkers. The results from our finding (H4) contribute to previous knowledge with new evidence that coworker support can exist in intensive, long-term telework and this, in turn, nurtures wellbeing. As seen above, this finding may reveal a new reality is possible in the future of remote work, after Covid-19 experiment, one in which close relationships can be maintained, despite the frequency and longevity in WFH. Our finding from H4 helps explain why teleworkers often show higher job satisfaction than their office-based colleagues. Brunelle and Fortin (2021) evidenced teleworkers have higher need for relatedness than collocated works, thus when they fulfill that need with fruitful distant relationships at work, they feel happier.

This finding has important implications for telework academics. We base our hypothesis (H4) on AET (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996). AET posits daily events at work affect the overall psychological state of employees. We propose to focus on everyday happenings at telework, as opposed to static conditions of work (e.g., schedule, flexibility conditions, salary, ...), to examine if and how these events (chatting with a coworker, attending a meeting, making new contacts on ESN,...), have an effect in the affective state (positive or negative) of the teleworker (Anderson et al., 2015), through

the mediating effect of perceived proximity. Results from H4 confirm that the psychological bonding gained during these events has a positive effect in the affective wellbeing of experienced teleworkers. According to telework literature, we find these events may have helped the employees to cope with usual situations WFH. For example, telework literature refers to lack of organizational visibility (Cooper & Kurland, 2002; van Zoonen et al., 2021a) or reduced accessibility to promotions (Latorre et al., 2016) as results of WFH. We believe stronger coworker support can trigger meaningful conversations in which to discuss, express these concerns. Additionally, WFH can result in higher job ambiguity or uncertainties to perform one's tasks (Perry et al., 2018). This is a source of stress WFH. Teleworkers with stronger coworker support can hold frequent, close conversations with workmates to solve technical doubts and feel better WFH (Liu et al., 2022a). These and other situations are examples of positive events WFH which will, in turn, enhance wellbeing. In our study, the mediating effect perceived proximity has on affective wellbeing (H4 supported) is explained through daily events (e.g., communication, ESN participation, or identify building events). Thus, we conclude the three antecedents of perceived proximity examined in our model are positive WFH events.

Previous studies on the impact of telework on wellbeing before are often inconclusive (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007). Telework researchers have advised to examine distinctive telework variables in search of mediating and moderating factors (Blahopoulou et al., 2022). Much has been investigated to confirm the negative effect of WFH in social isolation in individual and organizational outcomes (Becker et al., 2022; Galanti et al., 2021; Spilker & Breugh, 2021), but little on the positive effect of WFH relatedness in affective wellbeing. Wang et al. (2020b), for example, found social isolation damaged wellbeing, which in turn reduced organizational commitment. Golden and Veiga (2008) found professional isolation reduces job performance and satisfaction. Telework researchers call for deeper understanding of the consequences of coworker relationships in shaping positive experiences WFH. The results from this thesis give light into the mediating role of coworker relationships in employee wellbeing. The research question behind H4 is an attempt to cover this research gap examining the positive causal relationship between perceived proximity and affective wellbeing, in a post-pandemic world. The experience gained during crisis-induced telework may have highlighted the importance of close coworker relationships, especially during long periods of time where many coworkers were also WFH. This finding comes at a time where a paradigm shift has been raised towards a coexistence of employee psychological wellbeing and organizational performance (Loon et al., 2019). The positive and significant relationship found between perceived proximity and wellbeing, alongside the advancement in telework research, provide new avenues for applicable research on the design of future remote workplace practices.

Previous studies using the Connectivity paradox lens advise on the detrimental effect too much connectivity can have on the benefits of telework (Leonardi et al. 2010; Fonner and Roloff, 2012). The acceptance of H4 extends previous knowledge on connectivity during work-from-home arrangements by shifting the focus from communication frequency to perceived distance. The paradoxical effects of communication frequency seem to disappear when perceived proximity is the mediating variable. In other words, the number of interactions and which channels they are held becomes irrelevant to assess the benefits of telework. Finally, the acceptance of H4 is a novelty in the research of psychological distance. Perceived proximity has first been used as independent variable and confirmed its value as antecedent factor of a crucial employee outcome in organizational research, the wellbeing of those employees WFH. This finding extends the current knowledge on the effects of psychological distance and builds upon perceived proximity limited empirical data evaluating the effect of perceived proximity when at telework.

The finding from H4 is mostly relevant for practitioners. It reveals a new antecedent to positive telework experiences. Past knowledge is assertive of conditions such as self-efficacy training, development of video or telepresence solutions or the supportive role of managers as antecedents of telework satisfaction (Allen et al., 2015). Human Resource Managers inclined to pursue employee wellbeing can learn from the results of this thesis new ways to evoke positive affect, or eliminate negative affect, in the telework settings. The Covid-19 telework experience has left a generation of skilled WFH workers. The data collected in this thesis represents a population of experienced teleworkers (75,4% of respondents stated having more than 12 months of experience). 12 months has been defined the threshold for teams to effectively operate in remote contexts (Ortiz De Guinea et al., 2012). Experienced teleworkers show better abilities to socially interact with their peers over digital means, compared with telework newcomers (Stempel & Siestrup, 2022). Thus, the experienced gained during Covid-19 experiment by most knowledge workers across the globe resets the baseline for future workplace designs.

5.2.5 Hypothesis 5: Employee direct voice → Wellbeing

We predicted employee direct voice on public social media would have a positive effect on teleworkers affective wellbeing. We assumed that teleworkers sharing their opinions, suggestions, ideas about work conditions on public social media (e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter, ...) would improve their affective state, through an increased sense of being heard (Burriss et al., 2013). A contrast testing this prediction found a significant negative correlation between the variables (H5 rejected). Against odds, our finding resulted in this direct voice mechanisms negatively affecting the wellbeing of those WFH. Past research has found the provision of internal channels for direct voice expression (such as emails, face-to-face meetings) effective to motivate employees and increased their job satisfaction (Holland et al., 2011). The sentiment of being heard has been associated with the source of such positive attitude (Burriss et al., 2013). Apparently, being active on public social media with work related topics had a negative effect in teleworkers' affective wellbeing. The use of open social media, which has no relation with company management, to express one's voice may have not triggered the perception of being heard. Our finding suggests nuanced distinctions on previous knowledge may be needed to fully understand the implications of direct voice expression over new societal communication tools.

Little is yet known about the effect of public social media for voice expression during remote work. Houghton and Hodder (2021), for example found Unions had difficulties building the right engagement with their members using Twitter public social media platform. In this study the public social media platform seemed an effective one-way communication channel (e.g., share information about campaigns or strikes) but not to engage in conversations or taking action (e.g., recruit new members). Other public social media platforms were not examined in this study. Thus, current knowledge of online voice efficacy in WFH settings remains ambiguous (Uribetxebarria et al., 2021).

Feeling heard by management has been flagged formative to positive attitudes (e.g., satisfaction) derived from direct voice expression (Burriss et al., 2013). However, little is yet known about our category of voice expression: employee interactions through social media posting (Budd, 2014), more specifically public social media. Maybe expressing one's voice over such public channels fails to provide the sense of being heard. Also, work-related social media use may lack authenticity (Laumer et al., 2017). The visibility of social media communications raises concerns among employees about being exposed in the outline world. Inhibition of expected positive outcomes and

turning into negative ones may also be related with the threat of reputational damage from posting about work-related voice matters (Vu & Fan, 2022). In line with this idea, Martin et al., (2015a) suggest managers should honestly encourage the use of social media to channel voice for it to be effective. This honest encouragement may build a sense that management will be listening. Nonetheless, further research is needed to fully understand if and under which contextual settings social media can enact fruitful expression of voice.

Voice has been extensively associated with being a consequence of dissatisfaction (Silverman et al., 2013). If this was the case of teleworkers expressing their voice on public social media, then the relation with negative affect can be expected. Our finding from H5 seem in line with Abdulgalimov et al. (2020) idea that for voice expression to result in wellbeing improvements, anonymity of voicers must be guaranteed. We instrumentalized direct voice in the use of public social media platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, Here again, the debate on social media use for work-related topics remains open. On one side anyone can freely express their voice while, on the other the conversation may lack authenticity, with individuals pushing their own agendas (Barnes et al., 2019).

When asked about telework adoption measures being included in their collective agreements only 6,8% of participants confirmed these were included. Given the low level of establishment a direct expression of one's voice over telework adoption matters seem viable to channel concerns, issues, or suggestions WFH. In this context, our finding can open new avenues for research: (1) Are voice effects distinct in work-from-home arrangements? The effect of online voice expression in employee wellbeing remains ambiguous (Holland et al., 2016). Our finding suggests a negative correlation with wellbeing. Reasons behind our findings may be found in the perception of power distance in telework arrangements. Voice is known to be related with power distance (Huang et al., 2005); this explains, for example why the implications of voice vary across nationalities (2) Is power distance impacted by telework? If so, what's its implication with voicing on public social media? Fear of repercussions can be more prevalent in WFH (Wilkinson et al., 2018); in this sense voicers WFH may experience a deterioration of their affective state (less positive or presence of negative affect). Lastly, voice is a resource consuming activity. Increased job demands in WFH leaves less time to voice (Liu et al., 2022a). According to our results, those employing their time to express voice over public social media endangered their affective wellbeing; (3) What is the source of negative affect (or less positive one) in doing so? In public social media anyone can react to those voice posts (like/dislike, comment, forward, ...); are these random and uncontrolled by management reactions somewhat related with the impact on wellbeing?

In sum, direct voice expression through social media is a two-sided sword. For once it can be an untapped resource of employer branding whilst, if negative, it can be transformed into a "bomb" exploding in the sea of internet, with devastating impact on the firm's reputation (Miles and Mangold, 2014). In this sense, if expressed through internal social media it seems to be more inductive to produce happiness and positive emotions at work (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020). Our result from H5 raises a flag on the use of public social media. Since the expression of voice on public social media is not dependent on technology provided by the employer, our finding, as well as further contextual investigations as results of it, becomes crucially relevant for practitioners. The finding from H5 may have open Pandora's box for real damage to their employees' affective wellbeing.

5.2.6 Hypothesis 6: Employee indirect voice → Wellbeing

We predicted employee indirect voice would have a positive effect on teleworkers affective wellbeing. Our result did not support H6. Indirect voice mechanisms did not directly affect the wellbeing of teleworkers. At the time of our study, few companies had established collective agreements regarding telework policies (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020). In this sense, our finding is in line with Della Torre (2019) study which asserts that for employee voice to generate positive outcomes the Unions should be involved in the solution of problems or negotiations of changing work conditions.

According to our data, the representation of affiliated employees is trivial ($n=4$), far below Spain's 12,7% membership rate (ILOSTAT, 2022). 12,9% of participants chose not to express their affiliative status ($n=70$). Such low response rate suggests 1) the lack of awareness on telework regulation topics, or 2) the high sensitivity to respond to Union-related topics. Either way, such low representativeness may explain the result of our hypothesis. On the other hand, the number participants which confirm telework regulation was part of collective bargaining in their company ($n=37$) was scarce. At the time of this study 64,7% ($n=351$) of respondents reveal telework adoption was either not regulated ($n=147$), did not know ($n=59$) or decided not to answer this question ($n=145$). The data collected is indicative of an immature state of telework collective agreements, in which Unions or worker councils will inhibit any attempt to initiate the social process of voice (Gillet et al., 2012). In sum, results from H6 did not meet our expectation. Some of the reasons that may explain these results are 1) irrelevant representation of participant companies with telework collective agreements, 2) Union and worker councils' efforts over telework adoption topics have not been visible or perceived valuable during the pandemic WFH period.

5.3 Contributions of the research

The first theoretical motivation of this thesis is to provide greater clarity on the role social relations can play in building telework experiences indicative of positive emotions at work. In this respect, this thesis has analyzed the role of coworker *perceived proximity* (Wilson et al., 2008) and *employee voice* (Barnes et al., 2019) in shaping telework experiences, all under an up-to-date workplace context. On one hand, the data was collected at a singular time resulting in a large cross-industry sample where a large proportion of respondents ($n=407$) were long experienced WFH (more than 13 months). On the other, the independent variables of the study have been examined applying organizational ICTs available in most large organizations today (e.g., ESNs, social media). This dissertation attempts to contribute to literature broadening the knowledge of what makes successful telework experiences. The findings from this thesis, probably influenced by Covid-19 telework experiment (Carillo et al., 2021) show that close relationships between distant workers are possible. When that happens, teleworker's wellbeing is improved. Previous studies have noted that telework intensity may deteriorate communication quality and happiness at work. Our study takes a more nuanced view of the outcomes of telework. The topic of this thesis answers calls from previous telework researchers (Bailey & Kurland, 2002; Fonner & Roloff, 2012; Golden, 2006).

The dependent variable of this thesis (affective wellbeing) is of crucial relevancy for future research and practice. Employee wellbeing is positively related with business performance (Baptiste, 2008). Workers who experience positive emotions at work are more inclined to reciprocate by being productive (Blau, 1964). The relationship between employee wellbeing and organization performance has been often labeled as the Holy grail of organizational research (Wright et al., 2007). Previous studies have noted that WFH improves teleworkers' wellbeing (Anderson et al., 2015), but little is yet

known about its antecedents. This thesis contributes to this body of literature signposting a new significant antecedent of wellbeing at telework, perceived proximity. In this thesis we instrumentalize the dependent variable with a contrasted psychological wellbeing scale (Warr, 1990), a scale of overall psychological health, off and on the job, in contrast to other studies using simpler measures, such as job satisfaction, which exclusively assesses one's job (Locke, 1976). Although job satisfaction is a simple instrument of wide interest (Blahopoulou et al., 2022) its correlation with business outcomes (e.g., job performance) remains moderate (Judge & Klingler, 2008). In sum, the fact that job performance is best predicted by psychologically wellbeing of the employees provides a solid ground for the significant causal effect we found perceived proximity has on psychological wellbeing (H4 supported).

We contribute to the *far-but-close* paradox (Wilson et al., 2008) in two ways. First, our research extends knowledge on communication tools by including the use of ESNs, which has resulted a significant antecedent of perceived proximity. We have found in social base theories ground to include ESNs in our research model. Namely, in Social Identity (Tajfel & Turner, 1976) we base the assumption that ESN use is valuable for teleworkers in need to discover and connect with like-minded colleagues, and in Social Presence (Short et al., 1976) we find an argument by which technology can invoke sense of closeness with one another. Thus, we have found that work-from-home employees rely on ESNs to overcome the physical distance with coworkers. This finding contributes to former similar research (van Zoonen et al., 2021a) with data collected after Covid-19 experiment, providing a nuance view to ESN-perceived proximity relation (H1 accepted), whereas in the past, perceived proximity had shown a causal priority over ESN usage. Second, our work shows affirmative causal relation between perceived proximity and teleworkers' affective wellbeing. Perceived proximity is thus a new antecedent of positive telework experiences in long-term, regular work-from-home arrangements. In this sense, the *far-but-close* paradox can now be better understood. According to the chained effects demonstrated in this thesis, the *far-but-close* paradox may not only be explained by shared identity and frequent communication but also by the affective state generated between the dyad.

We also contributed to the *connectivity* paradox (Leonardi et al., 2010) by shifting focus from communication frequency to psychological distance. Instead of focusing on intensity of communications, we put the spotlight in the effective work-from-home connections to manage psychological distance. There seems to be no room for the connectivity paradox in our model. In other words, there is not *too much* connectivity with whom one feels close to, given the benefit in one's affective wellbeing. The previously observed strain derived from communication frequency seem to disappear when perceived proximity is the mediating factor for affective wellbeing.

With regards to the *telecommuting paradox* (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007), previous knowledge on telework relationships noted the detrimental effect telework intensity had on the quality of relationships, and, in turn, it negatively affected happiness at work negatively (Golden, 2006). Our findings, probably influenced by the experienced gained by employees during Covid-19 forced telework (Becker et al., 2022), provide a new positive view of these relationships. In our analysis, it becomes apparent that frequent communications with remote coworkers reduces the psychological distance between the dyad. Based on the data we collected we learned that collective communication platforms (ESNs) are valuable for teleworkers to feel subjectively close to distant others. One of the values observed in ESN usage is the ability to make new connections with coworkers with whom you share an identity. Identity-building activities result in closeness with the similar other. We are thus confident to say it is possible to build close relationships with distant coworkers WFH, at least after Covid-19 WFH experiment. This finding brings new light to previous beliefs about remote work relationships. Our result from H4 confirms coworker perceived proximity improves their affective wellbeing. In other words, telework is good for both employees and employers, provided the

psychological distance between coworkers is short.

This thesis, to the best of our knowledge, it is the first empirical study on the impact of collective voice in teleworkers' outcomes. Our findings contribute to the growing research interest in the mediating effect of employee voice in organizational productivity (Wilkinson et al., 2018). Also, given the predominance of Anglo-American studies on this field of study (Della Torre, 2019), the present empirical research presents new evidence from underexplored contexts (e.g., Spanish firms). A special attention to ICT-based interactions is consistent across the study. This study also contributes to employee voice literature (1) providing new empirical evidence on the usage of social media to express direct employee voice, (2) the current state of collective voice engagements to support the adoption of telework beyond Covid-19, and (3) the impact of employee voice in employee wellbeing in intensive telework contexts. Results from the statistical analysis evidence that indirect voice expression of telework-related topic were irrelevant to employees' wellbeing. Descriptive analysis of the collected data shows an unknown involvement from Unions/worker councils in conversations with management regarding telework adoption matters. With regards to direct voice, our finding was contrary to the initial assumption. Our findings put forward that wellbeing in the future workplace might be viewed as an essential managerial concern. Is the role of voice changing in remote work environments? Further research is needed to answer this question.

5.4 Implications for practice

In a period where remote work has become “the new normal” overnight (Wang et al., 2021) providing employees with positive telework experiences is key for their performance (Golden & Gajendran, 2019). The “telework revolution” is causing traditional employer's office concepts may fall out of use; WFH is becoming a way to attract and retain the right talent to thrive in digitized markets (Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021). This thesis provides new evidence on how remote workers can positively adapt to the new norm. The experienced gained during the pandemic has changed the paradigm of telework (Carillo et al., 2021) and, most importantly, the willingness for employees to continue the practice after the sanitary crisis is over (Labrado et al., 2022; Thompson et al., 2022). This thesis contributes to the design of future workplaces with new valuable information to reconfigure WFH practices, fostering social support in remote/hybrid work environments. Managers can benefit from guidelines to improve productivity and better manage talent through increased engagement (Coenen & Kok, 2014; Mehta & Sharma, 2022).

Future remote work environments need to be reconfigured (Becker et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021). Collaborative workplaces are rapidly evolving around the world and new hybrid work rearrangements are now a global phenomenon (Yang et al., 2022). Taken together, these findings suggest that organizations should closely monitor the wellbeing of their employees during the end of the pandemic period and into the foreseeable *hybrid* future (Lecours et al., 2022; Schifano et al., 2021). The conclusions drawn here provide actionable insights that help organizations better deal with post covid-19 telework scenarios. By understanding the conditions for fruitful affective telework experience, organizations are better able to design and implement telework arrangements. Variables such as the psychological distance to coworkers and ability to have a say in the working arrangements can be key for the acceptance of teleworking programs. Being a flexible employer is an increasing demand from today's key talent. Firms offering a solid remote work experience will see in telework a source of competitive advantage (Aguinis & Burgi-Tian, 2021). Learnings from Covid-19 firm-wide WFH experience has taught us the changes in organizational network dynamics (Yang et al.,

2022). The findings from this thesis show practitioners the goodness in ESN usage for collaboration and innovation through subjective proximity.

Our findings contribute to practitioners in several practical implications. Chiefly, the thesis has found that perceived proximity with a coworker nurtures employee wellbeing while at telework. Secondly, it was found that reliance on some modern firm-wide ICT tools, namely ESNs, contribute to such feelings of being close to a fellow worker. Thirdly, findings suggest that the two core processes of perceived proximity (communication and identity) are significantly related to perceived proximity in pandemic induced telework. Interestingly, the effect of time and extent of telework have turned to be positively related with self-perceptions of productivity and the overall desire of teleworkers to remain in this work arrangement. Fourthly, the high risk of systemic crisis, organizations shall prepare and start developing business continuity plans for such future scenarios (Carillo et al., 2021). The design of such business continuity plans should consider the mitigation of the negative effects of crisis induced telework contexts. Lastly, the findings on voice measurements may open the debate of voice on WFH arrangements. On one side, collective voice did not relate with employee wellbeing. On the other, expressing one's voice on public social media was detrimental to employee wellbeing. The use of public social media for work-related voice purposes had detrimental effects over the affective wellbeing of the participants. The uncontrollable behavior of employees over open, free of charge social media represents a threat to employers' efforts to increase wellbeing of their employees WFH. The unmanaged effect on the wellbeing of the company's talent pool can be a direct threat to the firm's competitive advantage. Rather than wellbeing just being an outcome of (tele)work arrangements, the role of interpersonal relations must strongly be considered to better design relational strategies in the remote workplace.

One of the biggest concerns practitioners have with telework implementation is finding ways to avoid the negative effect in professional isolation, and thus in job performance (Golden & Veiga, 2008). Not feeling connected may impact their ability to interpersonally relate with others, losing reliability on their own knowledge base or ability to collaborate in complex tasks or sharing and refining tacit knowledge are examples of diminished abilities. Practitioners should focus on implementing practices for effective transitioning to telework (Stempel and Siestrup, 2021). To add on the risk of isolation, the levels of negative emotions in the workplace have been deteriorating over the last decade (Gallup, 2021). This baseline situation reinforces the need to find ways for positive emotional states in telework. This study suggests practitioners that perceived proximity has a significant and positive effect on affective wellbeing in the remote workplace. This finding should encourage managers to create opportunities for remote socialization and provide the necessary technological resources to communicate and collaborate remotely. The finding from H4 suggests that, when monitoring organizational ICT configurations, practitioners should shift focus from measurements of hard characteristics (e.g., frequency of usage) to outcomes such as perceived distance, because reduced perceived distance contributes to the affective wellbeing of teleworkers. Providing for positive telework experiences is then crucial to create and maintain the competitive advantage in a globalized world (Avolio et al., 2014). The fact that we have looked at antecedents of perceived proximity such as ESN usage or communication through available ICTs in large organizations provide valuable context-specific evidence. As mentioned before, the development of context-specific telework practices is essential. Such practices should be designed to both attract and retain digital talent and promote employee engagement, motivation, and productivity. For instance, work-from-home team members should be encouraged to nurture workplace relationships and engage with the team and the organization. This can be done by providing a range of remote engagement activities such as virtual informal activities and online networking events.

Companies have long applied social media to connect with actual and potential customers. Social media, a people powered communication engine, has different characteristics of relevant interest to telework environments (CIPD, 2013). When used internally, it builds a sense of belonging to the firm (Bennett et al., 2021); resulting in higher levels of employee commitment and satisfaction. The novelty found in H1 with the ESN usage influence in perceived proximity is crucial for employers transitioning to telework and adjusting the organizational ICTs, and the cultural aspects around it. HRMs should prioritize the importance of bonding through frequent, interactive communication in the workplace (Ruiller et al., 2019). To do so, employers should consider investing in ESN that allows employees to search, post, follow, and unfollow coworkers and communities of their own choosing. This will feed rich network structures, which are necessary for creating affective wellbeing in the workplace, mediated by perceived proximity (Wilson et al. 2008). Restrictive approaches such as not being able to create new posts or requiring authorization to join a community will limit the ability for ESN to connect coworkers, or the employees' desire to use the tool.

Considering the effect that telework is about to play in the digital economy the present research intends to provide actionable insights to avoid employees feeling isolated and disengaged with the employer's organization. Expanding the knowledge about employee voice mechanisms in telework has many employment relation implications. Including (a) whether, implement a telework policy, (b) whether implement a participative practice around telework arrangements, (c) the design of such policy and practice, (c) predicting and planning the impact of such measures, (d) design of communication channels for participations, (e) measuring the effectiveness of the policy and practice. Practically, the findings of this study reveal teleworkers do not action their voice by means of improving the remote workplace affective experience. In other words, current employee voice mechanisms seem not relevant to employee wellbeing of those working from home.

Practitioners should also beware of the evolution in channel usage, rebalancing synchronous/asynchronous communications and reduction of informal interactions WFH. It requires an effort to communicate in virtual environments (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020). On a day at the office, informal encounters account for 75 minutes of the working day. Defining strategies to overcome the lack of unplanned watercooler time would allow remote workers to benefit again from those informal encounters, coaching and mentoring conversations. Finding ways to nurture working relationships is crucial for the performance of jobs in the future of work (Golden et al., 2008).

In sum, the results of this study may be useful for managers and Human Resources personnel in how to make the most out of distributed workforce. This study has implications for the workplace as it highlights the importance of fostering meaningful connections that improve wellbeing at telework. The findings also suggest that companies should consider investing in developing technology enabled social networks, and alternative ways to public social media for employees to express their voice, to ensure an engaging telework experience. The importance of creating a feeling of social connectedness and support among those WFH should be further explored to provide better working conditions. The results of this study can also inform policies and strategies aimed at improving the overall wellbeing of teleworkers.

5.5 Limitations and future direction

This study presents some limitations than need to be considered when interpreting the results. First, the data was collected at a singular time point, making it difficult to observe the dynamism of the studied relationships. The cross-sectional nature of the study allows us to examine associations between the analyzed constructs but, on the other hand, it implies the relationships found cannot infer causality between the variables. Second, the study relied on self-reported measures which may be subject to social desirability bias. Also, we employed a non-probabilistic sampling technique (snowball), thus interpretation of the results should be carefully considered. Future studies should consider longitudinal strategies to clarify whether, for example, coworker perceived proximity WFH is an expected outcome of frequent use of ESNs or, in the other hand it should be considered a dependency for successful ESN implementations. Also, it would enable to investigate the long-term effects of telework. Future studies should also consider the use of other sampling methods.

Recent studies are showing contradictory results in pandemic-induced studies, compared with previous knowledge (Becker et al., 2022). Running a similar study in a non-pandemic telework context could be valuable to better shape Human Resource Management strategies to generate and retain human capital in the new normal economy. A new sample would confirm the strength of the correlations found here; alongside further tests of validity of the communication construct in modern ICT-based processes.

The variable affective wellbeing could be conditioned by the overall exposure to Covid-19 pandemic. It would be interesting for future research to consider the consequences of the pandemic global crisis in the work-life interface. Psychological needs for relatedness are not the same for teleworkers and office workers (Brunelle & Fortin, 2021). Organizations will have to take this into consideration when designing effective working practices for post-Covid times as hybrid work environment will most likely be the norm. We encourage other researchers to investigate the depth of teleworkers experience at work. Interpersonal relationships during telework, become more formal and asynchronous (Yang et al., 2021), at least during Covid-19 forced telework. In this study we have distinguished formal and informal events between coworkers, in a humble attempt to contribute to the knowledge of the communication process in remote work environments. Additionally, in the advent of hybrid forms of work, the study of the effect of non-work-related daily events on affective wellbeing is of relevance. For example, the study of post- Covid-19 work-life balance contexts. Further exploratory research on the outcomes associated with increased informal time during telework is crucial for the management practice to increase social connectedness in the workplace. Teleworkers struggle with the perceptions of others have of them, feeling they must build legitimacy with co-located peers (Fay & Kline, 2012). Informal communications can function to create social presence, coworker liking and better manage activity coordination, which will facilitate teleworkers job satisfaction and subjective wellbeing. Future direction of studies should consider the role of informal communications in work-related outcomes such as productivity or intention to leave. Evidence from this study reveal the low use of technologies for informal type encounters. Further research might be needed on the reasons that may be preventing teleworkers from adopting more creative ways to communicate in the workplace.

The finding from H1 is a novelty in remote communications research. Further research on the role modern ICT platforms (e.g., gamified learning platforms) have on employee and organizational

outcomes is advisable. As seen with ESNs, the implementation of communication technologies is not free of difficulties, despite the advanced technical features it may provide.

Lastly, voice expression on telework environments needs revisiting (Uribetxeberria et al., 2020). Our finding in H5 suggests the use of public social media for work-related voice purposes needs further investigation. The lack of communication authenticity in these open, free of charge platforms (Laumer et al., 2017) may represent a threat to parallel gains in efforts to build wellbeing in WFH, as a source of competitive advantage. Longitudinal studies on the effect of public social media voicing in telework would provide new evidence to further explain what we have unveiled in H5. We couldn't find in our sample precise data about unionization, further studies on the outcomes of indirect voice during telework arrangements are needed.

5.6 Conclusions

This thesis contributes to the HRM research by providing new empirical evidence on the role of perceived proximity and employee voice in shaping telework experiences. The findings from our analysis reveal a new reality is possible in remote forms of work, one in which employees can build strong bonding relationships, despite the geographical distance between them and/ or the frequency and longevity WFH. The study of affective wellbeing of teleworkers is crucial for the understanding of the future workplace. The happy/productive thesis endorses the idea that happy employees are more productive (Blahopoulou et al., 2022). Perceived proximity seems to be crucial for envisioning a teleworker that experiences affective welfare. This study provides practical advice on how to effectively collaborate in telework contexts ensuring positive outcomes. The use of ESNs and the processes of workmate communication and identification are key for perceived proximity, which in turn benefits affective wellbeing. Employee wellbeing is well known to increase job performance (Wright et al., 2007) and organizational commitment (Grant et al., 2013). Human Resource Managers will find that the link between perceived proximity and wellbeing is a crucial asset to attract valuable workforce and increase organizational outcomes during the “telework revolution”.

Our intent was to expand the knowledge about wellbeing at telework by analyzing the effect of perceived proximity and employee voice mechanisms through quantitative research. To achieve this, the Perceived Proximity Model (Wilson et al., 2008) was applied and participants were asked to rate items related to this model in relation to a distant coworker of choice. Additionally, the Wellbeing Questionnaire (Warr et al., 1990) was used, in which participants had to rate items on how they had felt in the last two weeks. Employee voice was measured using scales previously used by Barnes et al. (2019); participants had to rate items relating to Union contributions to telework adoption, communication channels used by Unions, employee participation in Union online activities, and the use of public social media platforms for direct voice purposes.

542 participants (284 were line managers and 258 staff) were randomly selected using a snowballing sampling method and asked to fill out an online survey published on the LinkedIn professional network. Furthermore, they were asked to share the survey with other teleworkers (from or outside their company network). A demographic breakdown was provided in terms of age, gender, caring responsibilities, study level, years of tenure in the current employer.

This dissertation has been structured in five sections. Firstly, the introduction to the telework concept, the research question and the gap of knowledge intended to cover. Secondly, we described the main theories and previous knowledge relevant to the research question and the formulation of hypotheses to be empirically tested. Chapter 3 covered the methods to be used in the empirical study. Chapter 4 presented the statistics results and analysis. Finally, in chapter 5 the conclusions were presented, theoretical and managerial implications of the findings were discussed, and the limitations of the study and directions for future research were discussed.

We provided insights into the role of social connectedness in affecting telework experiences. Our research shows that the closer a teleworker symbolically feels to distant coworker, the higher the positive impact in his/her affective wellbeing. This is a novelty in the study of perceived proximity. Previous studies have evidenced the higher psychological need that teleworkers have for relatedness (Golden & Veiga, 2005). Some have noted the positive effect of coworker connectivity in job satisfaction (Brunelle & Fortin, 2021), but the link between perceived proximity and affective wellbeing was not explored. Increased wellbeing is a well-known antecedent of job performance (Wright et al., 2007) and organizational commitment (Grant et al., 2013). Practitioners will find in this result a source of increased competitiveness. Human Resource Managers will find in positive telework experience an asset to attract and retain valuable workforce. The results of this quantitative study also suggest that frequent communications and close relationships with a coworker improve wellbeing while at telework. In other words, the close you feel to distant coworker, the better you feel. A novelty found in the study is the mediating effect the use of social networking sites, such as ESN, have on promoting relatedness with a distant other. Thus, ESN use also tested positive for perceived proximity. The ability to find and connect with similar ones in a remote work environment is a must-have resource in future hybrid organizations (Abdulgalimov et al., 2020).

Data obtained from the study reveal that collective voice mechanisms to support telework adoption did not directly impact affective wellbeing. Previous studies are inconclusive on the effect of voice in wellbeing (Uribebarria et al., 2021; Wilkinson et al., 2023), especially if Unions are not actively engaged with management (della Torre, 2019). In the case of collective agreements covering telework conditions, few companies have embarked this negotiation journey (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020). This lack of regulation was evident in the data we obtained. Maybe this lack of involvement is one of the reasons that explain the low impact in affective wellbeing. With regards to direct voice, we found public social media voicing produced unexpected results on affective wellbeing. What holds true for face-to-face or internal social media voice channels (e.g., positive impact on job satisfaction) may not be applicable to uncontrolled voice expression on public social media.

Theoretically, the findings of this dissertation contribute to the literature of remote communication, social interaction and telework by providing new empirical evidence on the role of perceived proximity and employee voice in shaping telework experience. In terms of managerial implications, the results of this study provide practical advice on how to ensure positive telework experiences and how to promote employee voice in telework contexts.

Regarding the *far-but-close* paradox (Wilson et al., 2008), results from this study confirm that psychological bonds between remote coworkers can be created and consolidated in work-from-home settings, despite the lack of face-to-face interactions. The use of ESNs, workmate communication and identification allow to build engagement and commitment in a remote workforce. The ability to find and “follow” like minded colleagues in the workplace is a needed resource in the future of work

(Abdulgalimov et al., 2020). Collaborative work environments are rapidly growing as hybrid work is rearranging the way knowledge workers work (Yang et al., 2022). The conclusions drawn from this thesis are actionable insights for practitioners that must design and implement telework programs. Decisions about working conditions, technology requirements or cultural attributes associated with technology usage (e.g., open, collaborative, supportive) will impact differently the outcomes of telework.

The limitations of this dissertation are twofold. Firstly, the data was collected at a singular time point, making it difficult to observe the dynamism of the studied relationships. Secondly, the study relied on self-reported measures which may be subject to social desirability bias.

In terms of future research, this study provides a starting point for future investigations. Firstly, future research should focus on exploring the dynamism of the studied relationships, as well as the moderating effect of other variables, such as gender, tenure, and job type, on the relationships. Secondly, future research should focus on exploring the role of employee voice in other telework outcomes. Equally interesting would be running longitudinal examinations of the influential role employee voice has on affective wellbeing. These longitudinal studies would help clarify some of the findings in our study (H5 and H6 mainly). Thirdly, future research should focus on exploring the role of other ICT-based interactions, such as instant messaging, in perceived proximity and employee voice.

This thesis has provided significant theoretical and practical implications to the study of telework. As a result, future research should continue to investigate the antecedents of telework wellbeing, the impact of ICT-based interactions and the role of employee voice in telework contexts. Thus, this study paved the way to a better understanding of what makes telework successful.

ANNEXES

ANNEX I – TABLES AND GRAPHS

Table 10 - Adaptation to the statements used in the communication scale.

Statements used by O’Leary et al. (2014)	Adaptation to be used in the present study
“By phone”	“Online formal meetings (no video)”
“Face to face”	“Face to face formal meetings in the office”
“By email”	“Email”
“By instant message”	“Instant messaging (MS Teams, Whatsapp,..)”
“Social Media (Twitter, Whatsapp)”	
“Other communication media (Please specify)”	
	“Informal meetings organized by the employer”
	“Informal events organized by us”
	“Videoconference formal meetings”

Source: Own elaboration

Figure 12 -Telework longevity funnel graph

Source: Own elaboration

Figure 13 - Telework intensity funnel graph

Source: Own elaboration

Figure 14 - Perceived Proximity measure items

Describe how you think and feel about this colleague using the pull-down menus for each of the following statements.

- I feel close to Distant Colleague.
- Even when we are not working in the same place, I still feel close to Distant Colleague.
- I feel closer to Distant Colleague than the actual physical distance would suggest.
- I have a warm feeling about Distant Colleague.
- Physical distance doesn't matter in my relationship with Distant Colleague.
- When I think of Distant Colleague, the distance between the two of us generally seems small.
- With regard to work, I often think about Distant Colleague.
- Even when we're not actively working on something, I feel close to Distant Colleague.
- Psychologically, Distant Colleague feels close.
- I feel connected to Distant Colleague.
- Even when we haven't been in the same place, it hasn't seemed like I was far from Distant Colleague.
- When I think of Distant Colleague, she/he seems close.

The pull-down menus included five choices from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

Source: O'Leary et al. 2014. Appendix A, A2

Figure 15 - Perceived Proximity items used in questionnaire

statements?

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I feel close to this colleague	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Even when we are not working in the same place, I still feel close to this colleague	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel closer to this colleague than the actual physical distance would suggest	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Psychologically, this colleague feels close	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When I think of this colleague, he/she seems close	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel connected to this colleague	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Source: Own elaboration, extracted from Google Forms

Figure 16 - Results from workmate communication scale

Source: Own elaboration

ANNEX II - QUESTIONNAIRE

Work-From-Home and Wellbeing

We greatly appreciate your assistance with this scientific research undertaken by the Department of Organizational and Marketing studies at Complutense University of Madrid. Your answers will remain anonymous and will only be used for scientific purposes. The survey will take you approximately 10-15 minutes to complete.

*Obligatorio

Section 1. About your current employer and your working environment

Let's start. The next few questions address your role as a worker and your home-office environment

1. 1. What's your current employer's sector of activity?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing
- Mining
- Construction
- Manufacturing
- Transportation, Communications, Electric, Gas and Sanitary service
- Wholesale Trade
- Retail Trade
- Finance, Insurance and Real Estate
- Services
- Public Administration

2. 2. How big is your company? (Number of employees)

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Between 1 and 10
- Between 11 and 50
- Between 51 and 250
- More than 250

3. 3. Which of the following best describes your employment status?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Permanent full time
- Permanent part time
- Fixed-term/ Temporary
- Agency contract
- Freelancer/ contractor
- Civil servant

4. 4. How long have you worked for your current employer? (Number of years)

5. 5. On average, how many days a month do you currently work from from home?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- None
- 1-5
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 16-20
- 20+

6. 6. How long have you been working from home?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- I haven't yet
- Under 6 months
- 6-12 months
- 13-24 months
- More than 24 months

7. 7. Next, for each of the following, please state how things have been going on in the last two weeks:

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Never	Sometimes	Often	Almost all the time
Have you ever felt annoyed with someone?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever felt very lonely or remote from other people?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever felt that things were going your way?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever felt very worried?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever felt pleased because you've got good friends?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever been afraid of what might happen?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever felt particularly excited or interested in something?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever felt depressed or very unhappy?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever been full of energy?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever felt really tired?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have you ever felt so relentless that you couldn't sit long in a chair?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

**Have you ever felt that
you were really
enjoying yourself?**

**Have you ever felt
really cheerful?**

**Have you ever felt like
crying?**

**Have you ever felt on
top of the world?**

**Have you ever felt
confident about the
future?**

**Have you ever felt
bored?**

**Have you ever felt
pleased about having
accomplished
something?**

8. Please indicate how frequently you experience the following with regards to your work:

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Very infrequently	Infrequently	Occasionally	Frequently	Very frequently
I miss out on activities and meetings that could enhance my career	<input type="radio"/>				
I miss out opportunities to be mentored	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel out of the loop	<input type="radio"/>				
I miss face-to-face contact with coworkers	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel isolated	<input type="radio"/>				
I miss the emotional support of coworkers	<input type="radio"/>				
I miss the emotional interaction with others	<input type="radio"/>				

9. Lastly; at work, do you supervise the work of other people?

Marca solo un óvalo.

Yes

No

Section 2: Quality of relations at work, communications and technology

The following questions have been used in former studies about the quality of relations at work, and the impact of information technology

10. 10. Think of a remote coworker. Describe how do you feel about this colleague. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I feel close to this colleague	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Even when we are not working in the same place, I still feel close to this colleague	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel closer to this colleague than the actual physical distance would suggest	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Psychologically, this colleague feels close	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When I think of this colleague, he/she seems close	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel connected to this colleague	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11. 11. With the same colleague in mind, to what extent do you share similarities with him/her?

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Not like me at all	Not like me	Somewhat like me	Exactly like me	I don't know
Age	<input type="radio"/>				
Values	<input type="radio"/>				
Gender	<input type="radio"/>				
Commitment to work	<input type="radio"/>				
Hobbies, taste	<input type="radio"/>				

12. 12. With the same colleague in mind, how often do you communicate with him/her on an average week?

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Never	Less than once a week	1-4 times a week	Once a day	2-5 times a day	More than 5 times a day
Videoconference formal meetings	<input type="radio"/>					
Online formal meetings (no video)	<input type="radio"/>					
Face-to-face formal meetings in the office	<input type="radio"/>					
Instant messaging (MS Teams, Whatsapp,..)	<input type="radio"/>					
Email	<input type="radio"/>					
Informal events organized by employer	<input type="radio"/>					
Informal events organized by us	<input type="radio"/>					

13. 13. Now, a few questions about your usage of social media at work. Does your current employer provide a social networking platform (eg. Yammer, Oracle, ..) . If your answer is "No" skip to question 16.

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Yes and I use it
- Yes, but I hardly use it
- No

14. 14. To what extent do you agree with the following about the benefits of its usage?

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
The social network contributes to feeling closer to fellow workers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have discovered new coworkers with whom I share ideas, hobbies, ...	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The social network helps build a sense of belonging to the company	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My line manager supports me in the use of the social network	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My line manager uses the social network	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

15. 15. Now we would like to know your general impression about the effectiveness of enterprise social media as a communication channel with:

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Unions and affiliated members	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Workers representatives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Company management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coworkers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Section 3 - Work-from-home and employee voice

In this section you will be asked about the usage of different communication channels to express your voice and opinion about working arrangements.

16. 16. Are you affiliated to a trade union/ worker council?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Yes
- No
- I'd rather not say

17. 17. Based on your own knowledge; is telework adoption part of collective bargaining in your company?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- No
- I don't know
- It's currently being negotiated
- Yes, it's a company-specific agreement
- Yes, it's a sector-wide agreement

18. 18. How frequently do you reach out to unions or worker councils on the following subjects related to telework adoption?

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Gain information about my rights	<input type="radio"/>				
Gain information about union/council campaigns	<input type="radio"/>				
Gain information about what's happening in my sector	<input type="radio"/>				
To raise a complaint	<input type="radio"/>				
To make a suggestion	<input type="radio"/>				

19. 19. Now, to what extent do you feel unions/ worker councils contribute to improving the following work-from-home arrangements:

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Home office ergonomics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Worklife balance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The "right to disconnect"	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Teleworker privacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Equality of gender and minority groups	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Training and professional development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Digital communication amongst co-workers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

20. 20. How frequently do you receive useful information about working arrangements or union/work council activities?

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Email	<input type="radio"/>				
Digital Bulletin	<input type="radio"/>				
Company Social Network (Yammer, Oracle,...)	<input type="radio"/>				
Public social media (Facebook, Instagram, ...)	<input type="radio"/>				
Personal relations with an affiliated officer	<input type="radio"/>				
Web page	<input type="radio"/>				
Whatsapp/Telegram	<input type="radio"/>				
Meetings with workers representatives	<input type="radio"/>				
Other communication media	<input type="radio"/>				

21. 21. How frequently do you use the following social media to express your dissent with working arrangements, make suggestions, take part in decision making processes and/or share your professional aspirations?

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Linkedin	<input type="radio"/>				
Glassdoor	<input type="radio"/>				
Facebook	<input type="radio"/>				
Youtube	<input type="radio"/>				
Twitter	<input type="radio"/>				
Whatsapp/ Telegram	<input type="radio"/>				
Instagram	<input type="radio"/>				
Vimeo	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

22. 22. How frequently do you take part in any of the following activities organized by unions or work councils?

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often
Online campaigns (eg. Change.org)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Surf their web page	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
"Like" the account (Facebook, Twitter,...)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Post messages directed to union/work council account	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Comment on union/work council posts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Share the link to union/work council account with my others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Attend online meetings and events	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Final thoughts

We are reaching the end of the survey. The following questions address your summary valuation of your work-from-home experience

23. 23. If you were free to choose, how often would you prefer to work from home?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- I wouldn't like to work from home
- 1-2 days a month
- 1 day a week
- 2 days a week
- 3 days a week
- 4 days a week
- 5 days a week

24. 24. Finally, please help us rate your overall experience working from home:

Marca solo un óvalo por fila.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
The company's communication and participation has improved	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel more productive working from home	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel more autonomous to perform my work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel connected to the company	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel identified with the mission, vision and values of the company	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel enabled to use the online technology required to perform my job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I need additional training on the use of remote work technologies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Sociodemographics

Before submitting your answer, we would like to collect some information about you. Please help us analyze the results of the survey by providing some general information about yourself. The information you provide will be completely confidential

25. What's your age? (Number)

26. What's your gender?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- I'd rather not say

27. Your country of residence:

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Germany
- Austria
- Belgium
- Cipprus
- England
- Irland
- Italy
- Finland
- France
- Greece
- Netherlands
- Portugal
- Spain
- Stonia

28. Do you live with a partner? *

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Yes
- No
- I'd rather not say

29. How many children under 18 are living in your household? (Number)

30. (Aside from dependent children), do you have any caring responsibilities for anyone due to illness, age or disability?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Yes
- No

31. What's your highest degree of studies completed?

Marca solo un óvalo.

- Primary Education
- Secondary Education
- Higher Education
- Master's degree
- PhD

32. That's it! Your answers will help us complete this scientific research. THANK YOU! If you feel we have omitted relevant information that needs gathering, please feel free to state your comment below.

Este contenido no ha sido creado ni aprobado por Google.

Google Formularios

Annex III – MEASUREMENT MODEL DESCRIPTION

Estimated model in lavaan syntax

- WELLBEING ~ D_VOICE + I_VOICE + PROXIMITY
- PROXIMITY ~ COMMUNICATION + IDENTIFICATION + ENTERPSNET

Latent variable definitions

- WELLBEING =~ WELLB_01 + WELLB_02 + WELLB_03 + WELLB_04 + WELLB_05 + WELLB_06 + WELLB_07 + WELLB_08 + WELLB_09 + WELLB_10 + WELLB_11 + WELLB_12 + WELLB_13 + WELLB_14 + WELLB_15 + WELLB_16 + WELLB_17 + WELLB_18
- I_VOICE =~ Q20 + Q22
- D_VOICE =~ D_VOICE_01 + D_VOICE_03 + D_VOICE_04 + D_VOICE_05 + D_VOICE_06 + D_VOICE_07
- PROXIMITY =~ PERC_PROX_01 + PERC_PROX_02 + PERC_PROX_03 + PERC_PROX_04

First order constructs

- Q20 =~ IV_CHANNEL_01 + IV_CHANNEL_02 + IV_CHANNEL_03 + IV_CHANNEL_04 + IV_CHANNEL_05 + IV_CHANNEL_06 + IV_CHANNEL_07 + IV_CHANNEL_08 + IV_CHANNEL_09
- Q22 =~ IV_PARTIC_01 + IV_PARTIC_03 + IV_PARTIC_04 + IV_PARTIC_05
- COMMUNICATION =~ PP_COMMUN_01 + PP_COMMUN_02 + PP_COMMUN_04 + PP_COMMUN_05
- IDENTIFICATION =~ PP_IDENTITY_02 + PP_IDENTITY_04 + PP_IDENTITY_05
- ENTERPSNET =~ SM_EFFEC_01 + SM_EFFEC_02 + SM_EFFEC_03 + SM_EFFEC_04 + SM_BENEF_01 + SM_BENEF_02 + SM_BENEF_03 + SM_BENEF_04 + SM_BENEF_05
- WELLBEING ~~ WELLBEING
- D_VOICE ~~ D_VOICE
- I_VOICE ~~ I_VOICE
- PROXIMITY ~~ PROXIMITY
- Q20 ~~ Q20
- Q22 ~~ Q22
- COMMUNICATION ~~ COMMUNICATION
- IDENTIFICATION ~~ IDENTIFICATION
- ENTERPSNET ~~ ENTERPSNET

Annex IV – LAVAAN SUMMARY FUNCTION OUTCOME

lavaan 0.6.14 ended normally after 158 iterations

Estimator	ML	
Optimization method	NLMINB	
Number of model parameters	189	
	Used	Total
Number of observations	540	542
Number of missing patterns	105	

Model Test User Model:

Test statistic	4463.242
Degrees of freedom	1521
P-value (Chi-square)	0.000

Parameter Estimates:

Standard errors	Standard
Information	Observed
Observed information based on	Hessian

Latent Variables:

	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)
WELLBEING =~				
WELLB_01	1.000			
WELLB_02	1.541	0.242	6.368	0.000
WELLB_03	2.218	0.308	7.205	0.000
WELLB_04	1.595	0.242	6.577	0.000
WELLB_05	1.409	0.237	5.936	0.000
WELLB_06	1.647	0.253	6.515	0.000
WELLB_07	2.562	0.351	7.309	0.000
WELLB_08	1.873	0.263	7.116	0.000
WELLB_09	2.683	0.359	7.475	0.000
WELLB_10	1.589	0.248	6.412	0.000
WELLB_11	0.767	0.183	4.191	0.000
WELLB_12	2.711	0.365	7.432	0.000
WELLB_13	2.902	0.382	7.589	0.000
WELLB_14	1.444	0.228	6.323	0.000
WELLB_15	2.063	0.297	6.952	0.000
WELLB_16	2.610	0.355	7.358	0.000
WELLB_17	1.412	0.234	6.043	0.000
WELLB_18	2.159	0.300	7.195	0.000
I_VOICE =~				
Q20	1.000			
Q22	0.752	0.125	6.025	0.000
D_VOICE =~				
D_VOICE_01	1.000			
D_VOICE_03	0.936	0.087	10.787	0.000
D_VOICE_04	0.851	0.079	10.765	0.000
D_VOICE_05	0.753	0.080	9.412	0.000
D_VOICE_06	1.592	0.156	10.218	0.000
D_VOICE_07	1.014	0.092	11.013	0.000
PROXIMITY =~				
PERC_PROX_01	1.000			
PERC_PROX_02	1.014	0.027	37.778	0.000
PERC_PROX_03	0.786	0.046	16.939	0.000
PERC_PROX_04	0.888	0.035	25.269	0.000
Q20 =~				
IV_CHANNEL_01	1.000			
IV_CHANNEL_02	1.004	0.076	13.170	0.000
IV_CHANNEL_03	0.793	0.066	12.050	0.000
IV_CHANNEL_04	0.773	0.060	12.924	0.000
IV_CHANNEL_05	0.924	0.073	12.682	0.000

IV_CHANNEL_06	1.018	0.072	14.050	0.000
IV_CHANNEL_07	0.927	0.073	12.778	0.000
IV_CHANNEL_08	0.877	0.069	12.628	0.000
IV_CHANNEL_09	0.864	0.066	13.118	0.000
Q22 =~				
IV_PARTIC_01	1.000			
IV_PARTIC_03	1.123	0.100	11.206	0.000
IV_PARTIC_04	0.638	0.059	10.775	0.000
IV_PARTIC_05	0.890	0.081	10.957	0.000
COMMUNICATION =~				
PP_COMMUN_01	1.000			
PP_COMMUN_02	1.239	0.169	7.347	0.000
PP_COMMUN_04	1.268	0.209	6.071	0.000
PP_COMMUN_05	1.445	0.215	6.716	0.000
IDENTIFICATION =~				
PP_IDENTITY_02	1.000			
PP_IDENTITY_04	0.917	0.132	6.931	0.000
PP_IDENTITY_05	0.829	0.113	7.352	0.000
ENTERPSNET =~				
SM_EFFEC_01	1.000			
SM_EFFEC_02	1.028	0.092	11.129	0.000
SM_EFFEC_03	1.093	0.101	10.791	0.000
SM_EFFEC_04	1.151	0.103	11.211	0.000
SM_BENEF_01	1.225	0.115	10.620	0.000
SM_BENEF_02	1.014	0.102	9.911	0.000
SM_BENEF_03	1.122	0.107	10.521	0.000
SM_BENEF_04	0.918	0.115	7.960	0.000
SM_BENEF_05	0.920	0.116	7.912	0.000

Regressions:

	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)
WELLBEING ~				
D_VOICE	-0.064	0.027	-2.365	0.018
I_VOICE	0.043	0.025	1.694	0.090
PROXIMITY	0.087	0.015	5.710	0.000
PROXIMITY ~				
COMMUNICATION	0.478	0.094	5.106	0.000
IDENTIFICATION	0.472	0.131	3.607	0.000
ENTERPSNET	0.211	0.071	2.964	0.003

Covariances:

	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)
I_VOICE ~~				
D_VOICE	0.126	0.024	5.308	0.000
COMMUNICATION	-0.008	0.021	-0.404	0.686
IDENTIFICATION	-0.010	0.015	-0.705	0.481
ENTERPSNET	0.078	0.030	2.587	0.010
D_VOICE ~~				
COMMUNICATION	-0.005	0.019	-0.267	0.789
IDENTIFICATION	0.014	0.013	1.066	0.287
ENTERPSNET	0.043	0.024	1.807	0.071
COMMUNICATION ~~				
IDENTIFICATION	0.044	0.020	2.160	0.031
ENTERPSNET	0.087	0.038	2.280	0.023
IDENTIFICATION ~~				
ENTERPSNET	0.097	0.028	3.447	0.001

Intercepts:

	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)
.WELLB_01	3.394	0.027	125.324	0.000
.WELLB_02	3.279	0.034	97.832	0.000
.WELLB_03	2.700	0.034	78.319	0.000
.WELLB_04	3.103	0.033	92.911	0.000
.WELLB_05	3.037	0.034	88.085	0.000

.WELLB_06	3.126	0.034	90.688	0.000
.WELLB_07	2.511	0.036	70.608	0.000
.WELLB_08	3.384	0.031	108.360	0.000
.WELLB_09	2.312	0.034	67.351	0.000
.WELLB_10	2.784	0.034	81.020	0.000
.WELLB_11	3.364	0.033	102.531	0.000
.WELLB_12	2.091	0.035	60.225	0.000
.WELLB_13	2.315	0.034	67.933	0.000
.WELLB_14	3.411	0.032	105.834	0.000
.WELLB_15	1.776	0.034	52.966	0.000
.WELLB_16	2.445	0.037	66.103	0.000
.WELLB_17	3.127	0.034	90.672	0.000
.WELLB_18	2.686	0.033	82.280	0.000
.D_VOICE_01	1.506	0.042	36.078	0.000
.D_VOICE_03	1.182	0.027	44.481	0.000
.D_VOICE_04	1.140	0.026	44.429	0.000
.D_VOICE_05	1.213	0.028	43.186	0.000
.D_VOICE_06	1.804	0.053	34.226	0.000
.D_VOICE_07	1.190	0.028	42.123	0.000
.PERC_PROX_01	3.712	0.041	89.819	0.000
.PERC_PROX_02	3.636	0.042	87.276	0.000
.PERC_PROX_03	3.163	0.048	65.422	0.000
.PERC_PROX_04	3.494	0.043	80.624	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_01	2.503	0.058	43.429	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_02	2.017	0.054	37.343	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_03	1.651	0.046	35.884	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_04	1.495	0.040	37.264	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_05	1.761	0.050	35.354	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_06	1.652	0.048	34.760	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_07	1.545	0.048	31.957	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_08	1.647	0.047	35.068	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_09	1.675	0.044	38.205	0.000
.IV_PARTIC_01	1.358	0.032	42.267	0.000
.IV_PARTIC_03	1.265	0.029	43.619	0.000
.IV_PARTIC_04	1.081	0.016	67.939	0.000
.IV_PARTIC_05	1.118	0.019	57.569	0.000
.PP_COMMUN_01	2.826	0.057	49.415	0.000
.PP_COMMUN_02	2.821	0.062	45.170	0.000
.PP_COMMUN_04	3.973	0.067	59.081	0.000
.PP_COMMUN_05	3.959	0.064	61.478	0.000
.PP_IDENTITY_02	2.990	0.028	105.883	0.000
.PP_IDENTITY_04	3.369	0.030	112.058	0.000
.PP_IDENTITY_05	2.469	0.032	78.060	0.000
.SM_EFFEC_01	2.666	0.065	40.974	0.000
.SM_EFFEC_02	2.702	0.065	41.591	0.000
.SM_EFFEC_03	3.190	0.068	46.796	0.000
.SM_EFFEC_04	3.378	0.064	53.080	0.000
.SM_BENEF_01	3.006	0.066	45.334	0.000
.SM_BENEF_02	2.695	0.061	44.171	0.000
.SM_BENEF_03	3.106	0.064	48.843	0.000
.SM_BENEF_04	2.793	0.074	37.932	0.000
.SM_BENEF_05	2.847	0.074	38.373	0.000
.WELLBEING	0.000			
I_VOICE	0.000			
D_VOICE	0.000			
.PROXIMITY	0.000			
.Q20	0.000			
.Q22	0.000			
COMMUNICATION	0.000			
IDENTIFICATION	0.000			
ENTERPSNET	0.000			

Variances:

	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)
.WELLBEING	0.040	0.010	3.869	0.000
.D_VOICE	0.243	0.041	5.856	0.000
.I_VOICE	0.273	0.058	4.690	0.000
.PROXIMITY	0.578	0.047	12.180	0.000
.Q20	0.393	0.064	6.107	0.000
.Q22	0.010	0.020	0.491	0.623
.COMMUNICATION	0.395	0.090	4.377	0.000
.IDENTIFICATION	0.192	0.034	5.724	0.000
.ENTERPSNET	0.584	0.098	5.955	0.000
.WELLB_01	0.348	0.022	16.130	0.000
.WELLB_02	0.494	0.031	15.886	0.000
.WELLB_03	0.412	0.027	15.321	0.000
.WELLB_04	0.481	0.031	15.739	0.000
.WELLB_05	0.547	0.034	16.071	0.000
.WELLB_06	0.511	0.032	15.759	0.000
.WELLB_07	0.377	0.025	14.784	0.000
.WELLB_08	0.360	0.024	15.259	0.000
.WELLB_09	0.301	0.021	14.225	0.000
.WELLB_10	0.516	0.032	15.869	0.000
.WELLB_11	0.553	0.034	16.300	0.000
.WELLB_12	0.308	0.022	13.935	0.000
.WELLB_13	0.234	0.018	12.879	0.000
.WELLB_14	0.462	0.029	15.880	0.000
.WELLB_15	0.405	0.027	15.235	0.000
.WELLB_16	0.419	0.028	14.998	0.000
.WELLB_17	0.547	0.034	16.026	0.000
.WELLB_18	0.355	0.023	15.203	0.000
.D_VOICE_01	0.677	0.045	15.174	0.000
.D_VOICE_03	0.160	0.013	12.146	0.000
.D_VOICE_04	0.171	0.013	13.092	0.000
.D_VOICE_05	0.277	0.019	14.655	0.000
.D_VOICE_06	0.854	0.061	13.989	0.000
.D_VOICE_07	0.170	0.014	11.761	0.000
.PERC_PROX_01	0.118	0.014	8.692	0.000
.PERC_PROX_02	0.110	0.014	8.111	0.000
.PERC_PROX_03	0.757	0.048	15.644	0.000
.PERC_PROX_04	0.374	0.026	14.513	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_01	1.016	0.070	14.462	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_02	0.802	0.057	14.025	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_03	0.650	0.045	14.463	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_04	0.419	0.030	13.983	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_05	0.692	0.048	14.267	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_06	0.457	0.035	13.040	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_07	0.604	0.043	13.888	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_08	0.606	0.043	14.145	0.000
.IV_CHANNEL_09	0.479	0.034	13.886	0.000
.IV_PARTIC_01	0.369	0.026	14.149	0.000
.IV_PARTIC_03	0.228	0.018	12.621	0.000
.IV_PARTIC_04	0.064	0.005	12.369	0.000
.IV_PARTIC_05	0.066	0.007	9.171	0.000
.PP_COMMUN_01	1.333	0.102	13.125	0.000
.PP_COMMUN_02	1.452	0.120	12.071	0.000
.PP_COMMUN_04	1.758	0.139	12.640	0.000
.PP_COMMUN_05	1.368	0.132	10.396	0.000
.PP_IDENTITY_02	0.232	0.029	7.932	0.000
.PP_IDENTITY_04	0.320	0.030	10.706	0.000
.PP_IDENTITY_05	0.394	0.030	13.040	0.000
.SM_EFFEC_01	0.710	0.070	10.127	0.000
.SM_EFFEC_02	0.672	0.068	9.886	0.000
.SM_EFFEC_03	0.726	0.071	10.280	0.000
.SM_EFFEC_04	0.474	0.048	9.872	0.000
.SM_BENEF_01	0.481	0.054	8.897	0.000

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